

Orbiting Earth in the spaceship, I saw how beautiful our planet is. People, let us preserve and increase this beauty, not destroy it!

– Yuri Gagarin

Markus Fleschutz PhD 2024

Economical and Environmental Evaluation of Non-Residential Demand Response in the European Transition to Zero-Carbon Energy

Markus Fleschutz

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Economical and Environmental Evaluation of Non-Residential Demand Response in the European Transition to Zero-Carbon Energy

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Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)
by
Markus Fleschutz

Supervisors: Dr. Michael D. Murphy
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Marco Braun

Department of Process, Energy, and Transport Engineering
Faculty of Engineering and Science

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Declaration of Authorship

This is to certify that all work contained in this thesis is my own and has not been submitted for another degree, either at Munster Technological University, or elsewhere. All external references and sources are clearly acknowledged and identified within the contents. I have read and understood the regulations of Munster Technological University concerning plagiarism.

Markus Fleschutz

ORCID: 0000-0002-8516-9635

AUTHOR

Dr. Michael D. Murphy

ORCID: 0000-0002-4269-2581

SUPERVISOR 1

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Marco Braun

ORCID: 0000-0003-1598-3671

SUPERVISOR 2

Abstract

To meet climate objectives, major energy consumers with local multi-energy systems (L-MESs) must transition to renewable energy sources soon. The variability of renewable energies requires increased operational flexibility for integration. In this context, demand response (DR), a strategy in which electricity consumers adjust their load profiles in response to incentives, has become crucial, offering cost-effective flexibility. It supports L-MESs in integrating renewable energy, reducing decarbonization costs, and enhancing resilience. However, quantifying the economic DR potentials for L-MESs under carbon emission constraints is complex, especially when considering investment options in distributed energy resources. This complexity hinders the rapid adoption of DR programs and the investment in distributed energy resources. Addressing this issue, this thesis introduces methods and tools for the economic and environmental evaluation of non-residential DR, applying them to real-world case studies.

To assess the environmental impact of DR, electricity carbon emission factors (CEFs) are required. There are two types of CEFs: average grid-mix CEFs and marginal CEFs. The first experimental study introduced methods for calculating both types of CEF for European electricity systems and applied them to data from 20 European countries for 2017–2019. Based on the CEFs, simulations of standardized price-based daily load shifts revealed that carbon emissions increased in 8 of the 20 countries, averaging a 2.1% rise. Load shifts based on marginal CEFs reduced average emissions by 35%, but with 56% lower monetary savings compared to price-based shifts. Further simulations at varying carbon price levels analyzed the impact of carbon pricing on emissions. The results confirmed that, with adequate carbon pricing, price-based DR could effectively enhance both economic and environmental outcomes. *Elmada*, a novel open-source Python package, was developed by the author to integrate these CEF calculation methods, enhancing its utility in environmental assessments.

The open-source tool Demand Response Analysis Framework (DRAF) was developed in Python, focusing on optimizing the design and operation of energy technologies. It considers aspects such as demand-side flexibility, electrification, and renewable energy sources. DRAF quantifies the potential for decarbonization and cost reduction using multi-objective mixed-integer linear programming. It provides decision-makers of L-MESs with optimal scenarios in terms of costs, carbon emissions, or Pareto efficiency. Supporting all steps of the energy system optimization process, DRAF includes functionalities ranging from time series analysis to interactive plotting and data export. It features several component templates for easy initiation, while also allowing expansive modeling possibilities through a generic model generator.

DRAF was applied to various non-residential case studies: In a detailed case study, the value of demand-side flexibility for decarbonizing a German beverage company’s L-MES was quantified. The optimal synthesis, design, and operation were identified, considering self-consumption optimization, peak shaving, and DR based on hourly prices and CEFs. Vehicle-to-X for electrical industrial forklifts, power-to-heat at multiple temperatures, wind turbines, photovoltaic systems, and energy storage systems were considered. Novel metrics to evaluate the intensity of price-based and CEF-based DR were proposed and applied. The results revealed that flexibility usage reduced decarbonization costs by 19–80% depending on electricity and carbon removal prices. Furthermore, it reduced total annual costs, operational carbon footprint, energy-weighted average prices and CEFs, as well as fossil energy dependency. The results also suggested that achieving net-zero operational carbon emissions for L-MESs required flexibility, which, in an economic case, is provided by a combination of different flexible technologies and storage systems that complement each other. In an industrial case study, the scheduling of two cement mills and storages were optimized under two DR programs resulting in a 13% annual electricity cost reduction in a real-time vs time-of-use pricing scenario. Another study highlighted the impact of fixed peak-demand grid fees on industrial DR, revealing a conflict between demand flattening and incentives for DR, energy storage, and renewable sources. Additionally, a case study on green hydrogen import hubs demonstrated the importance of considering landing interruptions within the design stage of hydrogen hubs, to increase its resilience through on-site flexibility.

A final study analyzed the use of time series aggregation (TSA) for reducing complexity in L-MES models. It explored hidden costs for investors resulting from TSA application in designing flexible and decarbonized MESs. These costs were quantified by backtesting the TSA-based design with unaggregated time series. Additionally, the study assessed the impact of carbon removal prices on L-MES design and compared the effects of using marginal CEFs instead of grid-mix CEFs on TSA’s efficacy. The findings indicated that with highly ambitious emission reduction targets, TSA can lead to backtesting errors over 10%. Thus, TSA should be applied cautiously in low carbon L-MES contexts, especially when outcomes guide investment decisions and the full model is solvable with a reasonable level of computational effort.

This research provides tools to quantify and enhance DR-induced cost and emission reductions, demonstrating the potential of demand-side flexibility in reducing emissions in electricity and local non-residential energy systems. Additionally, it offers novel findings that grant researchers in the field new insights. Ultimately, it promotes the adoption of non-residential DR by addressing the complexities of modern energy systems through integrated modeling.

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All models are wrong, but some are useful.

— *George E. P. Box*

*Dedicated to my son Finn
and his generation*

Part I

INTRODUCTION & LITERATURE REVIEW

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Research background and motivation

Global climate goals. Following the Paris Climate Agreement of 2015 [1] and the Glasgow Climate Pact of 2021 [2], there is an urgent need to reduce carbon emissions (CEs) worldwide. The Paris Agreement marked a significant milestone in global climate policy, establishing a framework for international cooperation in combating climate change. Under this agreement, 196 countries committed to limiting global warming to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels, aiming to restrict the increase to 1.5°C. The Glasgow Climate Pact sought to strengthen the 1.5°C goal and accelerate the phase-out of coal. With the European Green Deal, approved in 2020, the European Union aims to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050 [3]. An interim target has been set to reduce CEs by 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels. According to the Emissions Gap Report 2021 of the United Nations Environment Programme [4], these targets are insufficient to meet the 1.5°C target of the Paris Agreement. However, they are still ambitious and represent just one example of the global pursuit of deep decarbonization.

Demand response (DR) as key for global decarbonization. The high penetration of variable renewable energy sources (vRESs) in the electricity market, driven by the transition to a sustainable energy system, has increased the need for flexibility among market participants [5, 6]. Due to their temporal variability, uncertainty, and locational constraints, integrating high shares of vRESs is challenging and may lead to integration costs [7, 8]. DR, wherein energy consumers provide demand-side operational flexibility to the electricity system by altering their load profile in response to price signals (price-based DR) or specific requests (incentive-based DR), increases the system's operational flexibility and is crucial for integrating high vRES shares [9]. DR, by leveraging existing facilities,

is a cost-effective source of flexibility compared to alternatives such as battery storage, network expansion, and flexible large-scale generation [10, 11]. Hence, DR is an essential and promising approach to the transition to a carbon-free energy system [12, 13]. The International Energy Agency envisions a significant expansion in global DR capabilities to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050, suggesting a tenfold increase in DR capacity to reach 500 GW by 2030 [14]. Realizing this vision requires accelerating supportive policies and technology deployment, as well as deepening our understanding of the evolving DR landscape. This includes recognizing the impact of digitalization and the adoption of clean technologies on current and future DR potentials.

European DR potential. The European DR potential is significant. As identified by Gils [15], the minimum aggregated hourly average of load reduction and increase is 61 GW and 68 GW, respectively. Märkle-Huß et al. [16] demonstrated that, specifically in the German-Austrian day-ahead electricity market, system cost reductions of 6% can be realistically achieved through DR, assuming a 25% adoption rate. Studies have found that in Germany alone, DR could economically substitute between 8 GW [17] and 10 GW [18] of power plant capacity. However, a 2023 study [19] projects that between 2022 and 2030, demand-side flexibility in Germany will increase by around 30 GW, mainly due to the integration of e-mobility, power-to-heat, and power-to-gas applications into the electricity grid. Additionally, stationary battery energy storage (BES) systems are expected to expand from 10 GW in 2022 to 100 GW in 2030 [19].

Non-residential DR. The value of electrical demand-side flexibility for a prosumer is influenced by several key factors, including installed power capacity, frequency of usage, and time-dependent elements such as reaction time, duration of load shifting, and access duration. In non-residential sectors, which include industrial, commercial, and public-sector organizations, these factors often align advantageously [20], enhancing the potential for effective DR strategies. Furthermore, these sectors frequently exhibit multi-energy systems (MESs), integrating various energy carriers like heat, electricity, and hydrogen (H₂) to provide services such as electricity, cooling, and compressed air [21]. Fig. 1.1 shows an exemplary local MES (L-MES) incorporating energy and information flows that connect the industrial site to energy markets, external energy supply, and control systems. Such MESs exploit synergy effects, enhancing energy efficiency and flexibility [22]. Large industries, like those in aluminum, cement, or food production, with substantial electrical aggregates and advanced load control and communication infrastructures, are ideal for DR implementation [23]. The expansion of the industrial internet of things further drives industrial DR by providing the necessary software and hardware infrastructure. Consequently, industrial DR constitutes a significant portion of the total economically

feasible DR potential. In Germany, the economic DR potential is estimated to be between 2 to 3 GW from existing energy-intensive industrial processes [24, 25], with an additional 2 GW from existing cross-sectional industrial technologies [26, 27]. The technical potential for industrial DR is even greater [28]. Therefore, enhancing DR incentives is likely to correspondingly increase the economic potential of DR.

FIGURE 1.1: Scheme of an exemplary industrial MES, highlighting flexible assets in industrial production and energy supply system. Icons are sourced from Flaticon.

Barriers for DR. To date, approximately only 30% of the current economic potential for industrial DR has been tapped, as indicated by Steurer et al. [29]. This underutilization arises from various challenges. One of the main barriers to unlocking the economic DR potential is insufficient knowledge about economic value of DR [30]. Identifying industrial DR potentials is complex due to technical constraints and intricate linkages between production processes, energy conversion and storage, sales, and material requirement planning [31]. These complexities can lead to interaction effects that either compensate for or amplify the achievable DR potentials. To quantify the specific economically viable DR potential, model-based approaches are typically used, based on simulation, metaheuristics, or mathematical optimization [32]. Another key obstacle is the lack of DR-promoting policies and regulations [23]. Fixed grid usage fees, in particular, pose a major economic hurdle for DR [33, 34]. Navigating diverse markets and incentive systems is complex and time-consuming, especially when there are conflicting directives, as illustrated by the contradictions in the current German network charging system [35], see also Chapter 7. An additional challenge is the low level of awareness and prevalence of DR compared to energy efficiency initiatives. This is evident in the service sector, where a survey of over 1,500 German service companies revealed that only 4% had implemented DR measures, in contrast to the 48% who reported adopting energy efficiency measures [36]. According to a

recent study [37], interviews with German industry experts identified the most frequent obstacles for non-residential DR as concerns over product quality, production process disruptions, human resource management, and revenue uncertainty. The research suggests that overcoming these challenges requires bridging knowledge gaps, allocating resources, and adapting policies to foster wider adoption of DR in these sectors.

1.2 Problem statement

While most research on non-residential DR has focused on the optimal operation of individual flexible assets, to the author's knowledge, a comprehensive model that integrally considers investments, CEs, and multiple flexible assets within the evaluation of the economic DR potential of non-residential L-MESs has yet to be proposed. Therefore, the main contribution of this work is the development, application, and publication of a holistic modeling framework. This framework enables the quantification of the economic and environmental DR potential of non-residential L-MESs through optimizing its design and operation. As the framework identifies the optimal L-MES design, it can also serve as a decision-support tool.

1.3 Research objectives

This thesis aims to assess the economic and environmental dimensions of non-residential DR in the context of Europe's transition to zero-carbon energy. The primary research objectives are outlined as follows:

1. Development of a methodology and an open-source tool for computing dynamic electricity marginal emission factors (MEFs) and grid-mix emission factors (XEFs) for European countries to approximate the impact of DR on CEs.
2. Analysis of the impact of price-based DR (PBDR) on CEs for different European countries and carbon prices.
3. Development and demonstration of a modular open-source optimization framework to integrally evaluate the PBDR potential of a L-MES by identifying its optimal design and operation for given CE reduction.
4. Application of the framework to multiple non-residential case studies to determine their individual economic and environmental DR potential.
5. Evaluation of the adequacy of using time series aggregation (TSA) for low-carbon industrial L-MES models considering DR.

Overall, these objectives contribute to a comprehensive and multidimensional perspective on enhancing DR strategies to achieve carbon reduction goals within European energy markets. The thesis incorporates empirical analyses, software tools, decision-support frameworks, and real-world case studies, addressing the complex challenge of decarbonization in the energy sector.

1.4 Thesis structure

This section outlines the structure of the thesis. Fig. 1.2 provides an overview of the thesis' main work areas and their connections.

FIGURE 1.2: Main structure and contributions of this thesis.

Part I: Global Introduction & Literature Review

Chapter 2 offers a comprehensive review of current academic literature in several key areas. It starts by exploring the various types and potentials of non-residential DR, along with approaches for modeling these systems. The chapter then delves into methodologies for calculating carbon emission factors (CEFs) and discusses the environmental evaluation

of DR strategies. Finally, it examines the application and development of TSA techniques in energy systems, highlighting their relevance and advancements in the field.

Part II: Experimental Studies

Chapter 3 examines the economic and environmental potential of PBDR, highlighting the importance of understanding MEFs in contrast to XEFs in European electricity markets. This chapter introduces two methods to approximate hourly MEFs and applies them across 20 European countries, revealing that PBDR can increase CEs in some cases due to the economic advantages of more CE intensive fuel sources in the merit order. It concludes that, with appropriate carbon pricing, PBDR can effectively reduce CEs, as demonstrated by the analysis of load shift simulations and the relationship between carbon intensity and marginal cost in the German merit order. The last section introduces Elmada, an open-source software that incorporates the aforementioned CEF calculation methods.

Chapter 4 introduces the Demand Response Analysis Framework (DRAF), an open-source Python tool to optimize the design and operation of L-MESs, focusing on flexibility, electrification, and renewables. DRAF employs multi-objective mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) to evaluate cost and decarbonization potentials, guiding decision-makers toward optimal scenarios for cost, CEs, and efficiency. The chapter demonstrates DRAF's capabilities through case studies on industrial DR, battery and photovoltaic (PV) system optimization, and thermal energy resource management.

The subsequent chapters, 5 to 9, apply the two tools, Elmada and DRAF, to various purposes and settings.

Chapter 5 explores how digitalization and sector coupling transform companies into *flexumers*, using their L-MES to reduce costs and CEs while balancing the electricity grid. Metrics for evaluating price-based and emission-based DR are introduced. In a detailed case study of a beverage company in Northern Germany, Elmada, DRAF, and the DR metrics are applied to quantify the flexibility value of the company's MES, optimizing its design and operation for self-consumption, peak shaving, and integrated DR, taking into account hourly prices and CEFs. The results demonstrate significant reductions in decarbonization costs and operational carbon footprints through the effective use of various flexible technologies and storage systems.

Chapter 6 presents a MILP formulation tailored for PBDR, capable of optimizing electricity purchase and addressing production planning issues through the modeling of various machines, storages, and production types. Applying this model to a case study involving the machine scheduling of two cement mills, the chapter compares time-of-use pricing

with real-time pricing schemes. The optimization demonstrates a significant 13% annual reduction in electricity costs for the two mills.

Chapter 7 addresses the challenges industrial DR faces in Germany, particularly its interaction with regulatory systems from the fossil energy era, exemplified by fixed peak-demand grid fees (FGFs) and intensive grid usage (IGU) policies. A case study featuring a local energy system optimization model, incorporating a PV system (PVS) and a BES system (BESS), with data from a German chemical plant, is presented. It concludes that current FGFs and IGU policies inadvertently restrict operational flexibility and PBDR expansion, also affecting investment decisions for energy storage systems and PVSs.

Chapter 8 investigates the impact of landing interruptions on the optimal design of a green H₂ and ammonia import hub, incorporating energy conversion and storage systems. Utilizing a MILP, the study optimizes the hub's design and operation, factoring in elements such as storage systems, an ammonia cracker, and a proton-exchange-membrane electrolyzer, while considering demand variability and energy prices. A case study in Karlsruhe, Germany, highlights that a hub not designed for landing interruptions meet only a fraction of demand during landing interruptions. However, incorporating landing interruptions into design considerations results in a modest cost increase yet significantly improves operational resilience.

Chapter 9 delves into the use of TSA in energy system optimization modeling, a method used to simplify models and reduce computational demands. The study investigates the often-overlooked hidden costs to investors resulting from TSA application in designing highly flexible, sector-coupled, and decarbonized MESs, using backtesting with original input data to quantify these costs. Additionally, the chapter assesses the impact of various carbon removal prices on MES design and explores the effects of using MEFs versus XEFs on the adequacy of TSA.

Part III: Global Discussion & Conclusions

Chapter 10 synthesizes the findings detailed in Chapters 3 to 9, offering a comprehensive discussion of the research conducted and a collective analysis of the outcomes from each study, all aimed at addressing the research project's primary objectives.

Chapter 11 presents the overarching conclusions of this thesis and integrates results from these studies to fulfill the research objectives presented in Section 1.3.

Chapter 12 outlines the limitations of this research and suggests avenues for future work, building upon the foundations laid by the completed research.

Chapter 2

Literature review

2.1 Demand response

2.1.1 General review of DR programs

DR is the provision of demand-side flexibility by a final electricity consumer to the electricity system, either by reacting voluntarily to price signals (price-based DR) or responding to specific requests (incentive-based DR) [9]. Driven by digitalization and the trend toward decentralization within the energy transition, DR represents a cost-effective alternative to other flexibility sources, such as storage or grid expansions [13, 20]. Consequently, as the electricity system's demand for flexibility is expected to quadruple by 2050, the importance of DR is increasing [38]. DR is a key element for integrating vRESs into the electricity system, a major challenge of the renewable energy transition [13]. The high relevance of DR is evidenced by intensive research activities [39] and numerous research projects funded at both European [40–42] and national levels [43–45].

While some authors, such as Steurer [46] and Jordehi [32], make a clear distinction between DR, demand-side management, and demand-side integration in the literature, these terms are often used synonymously.

Flexibility dimensions. The concept of energy flexibility encompasses multiple dimensions. Flexibility options can be categorized into three areas: generation, consumption, and storage [19]. However, with the ongoing trend of decentralization, consumers are evolving into entities that not only consume energy but also generate and store it. This evolution has led to a preference for the term *demand-side response* over DR in some contexts, as it more explicitly encompasses both electricity-generating and electricity-storing resources on

the demand side. In this thesis, however, DR is predominantly used to imply demand-side flexibility, including electricity-generating assets like combined heat and power (CHP) systems and electricity storage technologies, notably BESS.

Flexibility options in energy systems are classified into asymmetrical and symmetrical categories. Asymmetrical flexibility is further divided into positive and negative types. Positive flexibility enables a device to either increase electricity input to the grid or reduce its draw, while negative flexibility involves decreasing electricity input to the grid or increasing its draw. Symmetrical flexibility combines both positive and negative aspects, allowing a device to adjust its electricity input and draw in either direction.

Finally, energy flexibility can be categorized into three purpose-focused areas: self-use, involving optimizing consumption within the operator’s domain through strategies like maximizing self-consumption; grid-oriented use, aimed at enhancing transmission or distribution networks by actions such as improving voltage stability or alleviating line overloads; and system-oriented use, crucial for maintaining a balanced power system across market bidding zones, where the specific location of flexibility provision is less critical [19].

DR program types. Several methods exist for categorizing DR programs. While Eurelectric, the sector association of the European electricity industry, distinguishes between explicit and implicit DR programs [47], other publications refer to these categories as system- and market-oriented or stability- and economic-based [17, 48]. However, the most common categorization differentiates between incentive-based and price-based DR programs [49]. Fig. 2.1 shows a further subdivision of these two main criteria for the USA markets.

FIGURE 2.1: Categorization of DR programs. Source: Based on [50].

It is important to note that the definition of ancillary services differs regionally, including between the USA and Europe. In Europe, the most significant ancillary services are provided through the balancing markets, which consist of Frequency Containment Reserve, Automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve, Manual Frequency Restoration Reserve, and Replacement Reserve [51]. For simplicity, in this work, the European balancing markets and similar ancillary services are collectively referred to as reserve markets.

Among the PBDR programs, real-time pricing (RTP) programs, where retail electricity prices are closely aligned with wholesale prices, stand out for their economic and environmental benefits in enabling DR actions [52]. Currently, RTP programs are available in at least ten European Union countries [53]. In *The Clean Energy Package*, the European Union proposed that every final customer should be entitled, upon request, to receive an RTP contract from their supplier [54]. Eurelectric also advocates for RTP in electricity supply as an advanced type of implicit DR [47].

Local energy markets. Related approaches that are gaining scientific attention include the concepts of local energy trading and energy communities [55, 56]. Local energy trading allows members of an energy community to buy and sell energy directly to each other, often through peer-to-peer platforms and at the distribution system level. This can be done using vRESs, such as PV and wind turbine (WT), or electricity from the grid [57]. Local energy trading and energy communities can facilitate DR by providing consumers with more choice and control over their energy consumption. For example, a member of an energy community could sell excess solar energy to their neighbors during peak periods or reduce their energy consumption during times of high prices. This demand-side flexibility could be aggregated and then used to support the system, market, or network level.

For general reviews of DR programs, the reader is referred to the works of Paterakis et al. [39], Gelazanskas and Gamage [58], Siano [59], and Honarmand et al. [60].

2.1.2 Non-residential DR

This work focuses on DR in non-residential buildings, typically in the industrial and commercial sectors. This includes industrial and large commercial firms, as well as public sector organizations.

Industrial DR. The residential sector receives significant attention in DR research due to high consumer flexibility and load schedulability [61]. However, the industrial sector, responsible for the largest share of energy and electricity demand in Europe and worldwide, possesses larger individual DR devices and superior control infrastructure, making it a more suitable candidate for DR implementation [62, 63]. Despite this, the implementation of industrial DR is subject to sector-specific circumstances, such as critical temporal dependencies of manufacturing processes, data protection, bilateral power contracts, and common on-site electricity generation [64]. In [65], industrial DR potentials and limitations in specific industries are evaluated.

In Germany, recent top-down studies have identified high economic potentials for industrial DR applications from both system and business perspectives [18, 26, 29]. However, the results of the research project Interflex4Climate [66] indicate that a realistic assessment of economic industrial DR potentials requires individual bottom-up analysis. This analysis must consider both the connection to various markets and the individual production-technical and organizational requirements of the respective industrial sites' processes.

Over the past three decades, research in the field of industrial DR potentials and modeling has significantly intensified, leading to a substantial and expanding body of literature. Most studies have focused on industrial production processes, such as pulp and paper [67], chlor-alkali electrolysis [68, 69], air separation [70–72], glass [73], refinery [74], wastewater treatment [75], cement [76, 77], aluminum [78, 79], metal casting [80], copper [81], and green steel [82]. Fewer studies have focused on internet data centers [83, 84] or cross-sectional distributed energy resources in industrial and commercial buildings, such as CHPs [85–87], fuel cells (FCs) [88], BESSs [34, 89], electric steam boilers [90], and heat pumps (HPs) [91, 92]. Only a few studies have considered multiple flexible industrial loads [93].

Commercial DR. Previous research on DR can be classified by the sectors of electricity users: residential, commercial, and industrial sectors [20]. However, when considering only cross-sectional technologies, industrial companies can be grouped with large commercial companies (e.g., [91]). Similarly, small commercial businesses can be grouped with the residential sector due to their similar electricity consumption patterns (e.g., [17]). This grouping is also reflected in the electricity categorization of end-users [20]. Although the theoretical potential of the three sectors is estimated to be similar in magnitude [15], the commercial sector receives less scientific attention compared to the others [20, 94].

Non-residential vehicle-to-everything (V2X). Although numerous studies have investigated DR with battery electric vehicles (BEVs), there is a dearth of research on using BEV batteries to shape the demand profiles of companies through bidirectional charging approaches. Leippi et al. [95] underscored the importance of integrating BEVs into industrial applications via smart grids, highlighting the need to consider battery degradation in DR charging scenarios. They noted a significant gap in studies that concurrently address battery degradation and financial compensation for BEV owners in DR contexts. This underscores the necessity for developing optimized models that balance cost savings for companies with fair compensation for BEV owners. These models are especially vital in large BEV fleets and should be incorporated into multi-criteria approaches that consider both economic and environmental benefits.

Beyond industrial to commercial and residential sectors. Historically, DR programs have been primarily confined to the industrial sector and larger customers, as Ayón et al. [96] observed. Due to the substantial size of their equipment and the availability of advanced information technology infrastructure, industrial DR initiatives can often be implemented with minimal investment, making them particularly promising [97]. However, with the emergence of flexibility aggregators, both commercial and residential sectors now have access to DR programs, albeit indirectly. Other obstacles to DR implementation are expected to gradually lessen as the demand for flexibility in the power system increases. Furthermore, an increasing number of electricity consumers are becoming prosumers by installing on-site vRESs. Given a disparity between the prices for purchasing and feeding in electricity, these prosumers can directly benefit from their demand-side flexibility. This flexibility allows them to optimize their energy demand and feed-in profiles, thereby reducing electricity costs.

For recent reviews on non-residential DR, readers are referred to [20, 23, 39, 94, 97, 98].

2.1.3 Review of different modeling approaches

A substantial body of literature exists on the modeling of industrial DR [52, 61, 67, 69, 73, 74, 76, 77, 87, 92, 99–108].

DR and sector coupling. Molavi and Ardehali [91] utilized a genetic algorithm and particle swarm optimization to assess the impact of a time-of-use (TOU) tariff on an industrial customer with a thermal energy storage (TES) system charged by an electric HP. Arteconi et al. [92] conducted research using dynamic simulation to determine the load shifting potential of a cool TES system integrated with a PV system and HPs. Their findings underscore the economic benefits of TES systems, especially in reducing operational costs through strategic energy demand management, despite the increase in overall energy consumption and initial capital investment. In [109], a MILP unit commitment problem of a CHP system coupled with a TES was presented, considering both spot and reserve markets. Aghaei and Alizadeh [99] developed a multi-objective mixed-integer programming model for CHP-based microgrids, including electrical storage systems. Bischi et al. [86] introduced a rolling-horizon algorithm that incorporates MILP for optimizing the operating schedule of a co-generation energy system. Ata et al. [110] applied a MILP model to a MES including vRES, CHP, and HPs to reduce energy costs, fossil fuel use, and CEs. Simulation results indicated that integrating PV alone reduces operational costs by 5.49%, while combining PV and WT leads to a 13.45% reduction. Incorporating BEVs as a flexible electrical load further reduced costs by 8.81%.

DR of energy-intensive industrial processes. Khripko et al. [100] analyzed business models for industrial DR, although their study lacked quantitative results. [101] investigated the DR potential of a process plant, considering its participation in both spot and reserve markets. Helin et al. [67] examined the economic potential of industrial DR in the pulp and paper industry using MILP. Their results suggested that transmission system operators and policymakers should take economic factors into account when assessing the potential of industrial PBDR. Finn and Fitzpatrick [102] explored how industrial PBDR can enhance the utilization of wind energy in Ireland. Zare et al. [111] developed a technique for determining the bidding strategies of a large-scale consumer in the day-ahead market. Zhang et al. [103] proposed a model-predictive control approach for scheduling cement crushers, investigating how an electrical storage system can overcome granularity restrictions of cement crushers to provide valuable ancillary services.

Consideration of bidding in sequential energy markets. Baringo and Sánchez Amaro [112] proposed a stochastic optimization approach to identify the bidding strategies of electric vehicle aggregators. Boomsma et al. [113] examined the potential of coordinated bidding in sequential electricity markets, using stochastic programming to model bidding in two sequential markets under price uncertainty. Kumbartzky et al. [85] presented a method for optimizing the operation of a CHP plant participating in sequential energy markets, considering price uncertainty and a pay-as-bid auction mechanism within a multi-stage stochastic MILP framework. Bohlayer et al. [76] proposed a novel approach for integrating production-inventory planning with cost-minimizing bids in energy and reserve markets, specifically for industrial processes like cement plants. This approach employs a multi-stage stochastic MILP that accounts for time-coupling constraints and price uncertainties. The method's effectiveness was demonstrated through a case study on a cement plant participating in the German energy and reserve markets, highlighting its potential for significant revenue generation.

Consideration of uncertainties. Reka and Ramesh [106] applied a resource task network and stochastic dynamic programming to schedule industrial PBDR, validating their models with empirical data from a refinery plant. Huang et al. [52] used a MILP formulation for industrial DR, based on hour-ahead RTP forecasts generated by artificial neural networks. Golari et al. [107] explored the production-inventory planning problem of a system powered by on-site and grid renewable energy. Alipour et al. [87] proposed short-term self-scheduling for commercial and industrial customers with CHP units, forecasting power demand and pool prices using autoregressive integrated moving average models and treating them as stochastic processes in the scheduling problem. Yu et al. [108] addressed future price uncertainties through robust optimization, demonstrating a 13% reduction in electricity costs without

the need for additional energy storage or distributed energy resources. Abdulaal et al. [61] combined methods from quadratic, stochastic, and evolutionary programming with multi-objective optimization and continuous simulation, proposing a two-stage discrete-continuous multi-objective load optimization autonomous approach for industrial DR. However, their study did not account for CE savings.

The paradigm shift from supply-side to demand-side flexibility. The flexibility of conventional power plants is anticipated to decrease significantly as most fossil fuel power plants are decommissioned within the next two decades. Sector coupling allows sectors such as heat and mobility to utilize vRESs as a carbon-free energy source, supporting their integration into the electricity system by providing new flexibility options, for example, through HPs, electric heaters (referred to as power-to-heat or P2H), electrolyzers, or BEVs. HPs are an attractive investment option for electrifying and potentially decarbonizing heat demands, as emphasized by [114]. In the industrial sector, HPs can also utilize waste heat, thereby enhancing energy efficiency. For instance, the industrial waste heat potential in the European Union for temperatures below 200°C is estimated at 100 TWh/year [115]. Utilizing high-temperature HPs to exploit this waste heat potential creates new flexibility potentials, particularly when these HPs are combined with appropriate TES systems. Hübner et al. [116] analyzed the effects of industrial CE reduction measures on the industrial DR potential in 2050. Their results indicate that these measures could enable an additional 7.7 GW and 6.3 GW of positive and negative flexibility potential, respectively, compared to 2018 levels. Notably, over 85% of this potential is attributed to HPs and P2H. Furthermore, these findings suggest that industrial transformation could significantly enhance the integration of vRESs into the energy system, more than previously anticipated.

Meta-heuristics. Stoetzer et al. [17] employed genetic algorithms to forecast a DR potential of 8 GW in the German residential and commercial sectors by 2030. Aghajani et al. [88] used multi-objective particle swarm optimization to optimize the operation of a smart microgrid, considering incentive-based DR and accounting for uncertainties in wind speed and solar irradiance. In the realm of electricity system applications, several studies have utilized multi-objective evolutionary algorithms that apply the Pareto method to derive Pareto-optimal solutions for multi-objective optimization problems, as reported by [117, 118]. A notable algorithm in this domain is NSGA2, proposed by Deb et al. [119]. Cortés-Arcos et al. [120] implemented a task management methodology and an evolutionary algorithm for PBDR. In their multi-objective optimization model, both the daily cost of electricity and consumer dissatisfaction are minimized. However, this model was exclusively applied to the residential sector.

2.1.4 DR and investments

The incorporation of DR in optimal design planning often results in larger capacities for assets and storage systems associated with electricity demand. This is because the reduced average utilization rate of these assets is offset by the revenue or cost savings gained from DR participation. While many analyses of DR potential focus primarily on the flexibility of existing assets, it is crucial to also consider investment options that can modify existing flexibility. For instance, extending product storage for a flexible production process or implementing electrification measures should be factored into assessments of the flexibility potential of L-MESs. An example of such an approach is seen in the work of Liu et al. [121], who demonstrated synergistic effects when energy storage and DR of combined cooling, heating, and power systems are integrated.

2.1.5 DR and carbon emissions

Dynamic carbon emission factors. Electricity CEFs are classified into XEFs and MEFs. XEFs are suitable for calculating CE balances of energy consumption, whereas MEFs are more appropriate for approximating the real CE effects of short-term demand changes. Summerbell et al. [77] examined the cost and CE reduction potentials of a cement plant through PBDR using RTP. Although they calculated the CE reduction potential from dynamic CEFs, these factors were not part of an objective function, thus CEs could not be minimized directly. Their scheduling simulation resulted in electricity costs and electricity-derived CE reductions of 4% each. Baumgärtner et al. [122] calculated dynamic XEFs and MEFs for Germany in 2016 from an economic dispatch model and incorporated them into the objective function of a multi-objective problem to design low-carbon L-MESs. They concluded that CEs can be reduced by 6% when using dynamic XEFs instead of annual XEFs and by up to 60% when using dynamic MEFs, emphasizing the importance of using dynamic CEFs. Jordehi [32] reviewed optimization models considering DR and identified a scarcity of research on DR modeling for commercial and industrial consumers, strongly recommending the inclusion of environmental effects by placing CEs in the objective function. Stoll et al. [123] calculated CEFs for Sweden, Great Britain, and Ontario and their correlation with electricity market prices, concluding that the introduction of a DR program complemented with a 24-hour carbon intensity could help reduce CEs regardless if the correlation was positive or negative. However, there was no further use of these dynamic CEFs in their study. More recently, Lerch et al. [68] evaluated the potential of optimal load shifting in chlor-alkali electrolysis for electricity cost savings and CE reductions in Germany, using a MILP framework to analyze various scenarios. Their findings indicate that load shifting could lead to significant electricity cost savings (up to 22% by 2040)

and CE reductions (up to 10%), primarily driven by the electricity price spread and the operational flexibility of the electrolyzer, contributing both to business competitiveness and broader decarbonization goals. A more detailed literature review on the short-term environmental evaluation of DR is provided in Section 2.3.

24/7 carbon-free energy. In pursuit of entirely renewable electricity consumption, the 24/7 carbon-free energy approach is gaining traction. This approach employs granular guarantees of origin with a time granularity of one hour or less and geographic granularity at the level of electricity grids or bidding zones [124]. Promoted by international companies [125] and non-profit initiatives [126], this approach aims to incentivize the reduction of intra-year disparities between the supply and demand of renewable electricity. These disparities are often overlooked by conventional annual guarantees of origin [127]. This development could catalyze a paradigm shift in the evaluation logic. Rather than forecasting the CEFs of the electricity grid, the focus shifts to a specialized sub-market for guarantees of origin for carbon-free energy. In scenarios where such initiatives prove effective, the forecasting of hourly CEFs might even become redundant, being replaced by the forecasting of hourly prices for granular guarantees of origin. This pricing mechanism could significantly incentivize load shifting. Beyond wholesale electricity prices, the price of these granular guarantees of origin could become a crucial element in PBDR. In this transformed market landscape, the nature of PBDR would substantially change. It would no longer be primarily based on the wholesale market price, which includes fossil-based electricity. Instead, it would depend on prices within a market of guarantees of origin that trades exclusively in carbon-free electricity. As companies increasingly aim to achieve 24/7 carbon-free energy targets, the relevance of this price component intensifies. Given that carbon-free electricity generation is largely reliant on vRES, the price of such granular guarantees of origin is inherently volatile, thus creating strong incentives for PBDR.

2.2 Potential of DR

The literature on DR potential is expanding. Muche et al. [109] utilized MILP to assess the revenue from the participation of CHP plants in control reserve markets. In [128], an intelligent energy management framework based on MILP with DR capability was proposed for industrial facilities. This framework analyzed thermostatically controlled loads and BEVs, as well as production processes and renewable generation. However, in both studies, CEs were not considered. Kelley et al. [72] employed MILP to model the DR of air separation units, providing a novel scheduling framework that accounts for plant dynamics but focusing only on one DR application. Scholz and Meisel [129] analyzed the

energy flexibility of forklift trucks within a MES, but they did not consider investment decisions or V2X technology. Paul et al. [130] explored the potential of peak shaving in non-residential buildings, finding that peak shaving can be economically viable for specific BESS investment costs below €850/kWh.

Considering CEs. Summerbell et al. [77] investigated the potential for electricity cost and CE reductions in a cement plant through PBDR using RTP. A scheduling simulation with dynamic CEFs led to reductions in costs and CEs of 4% each. In [81], a MILP production scheduling model was developed to assess the PBDR potential of a representative copper production process. The optimal production schedule derived from this model could have saved 14.2% of electricity costs by shifting up to 16.5% of the annual load, without compromising production goals. However, in both studies, investments were not considered.

Considering system design. Alabi et al. [131] proposed a multi-objective design and operation optimization model for carbon-neutral MESs. They conducted a case study analyzing the effects of considering energy storage aging and DR in a residential district in Hong Kong. However, their methodology was not applied to the commercial and industrial sector. Ahmarinejad [132] presented multi-objective planning and operation MILP models considering DR. Unlike the work in this thesis, their approach was not evaluated in a real-world case study. Petkov and Gabrielli [133] introduced a multi-objective design optimization formulation for MESs considering H₂ as a seasonal energy storage. They concluded that for accurate seasonal storage evaluations, optimization must cover at least 2,000 hourly resolved time steps. Their findings also indicated that an MES can only achieve net zero operational CEs using power-to-H₂ technology.

Mansouri et al. [134] proposed an investment and operation optimization framework for MESs considering DR, showing a 15.1% reduction in operating expenses (OpEx) through price-based load shifting. However, their study only considered Scope 1 CEs with fixed CEFs. In [135], a design and operation optimization MILP problem was formulated for an exhibition center in southern Italy. The model considered energy flexibility through peak shaving with a BESS. CEs were assessed, but only using annual CEFs, and carbon neutrality was not analyzed.

Baumgärtner et al. [122] proposed an optimal planning and operation model considering hourly CEFs, PBDR, and carbon neutrality. They calculated costs and CEs comparing the use of annual versus hourly CEFs, with significant differences in results emphasizing the importance of hourly CEFs. This model was applied in a real-world case study of a chemical industry MES. However, the value of flexibility was not explicitly quantified in their study. Additionally, Jordehi [32] concluded in their comprehensive review on DR

that more research should focus on the commercial and industrial sector, on more realistic optimization problems, and on the analysis of environmental effects.

Flexibility metrics. Recent studies have proposed various flexibility metrics to quantify and characterize PBDR. In [136], four metrics (price responsiveness score, consistency score, flexible amount, and response time score) were introduced to identify and classify flexumers based on their electricity price and load responses. However, CEFs were not considered in these metrics, and they were designed for TOU tariffs rather than RTP.

Luo et al. [137] reviewed DR quantification indicators for residential energy flexibility, categorizing them into direct and indirect indicators. Direct indicators directly relate to the characteristics of a building, while indirect indicators also incorporate economic and environmental factors. The indirect indicators mentioned included operation cost savings, operation cost reduction ratio, cost flexibility factor, and CE reductions. However, weighted averages based on electricity price and load were not included, and the CE reduction indicator was based on time-independent CEFs.

In [138], several flexibility metrics were proposed, focusing exclusively on incentive-based DR, making them inapplicable to price or CEF-based DR. More recently, the study in [139] reviewed 156 articles, identifying 48 data-driven energy flexibility key performance indicators (KPIs) for operational buildings. These KPIs can be classified based on the requirement of a baseline energy demand (penalty-ignorant operation). For baseline-required KPIs, building performance data in both flexible and reference scenarios are necessary, whereas baseline-free KPIs can be calculated without a reference scenario. The study also identified the development of new baseline-free KPIs and the inclusion of non-engineering factors such as costs and CEs as major research gaps. The energy-weighted average electricity price, often referred to as the load-weighted or demand-weighted average price, is a widely used metric in the context of large-scale electricity systems, as seen in studies such as [140], [141], and [142]. However, to the author's best knowledge, this metric has not been employed to evaluate the DR intensity of L-MESs. In contrast, demand-weighted CEFs have only been utilized since the availability of hourly CEFs, as indicated by [143]. However, in this thesis, the author used energy-weighted average electricity prices to evaluate the effectiveness of price-based and CEF-based DR of an industrial company's MES and to compare it between scenarios.

Importance of electrification. To meet the challenging targets of the Paris Climate Agreement [1] and to stay within sustainable biomass limits, a high degree of electrification and H₂ integration is needed in the energy system [144] and the industry sector [145]. Sector coupling, such as the electrification of heat and mobility, enables sectors that traditionally

relied on fossil fuels, to benefit from the decarbonization possibilities offered by the electricity sector, such as PV and wind power [114]. In turn, sector coupling allows for the transfer of operational flexibility from other energy sectors (heat, mobility, H₂) to the electricity sector [146]. This operational flexibility is necessary to compensate for the increasing shares of vRESs and the decommissioning of controllable thermal power plants. Thus, carbon-free electricity systems require four times the operational flexibility of conventional systems [147]. DR programs activate demand-side flexibility through different incentive systems. Electrification gives rise to MESs that can provide existing and newly created flexibility that can be used through DR [21]. Besides private households and heavy industry, the commercial and light industrial sector also exhibits untapped flexibility potential [148].

Flexumer. By exploiting demand-side flexibility potentials to provide market, network, or system services, an electricity prosumer becomes a “flexumer” [136, 149]. Prosumers are residential, commercial, or industrial electricity consumers that also produce electricity. Flexumers are prosumers who additionally use their demand-flexibility to provide market, network or system services. While a prosumer draws power from the grid and feeds in surpluses, a flexumer additionally controls the energy profiles through the smart use of energy conversion and storage technologies as well as loads. Fig. 2.2 illustrates a comparison of the terms consumer, prosumer, and flexumer.

FIGURE 2.2: Differentiation of the terms consumer, prosumer, and flexumer. Example: A consumer only consumes electricity. A prosumer consumes electricity and feeds in surplus electricity from his on-site PV system. A flexumer provides market, network, or system services using the flexibility of his on-site battery system to optimize his electricity consumption and feed-in profile.

The value of demand-side flexibility for companies. There are several flexibility applications, e.g., ancillary service provision, energy-only market optimization, peer-to-peer energy trading, congestion management, self-consumption optimization, and peak-shaving [27, 150]. The value of demand-side flexibility for a company can be divided into three dimensions, see Fig. 2.3. Dimension 1 is direct financial benefits through additional

revenue streams or cost reductions. Dimension 2 represents the reduction of the company’s Scope 1 and 2 carbon footprint by reducing the volume or carbon intensity of purchased energy, or both. Dimension 3 includes corporate image gains, since DR helps stabilize the electricity system, prevents blackouts, and integrates vRESs into the electricity system [151]. With increasing renewable energy shares, DR and energy flexibility, in general, will gain reputation as key components of the energy transition [12]. By participating in DR, production companies provide an important overarching contribution that they can publicly communicate [152]. Note that the environmental and the financial benefits may interact, e.g., financial benefits (Dimension 1) could finance clean technologies and reduce carbon footprint. Analogously, carbon footprint reductions (Dimension 2) may reduce the need for expensive carbon removal and, therefore, imply financial benefits.

FIGURE 2.3: The value of demand-side flexibility for companies. Here, the term carbon footprint implies an attributional perspective as opposed to the consequential perspective of measuring operational CEs. This distinction is important because flexibility-induced carbon footprint reductions are not necessarily accompanied by CE reductions on the macro level. For an elaboration on this so-called merit order dilemma of emissions, the reader is referred to Chapter 3. While the consequential perspective is essential to assess the real impact on CEs, currently, most companies are evaluated with an attributional approach (using grid-mix emission factors) and are, therefore, incentivized to reduce their carbon footprint rather than their impact on the macro-level CEs.

2.3 Short-term environmental evaluation of DR

Classification of CEFs. In the literature, there are essentially two dimensions for classifying electricity grid CEFs. The methodology dimension classifies the methods behind CEFs into empirical data and relationship models (EDRM) such as regression analyses and power system optimization models (PSOM) such as economic dispatch models [153]. The other dimension divides CEFs according to their type into XEFs and MEFs. XEFs

describe the current generation mix of the electricity system and account for renewable energy sources (RES) shares, while MEFs quantify marginal system effects [154].

XEFs. The methodology behind XEFs involves an attributional approach where all CEs of the electricity grid within a particular time frame are allocated to all electricity consumers in proportion to their demand [122]. This method prevents double counting of CEs and is, therefore, frequently used in carbon accounting [155]. XEFs are calculated by weighting the power plant type-specific CEs according to their share of total electricity consumption during each hour. Consequently, XEFs reflect the current state of the electricity mix, including the proportions of renewable and conventional electricity production [154].

MEFs. The marginal power plant method for calculating MEFs focuses on the element of the power plant mix that is actually affected by changes on the demand side, reflecting the consequences on CEs of the electricity system [156]. In uniform-pricing markets, power plant owners are incentivized to bid at their individual marginal cost. This creates a merit order that arranges all power plants according to their marginal costs. A load reduction or increase within a specific hour is compensated by a change in the power output of the marginal power plant. Consequently, the MEF is equal to the specific emission factor of the marginal power plant.

Comparison of CEF research. Ryan et al. [153] offers a valuable guideline for selecting the most appropriate method for calculating CEFs. For a comprehensive review of CE accounting approaches in electricity generation systems, readers are directed to the work of Khan [157]. Within the literature, various approaches for determining CEFs can be found. Table 2.1 in the thesis provides an overview of studies, clustering them by type, methodology, temporal and geographic scope, and temporal resolution into three distinct groups.

Group A. Studies in Group A focused on calculating historic, hourly, or half-hourly XEFs using EDRMs for various countries. The majority of these studies, including [77, 123, 155, 158–163], concentrated on computing simple CEFs for individual or a few countries. This was done by weighting historic generation data with the corresponding CEFs per fuel type. Tranberg et al. [164] introduced a more advanced approach. They employed flow-tracing, which enables tracking of power flows on the transmission network from the region of generation to the region of consumption, to calculate consumption-based XEFs for 27 European countries. Their results revealed significant discrepancies between consumption-based and generation-based XEFs, suggesting the inclusion of cross-border flows for accurate

TABLE 2.1: Classification of studies that propose methods to calculate electricity CEFs according to type, methodology, scope, and temporal resolution. The studies are clustered in three groups and within these sorted by years.

	Study		CEF Type		Methodology		Scope		Temporal resolution of CEFs	
	Year	Name	Ref.	XEF	MEF	EDRM	PSOM	Temporal		Geographic
Group A	2014	Stoll et al.	[123]	•		• ^a		historic: 2011, 2012	UK, SE, US	hourly
	2014	Messagie et al.	[158]	•		• ^a		historic: 2011	BE	hourly
	2016	Roux et al.	[155]	•		• ^a		historic: 2013	FR	hourly
	2017	Kono et al.	[159]	•		• ^a		historic: 2011–2015	DE	hourly
	2017	Kopsakangas-S. et al.	[160]	•		• ^a		historic: 2011	FI	hourly
	2017	Summerbell et al.	[77]	•		• ^a		historic: 2015	UK	half-hourly
	2018	Khan et al.	[161]	•		• ^a		historic: 2015	NZ	half-hourly
	2019	Clauß et al.	[162]	•		• ^a		historic: 2015	NO, SE, DK, FI	hourly
	2019	Munné-Collado et al.	[163]	•		• ^a		historic: 2018	5 European countries	hourly
	2019	Tranberg et al.	[164]	•		• ^b		historic: 2017	27 European countries	hourly
Group B	2010	Hawkes	[165]	•	•	• ^c		historic: 2002–2009	UK	time-of-day/year
	2010	Greensfelder et al.	[166]	•	•	• ^c		historic: 2008	US (4 regions)	hourly
	2012	Siler-Evans et al.	[167]	•	•	• ^c		historic: 2006–2011	US (8 regions)	time-of-day/year
	2014	Thomson	[168]	•	•	• ^c		historic: 2008–2013	UK	time-of-day/year
	2017	Pareschi et al.	[169]	•	•	• ^c		historic: 2015	AT, CH, DE, FR	annual
	2017	Thomson et al.	[170]	•	•	• ^c		historic: 2009–2014	UK	time-of-day/year
	2018	Péan et al.	[171]	•	•	• ^c		historic: 2016	ES	hourly
Group C	2006	Bettle et al.	[172]	•	•		• ^d	historic: 2000	UK	half-hourly
	2018	Regett et al.	[154]	•	•		• ^d	future: 2030	DE	hourly
	2019	Baumgärtner et al.	[122]	•	•		• ^d	historic: 2016	DE	hourly
	2019	Böing & Regett	[173]	•	•		• ^d	future: 2020–2050	DE	hourly
	—	This chapter	—	•	•		• ^d	historic: 2017–2019	20 European countries	hourly

^a Simple emission factors

^b Flow tracing

^c Statistical relationship model

^d Economic dispatch model

CE accounting of electricity. This method is showcased in the electricityMap [174], a real-time visualization tool for the CE footprint of electricity consumption. However, it is important to note that these studies did not specifically focus on MEFs, which is a topic of interest in this thesis.

Group B. For Group B, a seminal work was published by Hawkes in 2010 [165]. Utilizing half-hourly data from the UK for 2002–2009, he calculated the first difference of system CEs and system load, respectively. The average MEF was determined by the slope of the regression line between these two difference vectors. Compared to purely merit-order based methods, this approach has the advantage of implicitly considering market trading decisions, logistical constraints of power plant operation, and transmission and distribution restrictions. However, the nature of statistical relationship models limits the temporal resolution of the resulting MEFs, which is crucial for assessing DR measures. The regression can be repeated on subsets of the data to obtain time-of-day or time-of-year MEFs, as subsequent studies have shown by applying Hawkes’ approach to different geographic regions [167–170]. However, this method still overlooks vital information, such as the fluctuating share of RES. Through the comparison of XEFs and MEFs, Siler-Evans et al. [167] discovered that XEFs might misestimate the CEs that can be avoided from a demand-side intervention. Péan et al. [171] expanded on Hawkes’ approach by clustering the 2016 data from Spain according to system load and RES share, then applying linear regression to each cluster.

By fitting a quadratic function of RES share and system load to the regression results, they were able to compute hourly MEFs. While this method appears promising for comparing the environmental effect of DR across different countries, it involves constant CEFs per fuel type. This overlooks the efficiency differences of power plants within a fuel type, which is particularly significant for national energy systems predominantly based on one or two fuel types, such as in Lithuania or Serbia.

Group C. Finally, studies in Group C calculated historic or future MEFs at hourly or higher resolutions using PSOMs, specifically economic dispatch models. Bettel et al. [172] utilized historic generation data per power plant in the UK for the year 2000 to calculate half-hourly MEFs. These MEFs indicated up to 50% higher CE savings compared to XEFs. However, this approach is not feasible for most European countries, where power plant-specific generation data are not readily available. Additionally, they used fixed power plant efficiencies per fuel type. Regett et al. [154] computed future, hourly XEFs and MEFs for Germany and discovered a negative correlation between them, meaning they can lead to contrasting results. This underscores the significance of choosing the appropriate CEF type. Building on [154], Böing and Regett [173] developed a CE accounting method determining dynamic XEFs and MEFs for different energy carriers in MESs. Their focus, however, was on the future energy system of Germany rather than comparing multiple countries based on historic data. Baumgärtner et al. [122] executed an economic dispatch model on German data from 2016, resulting in hourly XEFs and MEFs, which were then used in a multi-objective synthesis problem for a low-carbon utility system. They approximated power plant-specific efficiencies using a logarithmic size-dependent regression of real power plants. Nevertheless, power plant sizes are not available for all countries, and efficiencies also depend on the year of construction.

The significance of CEFs in evaluating demand side management based on CEs is evident from the extensive range of scientific literature on the subject. However, as shown in Table 2.1, the focus of the literature is primarily on XEFs and analyses specific to single countries. This trend is largely due to the sparse availability of data and the heterogeneity in the quality of available data. Only a few studies calculated MEFs with hourly resolution, and none of them compared hourly MEFs across different countries. To effectively address the diversity in generation technology mixes across these countries, carbon effect analyses must be conducted for each individual country. Consequently, there is a gap in the existing body of literature regarding the effects of PBDR on CEs for the major European markets using hourly MEFs.

Importance of PBDR. The integration of additional vRESs requires an increase in the operational flexibility of the electricity grids to compensate for the increasing fluctuation of

the residual load, which defines the total load minus the production from vRESs. Operational flexibility in this context means that it is not based on structural changes in the electricity system such as power station commissioning/decommissioning or fuel price changes [175]. This flexibility can be provided by flexible generation, interconnection, energy storage, and demand-side resources [11]. PBDR is seen as an essential and promising approach for unlocking the flexibility potential of demand-side resources in a cost-efficient way [176]. Thus, PBDR has been the subject of many recent studies across the residential, commercial, and industrial sectors, as shown in the review articles [32, 39, 59, 177]. Also, PBDR can be combined with incentive-based DR as demonstrated in [76].

Temporal granularity. For the quantification of electricity-related CEs, the temporal granularity of CEFs is important. Annual average CEFs, which are still commonly used, lead to inaccurate results because of the high variance of emission factors of different fuel types. This is even more important for the evaluation of emissions due to load changes such as with PBDR. Several studies, therefore, suggest the usage of time-varying CEFs instead of yearly average CEFs for short and long term decision making [122, 160, 161].

Marginal power plants. Dynamic XEFs are useful for calculating CE balances of energy consumers. Since it is usually not possible to trace electricity from a specific producer to consumer, the average carbon intensity of the entire generation system is attributed to each customer [178]. However, if XEFs are used to assess or reduce the real effect of DR on CE, the results may be misleading [165, 167]. The reason for this is that not all power plants react proportionally to a change in demand [165]. In theory, the electricity requested will come from the power plant with the lowest marginal cost and spare capacity, the so-called marginal power plant [179]. Dynamic MEFs estimate the carbon intensity of demand changes as the carbon intensity of the marginal power plant for each time step [165]. This is why, if the real impact of DR on operational CEs is to be determined or even minimized, MEFs should be used where possible. However, the calculation of hourly MEFs requires a very detailed database, which is why hourly MEFs are not available for most areas [167]. As a consequence and despite a growing body of literature that recognizes the necessity of MEFs for assessing the environmental effects of PBDR [122, 154, 157, 164, 165, 167, 169, 171, 180], XEFs are still used in this context.

Merit order dilemma of emissions. Through PBDR, price incentives and potential savings that arise in an energy spot market by varying supply and demand of electricity are passed on to the energy consumer. However, energy spot markets lead, under perfect competitions, to a cost-minimizing dispatch, which, depending on the correlation between prices and emissions along the merit order, may lead to a suboptimal dispatch in an

environmental sense. This phenomenon is known as the merit order emission dilemma as illustrated in [154].

Using PBDR for emission reductions. One option to minimize CEs through load shifting is the usage of MEFs instead of prices as a primary DR incentive signal, as Leerbeck et al. [181] suggest. Real-time MEFs with resolutions between 5 and 15 minutes are already commercially available via application programming interfaces from companies such as *WattTime* [182] or *Tomorrow* [183]. However, since prices and emissions along the merit order are not fully correlated, cost minimization and emission minimization are conflicting. As a second option, this cost-emission conflict can be resolved by internalizing the external costs of climate change by placing an adequate price on CEs. Both options will be analyzed in this chapter.

2.4 Energy system optimization

This chapter provides a concise review of the current state of the art in open-source energy optimization software for DR.

The two most prevalent optimization methods are metaheuristics and mathematical programming [184]. Both methods are used in optimizing the operation and design of complex energy systems. Metaheuristics offer advantages for black-box models or non-convex problems, whereas mathematical programming can guarantee a global optimal solution for explicit equation-based models. Among the various mathematical programming methods, MILP has proven effective for a wide array of related analyses. For example, Zhang and Grossmann [64] identified 42 studies using mathematical optimization models for industrial DR, with 35 of these employing MILP. Most energy-related components exhibit nonlinear behavior, but it is common in literature to approximate this behavior using MILP, which incorporates binary variables for piecewise linear approximation of nonlinear dynamics [185]. Additionally, complexity reduction methods such as TSA can be applied to MILP models for energy system optimization [186].

2.4.1 Multi-objective MILP

Multi-objective optimization combines two or more individual objective functions, such as minimizing costs and CEs, to derive a set of Pareto-optimal solutions [187]. These solutions represent the most favorable trade-offs and can be visualized as Pareto points on a scatter chart. This visualization offers users a spectrum of choices, facilitating informed decision-making by highlighting the range of available options.

2.4.2 Decarbonization of L-MESs

Decarbonization of L-MESs is often addressed by minimizing CEs and costs within multi-objective modeling [188]. For example, [189] presented an efficient energy management model based on a multi-objective optimal power flow problem, which considers the flexibility of storage units in industrial networks. Lombardi et al. [190] analyzed the contribution of energy storage systems, production buffer stocks, and smart transformers to achieving a net-zero energy factory. Additionally, Andiappan [191] reviewed mathematical optimization approaches for energy system synthesis, identifying the concept of eco-industrial parks as a potential future research direction.

2.4.3 Open-source software

In the scientific context, the open-source concept is gaining increasing prominence in the field of energy system analysis [192]. Publishing source code under an open-source license¹ enhances not only transparency and reproducibility but also the quality of the software, owing to the greater incentive for collaboration [193]. However, in contrast to models designed for large geographic scales, models for potential analyses and planning of L-MESs are often developed by consulting firms, where the release of source code is typically not aligned with prevailing corporate practices [194]. As a result, tools for analyzing L-MESs are less commonly published as open-source.

2.4.4 Other energy system frameworks/models

In recent years, the scientific community has produced a number of comprehensive energy system modeling frameworks. [195] reviewed 75 modeling tools, offering an extensive overview of available options. Additionally, [196] presented a review of 24 energy system models and model generators. Kriechbaum et al. [197] focused specifically on open-source modeling frameworks for grid-based MESs. Another significant contribution is [21], which conducted a review on the concepts and validation models of MESs.

Building on these reviews, Table 2.2 in the thesis compares DRAF with other existing frameworks and model generators capable of building bottom-up models for operation and investment decision support in L-MESs. It's important to note that this table includes some comprehensive frameworks like the Open Energy Modelling Framework (oemof), which offer a broad range of functions and aspects that are not fully detailed in the table.

¹A license that is approved by the Open Source Initiative: <https://opensource.org/licenses>

Framework	Open-source	Model			DRAF focus			DRAF features					
		Methodology	MO	Purpose	DR	MTL	IPP	TA	MG	PP	SG	IP	MD
EnergyPLAN [198]	✗	Simulation	-	LTS/IDS	✓	✗	✗	✗	-	✗	✓	✓	✓
HOMER Pro [199]	✗	Simulation ^a	-	IDS, ODS	✓	✗	✗	-	(✓)	✓	✓	✓	✓
TOP-Energy [200]	✗	Simulation+(MI)LP	✓	IDS, ODS	✓	✓	✗	✓	-	(✓)	✓	✓	✓
Calliope [201]	✓ [201]	(MI)LP	✓	IDS, ODS	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗
COMANDO [202]	✓ [202]	NLP	✓	LTS?, ODS	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗
ficus [203]	✓ [203]	(MI)LP	✗	IDS, ODS	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
oemof [204]	✓ [204]	(MI)LP	✓	LTS, IDS, ODS	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	(✓)	✓	✓	✗
OpenTUMFlex [205]	✓ [205]	(MI)LP	✗	IDS ^b	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
OSeMOSYS [206]	✓ [206]	LP	✗	IDS	✗	✗	✗ ^c	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗
Temoa [207]	✓ [207]	LP	✗	LTS	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗
urbs [208]	✓ [208]	LP	✗	IDS, ODS	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗
DRAF [209]	✓ [209]	(MI)LP	✓	IDS, ODS	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

^a: optimization through automatic sensitivity analysis

^b: focus on residential sector

^c: focus on developing countries

(✓): partly applicable

TABLE 2.2: Comparison of DRAF with other bottom-up model frameworks for operation and investment decision support of L-MESs divided by whether they are open-source. **Legend:** Simulation: computer simulation, LTS: long term scenarios, IDS/ODS: investment/operation decision support, MO: multi-objective, TA: time series analysis, MG: model generator, PP: parameter preparation, SG: scenario generator, IP: interactive plotting, DR: demand response, MTL: multiple temperature levels, IPP: industrial production processes, MD: metadata handling. **Sources:** Based on [\[195\]](#) and own research as of November 25, 2021.

Oemof is a powerful and versatile framework in the field of energy system modeling [\[210\]](#). Specifically, oemof serves as an organizational framework to bundle software for energy modeling, such as the model generator oemof-solph [\[211\]](#). However, oemof-solph employs Pyomo for model generation, which builds models slower than the Gurobi Python interface, GurobiPy [\[212\]](#). The framework does not handle metadata like units, parameter descriptions, and sources of parameter values. Although the oemof cosmos offers various packages for parameter preparation, like the load curve generation package demandlib [\[213\]](#), it does not include preparation of crucial data for modeling price-based DR in L-MESs, such as dynamic CEFs. Langiu et al. [\[202\]](#) proposed the framework for **component-oriented modeling and optimization for nonlinear design and operation** (COMANDO). It focuses on nonlinear optimization, however, it does not include features for parameter preprocessing, interactive plotting, or metadata handling. There are also initiatives exploring the speed benefits of the Julia programming language in energy system modeling, such as NEMO [\[214\]](#), which drew inspiration from OSeMOSYS. However, Julia, being a relatively new programming language, lacks the extensive community support that is crucial for DRAF’s target group, particularly programming beginners [\[215\]](#).

Frameworks with a modular structure and a clear separation between program logic and data, such as oemof, offer flexibility for a wide range of analyses across different temporal and geographic resolutions [\[204\]](#). This generic approach provides significant advantages for large-scale electricity system analyses, particularly in terms of transparency, reusability,

and maintainability. However, to effectively utilize such software as a decision support tool in an L-MES, it needs to be adapted to the specific problem through additional steps:

1. Model adaptation to industry-specific conditions.
2. Research and processing of market data such as dynamic CEFs (depending on the country, year, and temporal resolution) and cost functions.
3. Generation of weather-dependent energy-relevant time series such as energy yield time series PV or thermal load profiles.
4. Preparation, analysis, and plausibility check of project-specific data such as electrical load profiles.
5. Model parameterization.
6. Adaptation of result output functions such as plots and tables to the particular data structure.

Commercial tools, as referenced in the first three entries of Table 2.2, have addressed the need for specialized software in specific application areas, thereby accelerating the modeling process. These tools are designed to streamline various aspects of the energy system modeling, specifically tailored to the requirements of certain industries or applications. However, a corresponding open-source alternative, which could leverage the benefits of the open-source model as discussed in Section 2.4.3, is not currently available.

2.5 TSA of energy system models

Hoffmann et al. [216] and Teichgraeber and Brandt [217] recently reviewed articles on TSA of energy system models while Kotzur et al. [186] provide a useful guide for complexity handling in energy system optimization.

Table 2.3 shows recent literature proposing TSA for MESs and compares it with the research carried out in Chapter 9. Kotzur et al. [218] compared five different clustering methods for TSA including average, k-means, k-medoids, and hierarchical. They concluded that the model type (multi-node vs. single-node) and the temporal storage range (seasonal vs. short-term) have a bigger impact on the introduced relative objective error than the selected aggregation method. However, it was shown, that the usage of averaged values underestimates system costs and should be avoided. Kannengießer et al. [223] proposed an approach to simplify MILP optimization models for energy systems by splitting the problem into two levels: Firstly, determining the energy system structure using TSA and secondly, conducting operation optimization and technology scaling. Baumgärtner et al. [122] examined the influence of time-dependent XEFs on low-carbon utility systems and demonstrated that considering these factors can lead to CE reductions of up to 6% at the

TABLE 2.3: Comparison of the work of this chapter to recent literature that proposed or used TSA algorithms for MESs.

Article		Used or proposed approach			Considered DR attributes			Analyses			
Year	Ref.	Typical periods	Segments	Seasonal storage ¹	RTP	XEFs	MEFs	DAC costs	Hyper-parameters ⁴	Back-testing ⁵	Use case(s)
2018	[218]	✓							✓		residential & island
2018	[219]	✓		✓					✓		residential & island
2018	[220]	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓		urban residential
2019	[122]	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓				industrial
2019	[221]	✓	✓		✓						industrial
2019	[222]	✓		✓	✓ ²				✓	✓	urban residential
2019	[223]	✓		✓					✓		residential urban & island
2019	[224]	✓		✓					✓		national
2020	[225]	✓		✓	✓		✓		✓		residential
2021	[226]	✓					✓				district heating
2021	[227]	✓			✓				✓		industrial
2021	[228]	✓	✓	✓					✓		residential & national
2021	[229]	✓		✓	✓						research campus
2021	[230]	✓							✓		district heating & cooling
2022	[231]	✓		✓					✓		industrial
2022	[232]	✓		✓					✓		national
2022	[233]	✓			✓	✓		✓ ³			industrial
2022	[234]	✓	✓						✓		international & local
2022	[235]	✓							✓	✓	national
2023	[236]	✓		✓	✓				✓		local
2023	[237]	✓		✓					✓		multi-regional
This chapter		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	industrial

¹ Modeling formulation to allow storage durations longer than the typical period length² Considered time-of-use tariff³ Considered different carbon prices⁴ Multiple TSA runs with varied numbers of typical periods and/or numbers of segments⁵ Backtest TSA-based MES design against the full-year model

same costs, and up to 60% when incorporating MEFs. The findings emphasize the potential for time-dependent XEFs and MEFs to facilitate climate-friendly demand-side management and achieve significant CE reductions. Tejada-Arango et al. [224] proposed a method based on linked typical periods for incorporating short-term energy storage systems in stochastic hydrothermal dispatch models. This approach allows for more accurate operational decisions and hourly opportunity cost calculations, showing significant improvements over traditional models based on load duration curves. In [225], clustering methods for designing energy systems in Zero Emission Neighborhoods were investigated. The study found that k-means clustering outperformed k-medoids, clustering days was more efficient than clustering hours, and the choice of normalization method had minimal impact on results. Hering et al. [226] introduced a mixed-integer quadratically constrained program with temperature constraints for optimizing the integration of low-temperature waste heat in a district heating network. The study revealed a trade-off between economic and environmental optimal solutions,

demonstrating the importance of temperature in the optimization process. Hoettecke et al. [227] proposed an integer programming-based TSA approach for long-term industrial investment planning, considering industrial PBDR. Their method achieved similar results to the full annual time series for three industrial plants in Southern Germany, suggesting that a selection of 10 days can effectively represent the relevant statistical features of the examined sites. Hoffmann et al. [228] investigated different TSA strategies in energy system models and their impact on optimization results. The study indicated the choice of aggregation method depends on the specific mathematical structure of the model with typical periods being more suitable for depicting storage operations and typical time steps being effective when time-linking constraints are not considered. In Yokoyama et al. [230], a hierarchical MILP method and model reduction techniques for the multi-objective optimal design of energy supply systems were investigated. The research showed that clustering methods can enhance computational efficiency for certain objective functions but may be limited for others. Göke and Kendzioriski [232] explored the impact of TSA on macro-energy system models for renewable energy systems. The study found that the inclusion of renewables and storage reduced the effectiveness of TSA. Hoffmann et al. [234] proposed an algorithm designed to identify the Pareto-optimal aggregation in terms of the number of typical days versus the number of intra-daily temporal resolutions (segments). Additionally, the study enhanced previously proposed aggregation methods by explicitly maintaining the original time series' value distribution. This refinement resulted in improved accuracy for both a local self-sufficient single-node building-level model and a capacity expansion model that considered 96 European regions. Kuepper et al. [235] investigated the impact of TSA methods on optimal system design, specifically in low-emission systems with high shares of variable renewable energies. It was found that using representative days to model wind time-series data introduces negative impacts, leading to decreased reliability of supply, biased installed capacity estimation, and underestimated total system costs, particularly in cases with strong CE constraints. An open-source analysis framework was provided to assess future TSA methods and mitigate these identified negative impacts. Thiran et al. [237] explored the use of typical days clustering to simplify energy system optimization models in the context of the energy transition and integration of renewable energy sources. The researchers demonstrated that using a reduced number of typical days significantly decreases computational time while maintaining a low design error, a new bottom-up metric that they proposed. However, given the correlation between *a priori* and *a posteriori* metrics, they suggest using *a priori* metrics to choose the number of typical days.

2.5.1 Seasonal storage formulation

For seasonal storage systems which are crucial for sustainable energy systems, the storage duration may exceed the duration of a typical period. In this case, simple cyclic conditions that couple the state of charge (SOC) at the beginning and end of each typical period are insufficient. However, with special model formulations [219, 220], seasonal storage systems can be modeled even in a TSA context.

Gabrielli et al. [220] suggested modeling the storage SOC for the entire year while using a look-up table to link to the charging and discharging power of the typical periods. Kotzur et al. [219] proposed the decomposition and superposition of two different SOC contributions with different time grids: the inter-period and the intra-period SOC. This approach assumes that the SOC's first derivatives are the same in all periods linking to a certain typical period. E.g., in two different periods that link to the same typical period the charging and discharging decisions are identical, but the SOC values are different, see Fig. 2.4. While the approach by Gabrielli et al. is easier to implement, the reduction of computational complexity is higher in the approach by Kotzur et al., since it does not require a coupled SOC variable for every time step of the year. Blanke et al. [231] compared the above-mentioned seasonal storage formulations and extended the model of Kotzur et al. reducing the calculation time by approximately 10% while producing the same results.

FIGURE 2.4: Scheme of seasonal storage modeling with typical periods.

2.5.2 Segmentation & hyperparameters

TSA methods can be advanced by segmentation, a process where similar neighboring time steps are merged and weighted by their individual time step lengths [186]. An example is

shown in Fig. 2.5. Combining segmentation with typical periods allows for the tuning of certain hyperparameters such as the number of typical periods or the number of segments.

FIGURE 2.5: Exemplary distribution of 12 typical days with 8 segments each.

2.5.3 Evaluation of TSA accuracy

Evaluation approaches for TSA-induced error can be divided into *a priori* approaches (based on the model's input data) and *a posteriori* approaches (based on the quantified impact TSA has on the model's results). While the *a priori* approaches compare the original full-year input data with the reduced input data without running an optimization model, *a posteriori* approaches measure the impact of TSA on the results of the optimization models. While much effort has been made in *a priori* evaluations, fewer studies investigated TSA accuracy using *a posteriori* evaluation [237].

2.5.3.1 *A priori* evaluation

Three different *a priori* TSA evaluation methods have been used in the literature: The time series error, the duration curve error, and the correlation error [237]. All measure the accuracy of the aggregated time series to represent the complete time series from different aspects. The time series error measures at the deviation between the normed original time series and the aggregated time series [234]. The duration curve error considers the difference in the value distribution [218]. The correlation error involves the calculation of the Pearson correlation coefficient between the original and the aggregated time series [237]. Often the relative root mean squared error (RMSE) is used in this context.

Allen et al. [238] applied hierarchical clustering to condense building heating and cooling load profiles into a selection of days that could effectively represent an entire year. The analysis revealed that a subset of 30 days could adequately capture the annual heating and cooling load profiles, achieving a coefficient of variation RMSE of 10.8% and 5.9%, respectively. These results were considered acceptable according to the criteria outlined in ASHRAE Guideline 14 [239].

2.5.3.2 *A posteriori* evaluation

While the clustering error (*a priori*) was analyzed in detail, a lack of investigations into the effects of TSA on the model results (*a posteriori*) was recently indicated by [237]. *A posteriori* methods evaluate the TSA accuracy by comparing the outcome, (e.g., objective function value, MES design, or system constraint violations) between the TSA-based and the original model.

In some studies, the optimal capacities of the TSA-based problem are compared with the full-scale problem [218, 227]. E.g. Kannengießer et al. [223] analyzed the power and energy capacity error of conversion and storage technologies, respectively. Thiran et al. [237] proposed an *a posteriori* design error based on the technology sizing and primary energy use for multi-regional energy system optimization models. In a multi-regional energy system case study, they demonstrated a correlation between the *a posteriori* design error and the *a priori* TSA error.

Hoffmann et al. [228] suggested calculating the sum of squared relative cost deviations across all technologies. Multiple studies calculated the relative error of the objective function which is usually total annualized costs (TACs) [218, 237]. However, they only considered the original and the TSA-based model.

Kuepper et al. [235] proposed a TSA testing framework to investigate the impact of TSA on capacity expansion model outcomes such as total costs, lost load, and excess CEs. The study used a two-stage approach to backtest the TSA-based design scenario on the original input time series. For future research, they suggested that seasonal storage coupling approaches should be examined. Gabrielli et al. [222] calculated the TAC deviation between the original model (ideal case) and the TSA-based system design operated on the original time series to identify how many typical days are required to represent the original input time series. Interestingly, the results showed that the deviation increased with increasingly ambitious decarbonization targets. Note that the information about the degree of decarbonization ambitions is not captured in the time series, and, therefore, is not considered in the *a priori* TSA error. From the reviewed studies, [222] and [235] were the only studies that backtested the TSA-based MES design against the original time series in a two-stage

approach. However, unlike this work, previous studies did not consider segmentation, varying direct air capture (DAC) prices, or MEFs. Also, they used a case study in the residential and not in the industrial sector. Finally, they did not explicitly calculate the TSA-induced TAC and CE errors.

2.6 Conclusions of literature review

The reviewed literature highlights several significant gaps:

1. Environmental analyses of DR have predominantly focused on XEF, while readily available MEFs for European countries are lacking.
2. As a result, comprehensive comparisons of European countries regarding the impact of DR on CEs are limited.
3. Although numerous studies addressed the potential of industrial DR in specific areas, there is a shortage of comprehensive model frameworks that integrate flexible systems such as storage, production, and cross-sectional technologies to assess their interconnected impacts.
4. Despite the growing number of open-source modeling frameworks, there is a notable lack of modular, pre-parametrized frameworks for quantifying non-residential DR potentials.
5. There is also a need for more real-world case studies focusing on non-residential DR in low-carbon MESs.
6. Lastly, non-residential DR is underrepresented in the evolving literature on TSA methods for MES design and investment decision-making.

Part II

EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

Chapter 3

The effect of price-based demand response on carbon emissions in European electricity markets

Abstract. Price-based demand response (PBDR) has recently been attributed great economic but also environmental potential. However, the determination of its short-term effects on carbon emissions (CEs) requires the knowledge of marginal emission factors (MEFs), which compared to grid mix emission factors (XEFs), are cumbersome to calculate due to the complex characteristics of national electricity markets. This chapter, therefore, proposes two merit order-based methods to approximate hourly MEFs and applies them to readily available datasets from 20 European countries for the years 2017–2019. Based on the calculated electricity prices, standardized daily load shifts were simulated which indicated that CEs increased for 8 of the 20 countries and by 2.1% on average. Thus, under specific circumstances, PBDR leads to CEs increases, mainly due to the economic advantage fuel sources such as lignite and coal have in the merit order. MEF-based load shifts reduced the mean resulting CEs by 35%, albeit with 56% lower monetary cost savings compared to price-based load shifts. Finally, by repeating the load shift simulations for different carbon price levels, the impact of the carbon price on the resulting CEs was analyzed. The Spearman correlation coefficient between carbon intensity and marginal cost along the German merit order substantially increased with increasing carbon price. The coefficients were -0.13 for the 2019 carbon price of €24.9/t, 0 for €42.6/t, and 0.4 for €100.0/t. Therefore, with adequate carbon prices, PBDR can be an effective tool for both economical and environmental improvement.

Acknowledgments. The contents of this chapter are based on the paper *The effect of price-based demand response on carbon emissions in European electricity markets: The importance of adequate carbon prices* [240]. Markus Fleschutz is the primary author of this paper. This research was performed as part of the MeSSO Research Group at the Munster Technological University (MTU) and in relation to the project WIN4Climate as part of the National Climate Initiative financed by the Federal Ministry of the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU), Germany according to a decision of the German Federal Parliament (No. 03KF0094 A). It was additionally funded by the MTU Risam Scholarship Scheme, Ireland.

3.1 Overview and context

Motivation. Due to the characteristics of the electricity market, available approaches used for CEs accounting lead to misleading results when applied in the context of DR. Specifically, they overestimate the environmental potential of PBDR by ignoring the nature of the electricity markets and their special phenomenon called the merit order dilemma of emissions. This phenomenon refers to the fact that, for electricity generation, certain emission-intensive fuel types are, due to their low marginal costs, preferred to relatively lower emission-intensive technologies. At the time of writing, for example, highly efficient combined-cycle gas power plants are, according to the merit-order dispatch principle, only considered after more carbon-intensive lignite-fired power plants. Adequate approaches based on the idea of marginal emissions, require detailed data, which are usually not available. As a consequence, as long as the merit order of an energy market does not correlate with the CEFs, PBDR cannot exploit the full carbon reduction potential of load shifting. In the European Union, spot market prices already include a carbon price within the European Union Emission Trading System (EU ETS), however, this carbon price is currently too low to make a substantial impact on PBDR. Increasing the carbon price to an appropriate level is crucial to exploit this potential by internalizing the external cost of climate change and creating financial incentives for sustainable development [241].

Merit order dilemma for BPDR. The fluctuating feed-in of vRESs significantly affects the CEs of the electricity supplied to consumers. In times of high vRES shares, the CEs per produced unit of electricity are usually lower than in times of lower vRES shares since less fossil-based power plants per produced unit of electricity are in operation. This phenomenon leads to the hypothesis that a shift of energy consumption from an hour with a low vRES share to an hour with a high vRES share leads to a decrease in CEs. In fact, a calculation according to XEFs, which describes the current generation mix of the electricity

system supports this hypothesis in many cases, e.g., [77, 123, 160]. However, price-based or XEF-based load shifting might lead to increased emissions as illustrated in Fig. 3.1.

FIGURE 3.1: Exemplary case where price-based or XEF-based load shifting leads to increased total CEs: Two hours t_1 and t_2 are assumed, with the same loads but different levels of wind generation ①. In t_2 , less wind implies a higher residual load ②, thus, a different operating point in the merit order curve ③. This causes a price spread in the spot market ④ which incentivizes a load shift of 1 kWh from t_2 to t_1 ⑤. The power plant that increases production is coal-fired in the load shifting scenario and gas-fired in the non-load-shifting scenario ⑥. Since the MEF at t_1 is higher than the MEF at t_2 , the load shift causes increased MEF-based emissions ⑦. In contrast, the XEF is lower at t_1 than at t_2 , since at t_2 , coal and gas substitute the reduced wind. Therefore, in this example, using XEFs to quantify the effect of the load shift is misleading as it actually results in increased CEs ⑧.

Literature gap. A summarization of the current state-of-art literature related to the assessment of the short-term environmental impact of DR is discussed in detail in Section 2.3. In summary, fuel type-specific, temporally resolved national generation data (e.g., from the ENTSO-E Transparency Platform (ETP) [242]) allows for the calculation of temporally resolved XEFs which are necessary for CEs accounting of electric consumers. However, for the environmental evaluation of PBDR activities like load shifting, dynamic MEFs are needed, since they reflect the effects of system changes, which XEFs do not. Due to the lack of power plant specific electricity generation data, the purely empirical identification of the marginal power plant is not straightforward [243]. As a consequence, to the best of the author’s knowledge, dynamic historic MEFs are not available free of charge for European countries.

Contribution. This chapter, quantitatively analyzes the effect of load shifting on CEs in 20 European countries using hourly XEFs and MEFs. To overcome the barriers arising from the heterogeneous data quality, a piecewise linear (PWL) method to approximate hourly MEFs based on the technology mix is proposed. The PWL method is validated with the power plant (PP) method which is applicable if detailed data on the generators are

available. Since undesirable effects of price-based load shifts on CEs can be observed, this chapter investigates how this effect could be mitigated by an increase of carbon prices.

The novel contributions of this chapter are:

1. Quantitative comparison of the environmental effects of price-based, XEF-based, and MEF-based load shifting between 20 European countries using hourly XEFs and MEFs.
2. Proposal and validation of the PWL method which approximates MEFs and XEFs from datasets readily available for European countries.
3. Application of the PWL method to 20 European countries for the years 2017–2019 to compare the resulting CEFs.
4. Evaluation of the impact of varying carbon prices on the marginal cost–emission correlation, the merit order, and on the effects of load shifting.
5. Identification of the carbon price (€42.6/t) which decouples the carbon intensities from costs in the German merit order.

The resulting hourly and quarter-hourly XEFs, MEFs, marginal costs, and marginal fuel types as well as residual load, total load and marginal power plant efficiency can be downloaded as CSV files for 20 European countries and the years 2017–2020 from <https://github.com/DrafProject/marginal-emission-factors> [244].

Chapter organization. The remainder of this chapter is structured as followed. First, all datasets used for the calculation of the CEFs are described in Section 3.2.1. Then, the methods for the CEFs calculation, PP and PWL, are detailed in Section 3.2.2. In Section 3.2.3, the PP method is applied to the power plant resolved dataset for Germany in 2019 to evaluate the approximation error of the PWL method. Section 3.3 details the results of applying the PWL method to the data of 20 European countries. Section 3.4 concludes the chapter.

3.2 Materials and methods

3.2.1 Datasets used in this chapter

Net generation. For the calculation of the temporally resolved residual and total load of a national electricity system, historic electricity generation time series data (“Aggregated Generation per Type”) for each fuel type f and country c from the ETP [242] were used and accessed via the entsoe-py client [245]. For the years 2017–2019 and the 20 countries used

FIGURE 3.2: Overview of used data from ETP [242] per fuel type and country after preprocessing for the year 2019: (a) Net electricity generation and (b) Installed generation capacity. Blue fields with ‘-’ indicate missing data.

in this chapter, 10.2 Million data points were processed. Across all European countries, 20 different fuel types are used for electricity generation. The temporal resolution of the raw data varies depending on the country (15, 30, and 60 minute intervals). A comprehensive review of the data composition of the ETP can be found in [246]. Within the data preprocessing for the simulation, all time series were downsampled to hourly resolution. In the case of missing values and outliers, the last available data points were considered instead. The percentage of missing values that were filled were 1.9% for 2017, 1.3% for 2018, and 0.4% for 2019. However, 67% of the missing values appear in only two fuel types (‘Fossil Hard coal’ and ‘Other’) for the Netherlands for the years 2017 and 2018. Nine outliers were detected by a combination of z-score analysis and treated as missing values, see Appendix B.5. To save space, the fuel types were renamed¹. Fig. 3.2a shows the share of annual generation per fuel type and country in relation to the total generation for 2019 after preprocessing. Appendices B.1 and B.2 contain basic analyses of available generation data from the ETP [242] for Europe and Germany, respectively.

Installed generation capacity. Installed electricity generation capacities per fuel type f were also obtained from the ETP [242]. The same renaming of fuel types as in Section 3.2.1

¹Biomass → biomass, Fossil Brown coal/Lignite → lignite, Fossil Oil → oil, Fossil Gas → gas, Fossil Hard coal → coal, Hydro Run-of-river and poundage → hydro, Nuclear → nuclear

was conducted. Fig. 3.2b shows all preprocessed data for 2019 in a concise way. Appendix B.1 contains an overview of available installed generation capacity data on the ETP [242].

Open Power System Data (OPSD) power plant list. For the PP method and to verify the PWL method with a higher granularity of generation capacity, the power plant list from the OPSD [247] was used. This data consists of 893 power plants for the electricity market region Germany, Austria and Luxembourg with 38 features each. The most relevant features were country, capacity, date for commissioning and shutdown, type, as well as efficiency estimate. In this thesis, for the sake of simplicity, individually controllable power plant units are referred to as power plants. In Fig. 3.6, e.g., the nine light brown horizontally distributed dots near 20 GW represent the nine generation units of the Jänschwalde power plant which have similar characteristics. For the construction of the merit order, only active power plants were considered by constraining the year of simulation after date of commissioning and before shutdown. The distribution of efficiency and capacity can be seen in Appendix B.3.

Global Energy Observatory (GEO) power plant list. Due to the particularly strong influence of power plant efficiency, power plants are further distinguished according to their technology type in open cycle gas turbines (indicated with gas) and combined-cycle gas turbines (indicated with gas_cc). The division into gas and gas_cc was based on k^{cc} which is the proportion of combined-cycle gas turbines in all gas power plants for each analyzed country. These shares were calculated from the GEO power plant list [248] with two exceptions: For Germany, the share was calculated from the OPSD list in favour of more detailed data. For Serbia, no gas power plants were listed on [248] at the time of data retrieval. Independent investigation identified its share to be $k^{cc} = 0\%$. All used values for k^{cc} are listed in Table 3.1.

TABLE 3.1: Assumption of k^{cc} (share of combined-cycle gas turbines across all gas fuelled power plants in %).

AT	99.57 ^b	ES	94.73 ^b	HU	32.80 ^b	PL	100.00 ^b
BE	80.92 ^b	FI	100.00 ^b	IE	71.76 ^b	PT	93.26 ^b
CZ	100.00 ^b	FR	83.50 ^b	IT	99.78 ^b	RO	46.24 ^b
DE	53.52 ^a	GB	42.31 ^b	LT	0.00 ^b	RS	0.00 ^c
DK	28.12 ^b	GR	79.90 ^b	NL	85.96 ^b	SI	0.00 ^b

^a from the OPSD power plant list of the PP method [247]

^b GEO list [248]

^c [249]

Carbon emission certificate prices. In order to calculate the carbon-related marginal costs for the merit order, European Emission Allowances (EUA) prices of the EU ETS are

used from the European Energy Exchange (EEX) [250] (downloaded via [251]). The data was downsampled from weekly to annual resolution with average method and used in mean annual form as c^{GHG} , see Fig. 3.3.

FIGURE 3.3: Historic annual average CO₂-emission prices of the EU ETS for the years 2008–2019. Data source: [250].

Fuel type-specific emissions and costs. Table 3.2 shows an overview of the fuel type f specific input parameters used in this chapter. The fuel type-specific cost were used depending on the year and in the case of natural gas, also depending on the country. As fuel type-specific carbon-intensity ε_f , operational net emission factors from [252] were used which, in contrast to life cycle assessment approaches, do not include emissions embodied in infrastructure. This is consistent with the short-term nature of PBDR.

TABLE 3.2: Overview of the fuel type f specific input parameters for the merit order and its data sources.

Fuel type f	CO ₂ -intensity ε_f tCO ₂ eq/MWh	Fuel price c_f €/MWh
oil	0.28 [252]	54.31 ^y [253], [254], [255]
gas	0.25 [252]	26.10 ^{y,c} [254]
coal	0.34 [252]	14.58 ^y [253], [254]
lignite	0.36 [252]	6.18 ^y [253], [254]
nuclear	0.0 [252]	4.18 ^y [253]

^y Year-specific values were used. Here: 2019.

^c Country-specific values were used. Here: DE.

Transmission efficiency. Based on the methods employed in [159] and [122] a constant transmission efficiency η^{T} is employed to consider all losses for transmission and distribution. Table 3.3 shows the used average value over the last four published years (2010–2014) for each country [256].

3.2.2 Methods

This chapter proposes two approximating methods, the PP method and the PWL method, to calculate dynamic MEFs and XEFs from the available data. Both methods (PP and PWL)

TABLE 3.3: Transmission efficiencies η^T used in simulations. Data source: [256].

AT	94.9%	ES	90.8%	HU	88.8%	PL	93.3%
BE	95.1%	FI	96.2%	IE	92.3%	PT	90.6%
CZ	95.1%	FR	93.6%	IT	93.0%	RO	88.4%
DE	96.1%	GB	92.3%	LT	79.5%	RS	84.7%
DK	93.7%	GR	94.2%	NL	95.2%	SI	94.6%

include the application of a country and year-specific merit order on historic residual load data to simulate the time-dependent dispatch of conventional power plants and to identify the marginal power plant per time step t . In other words, the prices, XEFs, and MEFs from the simulation depend on the available conventional power plants, the time-dependent RES shares, and the total load, which was proxied by the national total generation.

The PP method takes power plant specific efficiencies as input data while the PWL method approximates these efficiencies internally. More specifically, the PWL method uses national installed generation capacities per fuel type to discretize the fuel type-specific generation capacity into virtual power plants. While the PP method may be more precise, the PWL method is more suited for this analysis as power plant specific efficiency data are not readily available for most European countries. However, the PP method is used to validate the PWL method for Germany where more detailed data is available.

FIGURE 3.4: Schematic depiction of data sources, data subsets and special calculations of the PP, PWL, and PWLv method to calculate CEF. White boxes indicate the following datasets: ETP [242], GEO [248], OPSD [247], Quaschnig [252], EEX [250], Worldbank [256], Konstantin [253], DESTATIS [257]. Light grey boxes indicate subsets or modified data. The dimension of each dataset is denoted by the characters t, y, f, and p in brackets. Dark grey boxes indicate special mathematical operations.

Fig. 3.4 shows a schematic depiction of the data sources and calculation steps. Besides the two main methods (PP and PWL), it also shows the PWL validation mode (PWLv), which is detailed in Section 3.2.3.

For the sake of simplicity, from here onwards, the term fuel types also include gas_cc which technically is a special combination of a fuel type and a technology. The remainder of this section describes the calculation of XEFs and MEFs using the PP and the PWL method.

3.2.2.1 Calculation of MEFs

Regardless of the merit order calculation method, the power plant specific emissions ε_p are given by:

$$\varepsilon_p = \frac{\varepsilon_f}{\eta_p^{\text{el}}} \quad (3.1)$$

where ε_f is the CE intensity per fuel type f and η_p^{el} is the generation efficiency per power plant p .

The time-dependent dispatch is then given by applying the merit order on the residual load. The time-dependent MEFs are given by the power plant specific emission intensity ε_p of the marginal power plant in given time step t divided by the transmission efficiency η^{T} :

$$\text{MEF}_t = \frac{\sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}} \varepsilon_p \gamma_{t,p}^{\text{m}}}{\eta^{\text{T}}} \quad (3.2)$$

where $\gamma_{t,p}^{\text{m}}$ is a binary variable that indicates the marginal power plant:

$$\gamma_{t,p}^{\text{m}} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} P_i^{\text{installed}} < P_t^{\text{resi}} \leq \sum_{i=1}^p P_i^{\text{installed}}, \\ 0, & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (3.3)$$

where $P_i^{\text{installed}}$ is the installed capacity of power plant i and P_t^{resi} is the residual load of time step t .

3.2.2.2 Calculation of XEFs

In all methods (PP, PWL, PWLv), the grid mix emission factor XEF_t is calculated using the electricity supply-specific emissions divided by the electricity consumption:

$$\text{XEF}_t = \frac{\sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}} \varepsilon_p \gamma_{t,p}^{\text{x}} P_p^{\text{installed}} \Delta t}{\eta^{\text{T}} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} E_{t,f}^{\text{gen}}}. \quad (3.4)$$

where ε_p is the CE intensity per power plant p , $P_p^{\text{installed}}$ is the installed power plant capacity, $\gamma_{t,p}^{\text{x}}$ is the capacity utilization rate defined in Eq. (3.5), Δt is the time step width, η^{T} is the constant transmission efficiency considering all transmission and distribution losses, $E_{t,f}^{\text{gen}}$ is

the generated energy per fuel type f and time step t , and \mathcal{F} is the set of all generation fuel types.

$$\gamma_{t,p}^x = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \sum_{i=1}^p P_i^{\text{installed}} < P_t^{\text{resi}}, \\ 0, & \text{if } \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} P_i^{\text{installed}} \geq P_t^{\text{resi}}, \\ \frac{P_t^{\text{resi}} - \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} P_i^{\text{installed}}}{P_p^{\text{installed}}}, & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (3.5)$$

3.2.2.3 Residual load

Since fuel type-specific generation data $P_{t,f}^{\text{gen}}$ is available in most European countries, the residual load P_t^{resi} is approximated by the sum of energy generated by the conventional power plants for all methods (PP, PWL, PWLv) and both CEF types (XEF and MEF):

$$P_t^{\text{resi}} = \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}^{\text{CONV}}} P_{t,f}^{\text{gen}} \quad (3.6)$$

where $\mathcal{F}^{\text{CONV}}$ is the set of all available conventional fuel types (first 11 fuel types in Fig. 3.2a).

FIGURE 3.5: Top: Distribution of the CONV share (left) and RES share (right) of the total national generation. White dots represent medians. Bottom: Corresponding average values in %.

Fig. 3.5 shows the distributions and average values of the time-dependent CONV share and RES share of the total national generation for the year 2019 for different countries. The average RES share varies from 7% in the Netherlands (NL) to 77% in Denmark (DK). Given Eq. (3.6) and the limitation to national electricity supply, in this analysis, the CONV share in Fig. 3.5 is also the residual load share of the total national load.

3.2.2.4 Merit order calculation with the PP method

The PP method can be used to calculate the merit order if power plant specific efficiencies are available. The merit order results from sorting all active power plants p according to their ascending marginal costs c_p^m , which are given by:

$$c_p^m = \underbrace{\frac{x_f}{\eta_p^{\text{el}}}}_{\text{fuel costs}} + \underbrace{\frac{\varepsilon_f}{\eta_p^{\text{el}}} c^{\text{GHG}}}_{\text{carbon-related costs}} \quad (3.7)$$

where η_p^{el} is the efficiency per power plant p (data from Section 3.2.1), c^{GHG} is the carbon price (data from Section 3.2.1), and ε_f and x_f are the fuel type-specific emission intensities and prices, respectively (data from Section 3.2.1).

Fig. 3.7a) exemplarily shows the resulting merit order with power plant specific marginal costs c_p^m and emissions ε_p^m for Germany, 2019.

3.2.2.5 Merit order calculation with the PWL method

The PWL method is a piecewise-linear approximation approach that can be used to approximate the country and year-specific merit order if power plant specific capacity and efficiency data are unavailable. For most European countries only fuel type-specific data are provided, hence the PP method which is based on the power plant list including power plant efficiencies is not applicable in these countries. A very simple approach to approximate MEFs is the usage of fuel type-specific efficiencies. In this PWL method, instead, it is assumed that all countries have the same maximum and minimum efficiency per fuel type and that within each fuel type the capacity over the range of occurring efficiencies is uniformly distributed. These assumptions allow us to approximate the efficiencies of the power plants by a piecewise-linear function. For each fuel type, the minimum and maximum efficiencies were determined by the minimum and maximum values of an ordinary least squares regression of the power plant efficiencies of the German power plant list, see Fig. 3.6. To enable the non-disjunct structure of the merit order, which can be observed in reality, the total generation capacities per fuel type were discretized into discrete equally sized virtual power plants. Country and fuel type-specific values were used, see Appendix B.4. They were computed from the GEO power plant list [248], which contains capacity data but no efficiency data.

FIGURE 3.6: Ordinary least squares regressions on efficiencies of the power plant list to identify fuel type-specific minimal and maximal values (indicated with black open circles). Linear interpolation between these minimal and maximal values result in a piecewise linear function. Source: Calculations based on [247].

3.2.3 Validation of the PWL method

To evaluate the approximation error of the PWL method, the PP method was applied to the detailed dataset for Germany described in Section 3.2.1 for the years 2015–2019. For this, the PWLv method is introduced as a validation variant of the PWL method which ensures consistency of data sources between the two main methods (PP and PWL). In Fig. 3.4, it can be seen that in contrast to the PWL method, the PWLv method used installed generation capacity data from the German OPSD power plant list to ensure the same data basis with the PP method. The PWLv-based merit order for Germany, 2019 is shown in Fig. 3.7b); and for better comparison, Fig. 3.8 shows the same merit order together with the PP-based merit order. Fig. 3.9 shows a comparison of the two CEF-types and the two calculation methods applied to Germany for the first week in May 2019. It can be seen that the PWL method succeeds to represent the MEFs well. A whole-year comparison between the resulting MEF_t^{PP} and $\text{MEF}_t^{\text{PWLv}}$ can be found in Appendix B.7.

Fig. 3.10 shows the values of the three different relative error types that were calculated to evaluate the approximation quality of the PWL method compared to the PP method:

1. The error of power plant specific marginal costs c_p^m and emission intensities ε_p along the merit order ($\delta^{\text{MO},c}$, $\delta^{\text{MO},\varepsilon}$). $\delta^{\text{MO},c}$ and $\delta^{\text{MO},\varepsilon}$ were calculated as averaged relative

FIGURE 3.7: Merit orders for Germany, 2019 based on a) PP method and b) PWLv method, respectively. The background colors correspond to the fuel types. The x-axis is shared.

FIGURE 3.8: Direct comparison of PP vs. PWLv method based merit orders. The colors of the additional horizontal bars at the top correspond to the fuel types.

FIGURE 3.9: Comparison between XEFs, MEFs, and marginal prices for the methods PP and PWLv in hourly resolution for the first week in May 2019 in Germany.

	type 1		type 2			type 3		
	$\delta^{MO,\epsilon}$	$\delta^{MO,\epsilon}$	δ^P	δ^{MEF}	δ^{XEF}	$\delta^{\bar{P}}$	$\delta^{\bar{MEF}}$	$\delta^{\bar{XEF}}$
2015	1.78	5.63	2.40	9.91	1.21	2.11	1.79	1.16
2016	1.52	4.93	1.67	9.64	0.73	0.79	0.40	0.46
2017	1.51	7.48	1.93	6.38	0.53	0.06	0.04	0.47
2018	1.54	14.26	1.87	9.68	0.65	0.04	1.11	0.64
2019	1.36	16.65	1.82	16.21	1.14	0.06	0.42	0.43
mean	1.54	9.79	1.94	10.36	0.85	0.61	0.75	0.63

FIGURE 3.10: Relative approximation errors of the PWL method vs. PP method for Germany and the years 2015–2019 in % grouped in three error types.

errors of marginal costs and emission intensities, respectively, between the PWLv method and the PP method along the merit order. To be able to deal with the different cumulative power values in the merit orders, the merit order was discretized by 10 MW-elements which are more than ten times smaller than the average power plant.

2. The error of time-dependent prices, MEFs, and XEFs (δ^P , δ^{MEF} , δ^{XEF}).
3. The error of yearly aggregated prices, MEFs, and XEFs ($\delta^{\bar{P}}$, $\delta^{\bar{MEF}}$, $\delta^{\bar{XEF}}$).

From Fig. 3.10, one can see that while all other error types are below 2.5%, $\delta^{MO,\epsilon}$ and δ^{MEF} are above. However, due to the high number of lignite and coal power plants with similar marginal costs, Germany has by far the most fuel type changes along the merit order, see Fig. 3.11. And since $\delta^{MO,\epsilon}$ and δ^{MEF} correlate with the number of fuel type changes, they are expected to be smaller for all other countries.²

²The Pearson correlation coefficients for $\delta^{MO,\epsilon}$ and δ^{MEF} are 0.99 and 0.77, respectively.

	AT	BE	CZ	DE	DK	ES	FI	FR	GB	GR	HU	IE	IT	LT	NL	PL	PT	RO	RS	SI
2015	4	5	6	28	4	10	4	5	5	4	5	4	4	2	4	20	3	9	1	3
2016	4	5	8	24	4	8	4	5	5	3	5	4	4	2	4	16	3	7	1	3
2017	4	9	4	28	4	25	4	11	35	3	5	6	29	2	10	4	9	14	2	4
2018	8	7	6	68	4	33	6	13	31	3	5	6	23	1	11	26	8	12	2	4
2019	8	7	12	84	12	19	6	13	23	3	5	8	12	1	12	42	7	11	2	4

FIGURE 3.11: Number of fuel type changes along PWL-based merit orders for the years 2015–2019.

3.3 Results - Analyses and discussions for European countries

The following analysis, applies the previously developed methods (PP and PWL) presented in Section 3.2.2 to data described in Section 3.2.1, see also Fig. 3.4. More specifically, it applies the PP method to the German power plant list described in Section 3.2.1 and the PWL method to data from 20 European countries described in Section 3.2.1. The remaining European countries were removed from the analysis due to poor data quality or insufficient electricity demand (small countries). The rejection criteria are detailed in Appendix B.6.

3.3.1 Merit orders and CEFs for European countries

FIGURE 3.12: Distribution of residual loads for countries under study in descending order of median. Plots were splitted to enhance readability.

Fig. 3.12 shows the distribution of the residual load (the load that has to be provided by conventional power plants) from the analyzed countries described in Section 3.2.2.3. The median value for France (FR), 47.31 GW, is 739 times greater than that of Lithuania (LT), 0.06 GW. The respective maximum values are 69.67 GW and 0.80 GW. Detailed depictions of the resulting merit orders for the years 2017–2019 for the 20 analyzed countries are contained in Appendix B.8.

In Fig. 3.13, the distributions of XEFs, MEFs, and marginal prices resulting from the simulations are depicted. One can see that the MEFs tend to be higher than the XEFs. Only in the Netherlands (NL) is the median of XEFs higher than the median of MEFs. The

FIGURE 3.13: Distribution of resulting CEFs and marginal prices for 2019. Note that 1.2% of AT's values (104–190 €/MWh_{el}) were trimmed.

reasons are a RES share of only 7%, a coal baseload mostly, and efficient gas_{cc} marginal power plants. However, the average values of MEFs are higher than those of XEFs for all countries. This means that the marginal power plant, on average, emits more emissions per unit of electricity than the national generation mix. From Fig. 3.13, the 20 countries can be divided into three groups. The first group contains Poland (PL) and France (FR), where fluctuations of the CEFs are low compared to the other countries and the medians are almost identical. The reason for this could be that the main marginal power plant's fuel type is also the main energy source, e.g., coal for PL, nuclear for FR. The second group includes Austria (AT) and Czech Republic (CZ), where the value sets of XEFs and MEFs are disjointed due to dominant low carbon energy sources, such as hydro in Austria with 26% of generation, or nuclear and solar in Czechia (CZ) with 10.4% and 9.8% generation, respectively. All other countries are in the third group, where the value sets of XEFs and MEFs intersect, but the medians differ substantially. An explanation could be that the marginal power plant's fuel type is only one of many energy sources, including RES.

3.3.2 Correlation analysis of emissions and prices

For the correlation analysis of the CEFs, the author follows [123] in using the Spearman rank correlation coefficient r as the relationship between CEFs and marginal costs is not expected to be linear [123]. This coefficient r quantifies how well the relationship between two variables can be described using a monotonic function. In Appendix B.9, the correlation between electricity prices (simulated and historic) and the calculated CEFs (XEFs^{PP}, XEFs^{PWLv}, MEFs^{PP}, MEFs^{PWLv}) for Germany for the years 2017–2019 are presented in scatter plots. It can be seen that the XEFs correlate positively with the simulated and the historic prices for all three years 2017–2019 and for the methods PP and PWLv (r -values range between 0.62 and 0.88). In contrast, the MEFs have negative r -values (between -0.16 and -0.42) for all mentioned combinations, which is a first indicator of the phenomenon where PBDR leads to a CE increase. Fig. 3.14 shows r -values for all analyzed countries using the PWL method. The correlation values are positive for 16 and negative for 4 of the 20 countries.

	AT	BE	CZ	DE	DK	ES	FI	FR	GB	GR	HU	IE	IT	LT	NL	PL	PT	RO	RS	SI
XEFs	0.92	0.98	0.98	0.88	0.67	0.78	0.98	1.00	0.96	0.40	0.88	0.77	0.30	0.74	-0.00	0.41	0.61	0.84	0.35	0.89
MEFs	0.31	0.97	0.93	-0.18	0.99	-0.05	0.24	1.00	0.47	-0.14	-0.37	0.57	0.93	1.00	0.70	0.57	0.20	-0.01	1.00	0.86

FIGURE 3.14: Spearman correlation coefficients r between CEFs (MEFs, XEFs) and marginal prices with the PWL method for the year 2019.

3.3.3 Price-based load shift analysis

For environmental evaluation of PBDR, only the source and sink hours are relevant, i.e., the hours where energy is shifted from and to. The analysis of the CEs without the consideration of the electricity price, which is the driving signal for PBDR, might be misleading. Thus, the author quantifies and compares the incentives and effects of PBDR for the years 2017–2019 and the 20 analyzed countries with a simulated load shift: Every day, an hourly load of 1 kWh is shifted from the most expensive to the cheapest hour of that day. Annual simulations were conducted for the years 2017–2019 for the 20 analyzed countries. The electricity prices relate to the marginal costs of the previous simulation.

Since MEFs quantify the marginal system effects, the marginal emission changes are the total emission changes, i.e., if marginal emissions increase by 1 t, total emissions increase by 1 t, too. In the remainder of the thesis, the total emission changes is referred to as marginal CE changes only to distinguish them from grid-mix CE changes, which are the change in CEs calculated from the XEF.

	AT	BE	CZ	DE	DK	ES	FI	FR	GB	GR	HU	IE	IT	LT	NL	PL	PT	RO	RS	SI
ΔC	-24	-6	-6	-12	-6	-4	-10	-21	-16	-24	-13	-4	-4	-3	-5	-5	-14	-11	-3	-19
ΔXE	-53	-45	-21	-37	-38	-10	-10	-92	-57	-3	-13	-30	-3	-53	-1	-7	-20	-20	3	-27
ΔME	11	-7	-5	10	-5	25	-4	-64	-3	53	31	3	-4	-3	-5	-1	22	4	-3	-13

FIGURE 3.15: Relative annual changes in cost and carbon emissions (CEs) resulting from load shift simulation for the year 2019 (%). The grid mix emissions are based on XEF_t^{PWL} , the marginal CEs are based on MEF_t^{PWL} .

In Fig. 3.15, the relative changes of cost and CEs of the shifted energy due to load shifts are shown. Since PBDR is considered, the cost reductions are the incentives and the changes in CEs are the effects. It can be seen that, in contrast to the costs, which decreased for all countries as expected, the CEs increased for some countries. Marginal emissions increased for the eight countries Austria (AT), Germany (DE), Spain (ES), Greece (GR), Hungary (HU), Ireland (IE), Portugal (PT), and Romania (RO).

Grid-mix emissions are usually reduced since PBDR leads to load shifts from high-XEF-hours to low-XEF-hours. The only exception of the 20 countries is Serbia (RS), where the load shifts increased the total grid-mix emissions by 3%. The reason might stem from the fact that Serbia’s power supply system is dominated by hydro (run-of-river and pondage)

and lignite. In the simulation, the marginal power plant for Serbia is always a lignite power plant (see also Fig. 3.18 and the merit order in Appendix B.8). With the aid of the pondage, hydro power plants have storage capacities enabling them to shift electricity generation from low-load-hours (0:00–6:00) to peak load hours (8:00, 19:00), see Fig. 3.16. While this also happens in other countries, in Serbia the pondage effect has more weight as there are no significant shares of vRES such as wind or solar. A similar case, where PBDR led to an increase in grid-mix emissions is reported by [162] for Norway in the year 2015.

FIGURE 3.16: Historic data for the year 2019 for Serbia: Hydro run-of-river and pondage (left) and total load (right). Data source: [242].

FIGURE 3.17: Distribution of source time and sink time of simulated load shifts for 2019.

Fig. 3.17 shows the source and sink time of the load shifts. These are the times with the highest and lowest prices of the day. For most countries, the distribution of source time has two humps: One for 5:00–10:00 and another for 16:00–20:00. This result was expected by the authors since it reflects the double-hump pattern of historic price curves. The load shift sink is mainly at night (21:00–07:00). Only in Germany and Italy does the sink occasionally occur around midday (11:00–15:00). In France, source and sink hours are both just after midnight. This is because France’s sole conventional energy source is usually nuclear which is evaluated with a constant efficiency by the data source [247]. Therefore, the daily price spreads were zero on most days, and load shifts were only carried out in cold winter months where coal and gas_cc power plants additionally stepped in to cover the increased load.

Fig. 3.18 gives insights on the marginal fuel type combination of the conducted load shifts. For the small country of Lithuania (LT), it can be seen that the national energy supply with gas as the only energy source and a low ratio between load and average power plant size provides only little incentive for load shifting.

	AT	BE	CZ	DE	DK	ES	FI	FR	GB	GR	HU	IE	IT	LT	NL	PL	PT	RO	RS	SI
oil⇒gas_cc	28	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
oil⇒coal	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
nuclear⇒nuclear	-	1	-	-	-	-	8	320	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
lignite⇒nuclear	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	-	31
lignite⇒lignite	-	-	354	86	-	-	-	-	119	75	-	-	-	-	-	7	-	171	365	300
lignite⇒coal	-	-	-	14	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	35	-	21	-	-
gas⇒lignite	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	34
gas⇒gas_cc	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	33	-	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	18	-	-
gas⇒gas	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	365	-	-	-	-	-	-
gas⇒coal	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-
gas_cc⇒nuclear	-	6	-	-	-	1	-	9	9	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-
gas_cc⇒lignite	-	-	-	22	-	-	-	-	-	241	129	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	20	-
gas_cc⇒gas_cc	179	330	-	1	-	139	43	-	108	5	149	266	345	-	259	-	167	1	-	-
gas_cc⇒coal	130	12	-	22	3	144	51	11	114	-	-	63	10	-	45	-	150	9	-	-
coal⇒nuclear	-	-	-	-	-	-	32	22	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
coal⇒lignite	-	-	11	148	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	77	-	112	-	-
coal⇒gas_cc	9	15	-	-	-	25	6	-	44	-	-	36	9	-	47	-	8	1	-	-
coal⇒coal	16	-	-	72	362	56	225	3	39	-	-	-	-	1	-	12	246	19	25	-

FIGURE 3.18: Frequency of load shift events per country and marginal fuel type combination (denoted in the form $f^{\text{source}} \Rightarrow f^{\text{sink}}$) for the year 2019.

3.3.4 CEF-based load shift analysis

For PBDR, the time-dependent electricity price is the incentive signal that determines the source and sink hours. However, conducting DR based on XEFs or MEFs could be an option for consumers who want to minimize their CEs. In this analysis, the previous load shift simulation was rerun with XEFs or MEFs as incentive signals, so 1 kWh is shifted every day from the hour with the highest XEF or MEF of that day to the lowest, respectively. In Fig. 3.19, the relative changes of cost and CEs of the shifted energy due to load shifts are shown; note that the results from Section 3.3.3 are repeated for better comparison. The resulting effects of the XEF-based load shifts are similar to that of the cost-based load shifts: Both lead to increased marginal emissions in 8 countries. In contrast, the MEF-based load shifts lead to marginal emission savings between 3 and 84% with an average of 35%, albeit reducing the average cost-saving potential by 56% compared to cost-based load shift.

	AT	BE	CZ	DE	DK	ES	FI	FR	GB	GR	HU	IE	IT	LT	NL	PL	PT	RO	RS	SI
• ΔC	-24	-6	-6	-12	-6	-4	-10	-21	-16	-24	-13	-4	-4	-3	-5	-5	-14	-11	-3	-19
ΔXE	-53	-45	-21	-37	-38	-10	-10	-92	-57	-3	-13	-30	-3	-53	-1	-7	-20	-20	3	-27
ΔME	11	-7	-5	10	-5	25	-4	-64	-3	53	31	3	-4	-3	-5	-1	22	4	-3	-13
ΔC	-20	-6	-6	-10	-5	-3	-8	-21	-15	-3	-11	-2	0	-3	-0	-4	-5	-5	0	-15
• ΔXE	-57	-48	-24	-44	-59	-23	-20	-93	-59	-35	-17	-42	-26	-70	-10	-11	-38	-25	-22	-38
ΔME	14	-7	-5	6	-4	20	-8	-64	-4	-8	30	-4	3	-3	-1	1	16	3	0	-12
ΔC	-12	-5	-5	-3	-5	-2	-8	-19	-12	10	-2	-2	-3	-3	-3	-3	-5	-0	-3	-8
ΔXE	-30	-37	-19	-15	-37	-3	-8	-63	-48	-6	-6	-18	-1	-53	-1	-4	-8	-4	3	-24
• ΔME	-51	-30	-9	-38	-7	-50	-27	-84	-53	-47	-36	-47	-43	-3	-47	-32	-54	-28	-3	-21

FIGURE 3.19: Relative annual changes of Cost (C), Grid Mix Emissions (XE), and Marginal Emissions (ME) resulting from load shift simulations for 2019 in % with “•” indicating the optimized criteria. The grid-mix emissions are based on XEF_t^{PWL} , the marginal emissions are based on MEF_t^{PWL} .

3.3.5 Detailed discussion of six sample countries

In the following, the reasons and conditions under which PBDR lead to increased CEs will be discussed using detailed results of the load shift analyses of six exemplary countries for the year 2019, shown in Fig. 3.20. For corresponding analyses of the remaining 14 countries, see Appendix B.11. The six countries were selected because first, they are representative in terms of country size and the range of relative annual changes from Fig. 3.15, including its maximum (GR) and minimum (FR) of marginal emission changes, and second, they have different interesting attributes, e.g., the dominance of nuclear (FR), high wind share (DK), the dominance of lignite/coal (PL), or being a small country very reliant on wind and gas_cc (IE). For each country, Fig. 3.20 shows a) the merit order, b) the histogram of P_t^{resi} as the range of possible load shifts, c) the load shifts with its sources and sinks, and d) their inverted load duration curves. For according plots for all 20 countries for the years 2017–2019, see Appendix B.10. In Fig. 3.20, the three countries in the first row (DE, GR, IE) have increased marginal emissions in Fig. 3.15, the countries in the second row (DK, FR, PL) do not. (To guide the reader’s eye, the six sample countries have been marked with bold letters for several previous diagrams.)

Germany (DE). Even though Germany has a comparatively diversified energy supply, the main marginal fuel types are lignite, coal, and gas_cc, which are also the main causes of the merit order dilemma of emissions. The results show 159 load shifts in which the marginal fuel type does not change. In these cases, the load is generated by a generation unit with the same fuel type but with a higher efficiency, which leads to reductions in cost and marginal emissions. With 192 cases, more than half of the German load shifts display a reduction in marginal emissions (148 coal-to-lignite, 22 gas_cc-to-coal, and 22

FIGURE 3.20: Load shift analyses of 6 European countries for the year 2019 based on the PWL method: **a)** Merit order with marginal costs c_p^m (left) and emission intensities ε_p (right), **b)** histogram of residual load P_t^{resi} , **c)** load shifts of all days of the year (squares indicating sources and triangles indicating sinks), and **d)** inverted load duration curves of sources (right) and sinks (left)). The x-axis (net generation power in GW_{el}) is shared across the four subplots.

gas_cc-to-lignite). Only 14 energy units were shifted towards a situation with a greener marginal fuel type (lignite-to-coal).

Greece (GR). In Greece, the increase of marginal emissions due to load shifting is particularly strong with 53%. The reason is that the residual load oscillates most days around the capacity limit between lignite and gas_cc at around 4 GW leading to 241 gas_cc-to-lignite load shifts, which are the most disadvantageous occurring load shifts regarding the unwanted effect of increasing marginal emissions. Due to Greece's still moderately developed expansion of renewable energies with 30% RES share, the potential for reducing grid-mix emissions is only 3%.

Ireland (IE). With a wind share of 40%, Ireland's RES share of 43% is similar to that of Germany even though there is very little solar power. This drives the grid-mix emission saving to up to 30%. However, marginal emission changes are slightly positive with 3% due to 63 gas_cc-to-coal load shifts. Only the 36 coal-to-gas_cc-load shifts imply changing to a greener marginal fuel type while the vast majority of load shifts (266) stay within the dominant fuel type gas_cc.

Denmark (DK). In Denmark, the load shifts lead to 40% grid-mix emission reductions. This is mainly caused by the high RES share of 76% of which wind_onshore contributes almost half. The national residual load P_t^{resi} is subject to strong seasonal fluctuations. Causing factors could be power demand for heating during winter and reduced imports of German excess solar power. The marginal emissions are moderately reduced by 6%. More than 99% of the load shifts are within the fuel type of coal, thus, yield only emission reductions through higher power plant efficiencies.

France (FR). In France, 71% of electricity is produced by nuclear power plants making the country's national power supply system heavily conventional-based, yet low in CEs. The national power supply gives only little economic incentive for load shifting since the residual load is predominantly in the range of marginal nuclear power. Only in the cold winter months, when the residual load exceeds the nuclear power capacity limits, incentives for intraday load shifting are created. There are 31 load shifts into hours with nuclear as marginal fuel type: 9 shifted from gas_cc and 22 from coal. These few cases do not lead to particularly high CE savings in absolute terms. In relative terms, however, due to the low emission baseline level of France's electricity system, they contribute to the highest savings of all analyzed countries: 92% grid-mix emission and 64% marginal emission savings.

Poland (PL). Poland has a low RES share. Predominant fuel types are coal (52%) and lignite (26%). In the merit order, they are intertwined due to similar marginal cost levels – in contrast to Greece where the fuel types lignite and gas_cc form continuous blocks in the merit order. This leads to all combinations of load shifts between the two fuel types: 35 lignite-to-coal-shifts, 77 coal-to-lignite-shifts, 7 lignite-to-lignite-shifts, and 246 coal-to-coal-shifts. Together these result in 7% marginal emission savings mainly stemming from power plant efficiency gains of the coal-to-coal load shifts.

3.3.6 Impact of carbon price

A promising measure to solve the merit order emission dilemma is to set a price for CEs in the form of a carbon price or carbon tax to an appropriate level. This increases the correlation between marginal costs and carbon intensities in the merit order.

3.3.6.1 Impact on marginal costs–emissions correlation

To demonstrate this, a sensitivity analysis was carried out in which the merit order of the German power plants for the year 2019 was determined for different hypothetical carbon prices. To quantify the effect on the merit order, the Spearman correlation coefficient r between the marginal prices c_p^m and the power plant specific carbon intensities ε_p along the merit order was calculated for each scenario. The quantitative results can be seen in Fig. 3.21. It shows negative r values for carbon prices below €42.58/t. For comparison, the average carbon prices for the years 2017–2019, $\bar{c}_{2017}^{\text{GHG}}$, $\bar{c}_{2018}^{\text{GHG}}$, and $\bar{c}_{2019}^{\text{GHG}}$, were €5.8/t, €16.0/t and €24.9/t, respectively. $r = 0$ means that CEFs and marginal costs are decoupled. $r = 0.2$ was calculated for $c^{\text{GHG}} = \text{€}65.3/\text{t}$, $r = 0.4$ for $c^{\text{GHG}} = 100.0/\text{t}$, $r = 0.6$ for $c^{\text{GHG}} = \text{€}156.1/\text{t}$, and $r = 0.8$ for $c^{\text{GHG}} = \text{€}235.6/\text{t}$. In comparison, the German Federal Environment Agency suggests the usage of climate damage costs of €₂₀₁₆180/t for the year 2016, €₂₀₁₆205/t for 2030, and €₂₀₁₆240/t for 2050 [258]. For $r \gtrsim 0.8$ or $c^{\text{GHG}} \gtrsim \text{€}235.6/\text{t}$, the marginal gains of r decrease. In order to reach $r = 0.99$, a carbon price of €1269.5/t is needed.

3.3.6.2 Impact on the merit order

Fig. 3.22 shows the corresponding effects on the merit order. One can see that with increasing carbon prices, the low-emission gas_cc power plants gain a comparative economic advantage over lignite and coal and shift to the left side of the merit order. With $c^{\text{GHG}} = \text{€}100/\text{t}$, almost all gas_cc power plants are directly behind nuclear. The same happens to the gas power plants, coal power plants, and for c^{GHG} somewhere above €236/t even to oil power plants. These values mostly align with the simulation results in [259]. For $c^{\text{GHG}} = \text{€}10,000/\text{t}$,

FIGURE 3.21: Sensitivity analysis of the carbon price c^{GHG} and the Spearman correlation coefficient r between marginal costs c_p^m and marginal emissions e_p^m with German power plant data in 2019. Indicated in blue color, the average carbon prices \bar{c}_*^{GHG} for the years 2017–2019 and additional interesting carbon prices and r-values are added.

where r reaches the value 1.00, the CE intensity ε_p (black line) is, except for a few small power plants, monotonically increasing and fully correlated with the marginal price c_p^m (blue line).

3.3.6.3 Impact on load shifting

In a final analysis, the load shift effects on marginal emissions, grid-mix emissions, and costs are calculated for different carbon prices for the case of Germany in 2019. The results are depicted in Fig. 3.23.

In general, an increasing carbon price leads to decreasing marginal emissions and grid-mix emissions. However, in the special cases of carbon price raise from €24.9/t to €42.6/t and from €156.1/t to €235.6/t, an increase of marginal emissions and grid-mix emissions can be observed. This is because with $c^{\text{GHG}} = \text{€}42.6/\text{t}$, gas_cc power plants move into the 35 GW area, around where the residual load fluctuates (see Fig. 3.20b for Germany) increasing the number of gas_cc-to-lignite and gas_cc-to-coal load shifts, see Fig. S21 in Appendix B.10. At $c^{\text{GHG}} = \text{€}65.3/\text{t}$, gas_cc power plants already arrived on the lower half of the residual load range and therefore act more frequently as load shift sink. $c^{\text{GHG}} = \text{€}65.3/\text{t}$ is already sufficient to achieve 58% of the possible achievable marginal emission savings, and $c^{\text{GHG}} = \text{€}100.0/\text{t}$ yields 93% of the possible achievable marginal emission reduction of 21.4%.

The effects on grid-mix emissions are similar to the effects on marginal emissions. Increasing emissions for increasing carbon prices can be observed for the same price steps and traced back to the same reasons, but with lower amplitude, due to the damping influence of averaging.

The effect curve on costs in Fig. 3.23 is concave. For $c^{\text{GHG}} \leq \text{€}65.3/\text{t}$, the cost savings decrease with increasing carbon prices. The reducing daily price spreads are caused by the convergence of marginal costs of power plants in the relevant residual load range (around 35 GW) as the high carbon intensities of formerly cheap coal and lignite power plants are effectively penalized by the increasing carbon price. For $c^{\text{GHG}} > \text{€}65.3/\text{t}$, the carbon-related marginal costs (see Eq. (3.7)) increasingly outweighs the fuel costs and ultimately makes the fuel costs insignificant. Through the formation of coherent technology blocks – now in the new ascending order of carbon intensity – steps in the marginal costs curve are shaped (e.g., at 23 GW) which in turn lead to higher price spreads.

FIGURE 3.22: Effects of carbon price (c^{GHG}) on the German merit order in 2019 and the spearman correlation coefficient (r) between marginal costs (c_p^m) and marginal emissions (ϵ_p^m).

FIGURE 3.23: Relative annual changes of Cost (C), Grid Mix Emissions (XE), and Marginal Emissions (ME) resulting from load shift simulation for 2019 in % for different carbon prices. The grid mix emissions are based on XEF_t^{PP} , the marginal CE are based on MEF_t^{PP} .

3.3.7 Discussion summary

While MEFs are essential for quantifying the carbon differential of load shifts, XEFs are more suitable for calculating the CEs of a static electricity load profile. Also, XEFs can be determined with less uncertainty and in a straightforward approach, which is reflected in their high availability.

European national electricity supply systems differ widely in both size (0.13–49 GW residual load) and composition (7–77% RES share), which is reflected in the varying prices and CEFs that resulted from the simulation, Fig. 3.13. The differences between the European countries became even clearer when running yearly simulations of daily load shifts on the basis of the calculated prices and CEFs. The electricity cost-saving potentials ranged between 3% for Lithuania (LT) and Serbia (RS) and 24% for Austria (AT) and Greece (GR). The resulting changes in marginal emissions varied between 64% decrease for France (FR) and 53% increase for Greece (GR), with increases in eight countries (AT, DE, ES, GR, HU, IE, PT, RO). The changes of grid-mix emissions varied between -92% for France (FR) and +3% for Serbia (RS), with Serbia being the only country where grid-mix emissions increase. Averaged over all countries, the costs decreased by 10.4%, the grid-mix emissions decreased by 26.9%, but the marginal emissions increased by 2.1%. While XEF-based load shifts, like the price-based load shifts, led to marginal emission increases in eight countries, MEF-based load shifts resulted in average emission savings of 35%, albeit with 56% lower cost savings. A final sensitivity analysis regarding the carbon price brought the following salient findings: (1) For Germany, a carbon price of €42.6/t was necessary to decouple emissions from prices, i.e., where r , the Spearman correlation coefficient of emissions and prices along the merit order, is zero. (2) A carbon price increase from 0 to €156.1/t led to a switch between gas_{cc} and lignite/coal in the German merit order and flipped effects of

the according price-based load shifts on CEs from a 10% increase to a 21% decrease. (3) Increases of the carbon price beyond €156.1/t led to insignificant changes.

3.4 Conclusions

The aim of this chapter was the quantification and discussion of the effects of PBDR on operational CEs for European countries. Straightforward approaches based on the calculation of XEFs are not suitable for this purpose due to the characteristics of electricity markets. More adequate methods based on the knowledge of marginal power plants require detailed data, thus MEF values are not readily available for European countries. This chapter, therefore proposed a method (PWL) to approximate MEFs with readily available datasets and validated it with another method (PP) using power plant specific efficiency data from Germany. Then, the PWL method is applied to 20 European countries for the years 2017–2019 to calculate prices, MEFs, and, for comparison purposes, XEFs. The resulting prices and CEFs served as basis for subsequently conducted load shift simulations, to evaluate its effects on CEs. Starting from the so-called merit order dilemma of emissions, the results were discussed for six representative countries. In a final analysis, the impact of carbon pricing was analyzed by calculating the Spearman correlation coefficient between prices and emissions along the merit order for different carbon prices.

The key findings of the chapter are:

1. The great diversity of European countries in terms of the composition and the size of their national electricity supply systems is reflected in the XEFs and MEFs.
2. Price-based load shifts indicated that CEs increased for 8 of the 20 countries and by 2.1% on average.
3. MEF-based load shifts led to average CE savings of 35%, however decreasing the cost-saving potential by 56% compared to price-based load shifts.
4. Emissions and prices along the German merit order for the year 2019 decoupled with a carbon price of €42.6/t.
5. An carbon price increase from 0 to €156.1/t led to a switch between gas_cc and lignite/coal in the German merit order of 2019 and improved the CE effect of the according price-based load shifts for European countries from a 10% increase to a 21% decrease.

Despite the limitations outlined in Chapter 12, the following main conclusions can be drawn:

1. Currently, DR could increase operational CEs if spot-market prices are used as an incentive signal (under the current carbon price).

2. This phenomenon does not occur
 - (a) if dynamic MEFs are used as DR incentive signal or
 - (b) if an adequate carbon price is set.

While PBDR leads to negative environmental effects under specific circumstances, it is a very promising method of reducing operating cost and CEs when adequate carbon prices are implemented. To exploit the full positive environmental potential of PBDR, high correlations between carbon intensity and marginal cost in the merit order need to be ensured either by adequate carbon prices or other market interventions.

Appendix: Detailed analysis and data descriptions. Appendix [B](#) offers additional insights into the data sources, preprocessing methods, price-CEF correlations, and includes plots and descriptions for the remaining 14 analyzed European countries.

3.5 The Elmada tool

The CEF calculation methods described in this chapter have been incorporated into Elmada, an open-source Python software developed by Markus Fleschutz and listed on the Open Sustainable Technology directory [260]. Elmada offers historical dynamic MEFs, XEFs, and wholesale prices for 30 European countries. As a by-product of the CEF calculations, Elmada provides additional information, including merit order lists, plots, fuel-specific generation data, and power plant lists. The primary target group consists of modelers of L-MESs who require electricity market data.

Fig. 3.24 displays the logo of Elmada.

FIGURE 3.24: Logo of the Elmada tool.

The source code and documentation of Elmada are published on GitHub under an open-source license and can be accessed at <https://github.com/DrafProject/elmada>.

Additionally, Elmada was published in the Journal for Open Source Software (JOSS) following a thorough peer-review of the version 1.0 of the software package including source code, tests, and documentation [261]. The JOSS paper is included in this thesis in Appendix C.

In July 2021, Elmada was registered on the Python Package Index (PyPI). As of December 2023, the package had been downloaded over 7,000 times via the Python package installer `pip` [262].

Chapter 4

Demand Response Analysis

Framework (DRAF): An open-source multi-objective decision support tool for decarbonizing local multi-energy systems

Abstract. A major barrier to investments in clean and future-proof energy technologies of local multi-energy systems (L-MESs) is the lack of knowledge about their impact on the company's profitability and carbon footprint due to their complex techno-economic interactions. To reduce this barrier, decision support tools should integrate different fields of decarbonization measures. This chapter proposes the Demand Response Analysis Framework (DRAF), a new open-source Python decision support tool that integrally optimizes the design and operation of energy technologies considering demand-side flexibility, electrification, and renewable energy sources. It quantifies decarbonization and cost reduction potential using multi-objective mixed-integer linear programming and provides decision-makers of L-MESs with optimal scenarios regarding costs, carbon emissions, or Pareto efficiency. DRAF supports all steps of the energy system optimization process from time series analysis to interactive plotting and data export. It comes with several component templates that allow a quick start without limiting the modeling possibilities thanks to a generic model generator. Other key features are the access and preparation of time series such as dynamic carbon emission factors or wholesale electricity prices, and the generation, handling, and parallel computing of scenarios. DRAF's capabilities are demonstrated through three case studies on (1) DR of industrial production processes, (2) design optimization of battery and

photovoltaic systems, and (3) design optimization and DR of distributed thermal energy resources.

Acknowledgments. The contents of this chapter are based on the paper *Demand Response Analysis Framework (DRAF): An Open-Source Multi-Objective Decision Support Tool for Decarbonizing Local Multi-Energy Systems* [209]. Markus Fleschutz is the primary author of this paper. This research was performed as part of the MeSSO Research Group at the Munster Technological University (MTU) and in relation to the project WIN4climate as part of the National Climate Initiative financed by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK) on the basis of a decision by the German Bundestag (No. 03KF0094A). It was additionally funded by the MTU Risam Scholarship Scheme.

4.1 Overview and context

Energy system modeling is essential to drive the rapid adoption of smart energy services and clean innovative technologies needed to decarbonize energy systems [263]. As demonstrated in Section 2.4, powerful energy system modeling frameworks have been presented as proprietary and open-source software. Most open-source frameworks, though, were developed with large-scale energy systems in mind and only a few focus on decision support for L-MESs. However, significant adoption of clean technologies and DR programs are required in individual L-MESs, as the success of the energy transition depends on decentralization. According to the International Energy Agency, 70% of clean energy investments over the next decade will have to be made by private developers, consumers, and financiers [147]. Industrial and commercial electricity consumers can contribute to the expansion of RES, e.g., through on-site PV systems. At the same time, they can help to integrate the RES through the smart use of flexible loads and energy storages through DR which additionally offers cost-saving potential for companies. This demand-side flexibility is needed as the flexibility demand of the electricity system is expected to quadruple by 2050 even though the availability of conventional flexibility sources will decrease due to the decommissioning of fossil power plants [38]. Therefore, in this chapter, the author focuses on how cost and CE reductions that arise from applying DR to L-MESs, especially in the industrial and commercial sectors can be quantified using the Demand Response Analysis Framework (DRAF).

As part of the conclusions of the literature review in Section 2.4, the author chooses MILP, since the formulated optimization problems can be solved to global optimality within reasonable, computational time. The author assumes that an explicit equation-based model

exists and that all occurring non-linear phenomena can be approximately modeled as piecewise linear.

Commercial and industrial enterprises have large DR potentials [264] which can be divided in cross-sectional technologies [265] and energy-intensive production processes [23]. However, in order to exploit the full environmental and economic DR potential in the industrial and commercial sector, aspects such as dynamic pricing, sector coupling, onsite generation, and onsite energy storage need to be considered in an integral analysis [6, 266]. Due to this complexity, there is still a lack of knowledge about existing flexibility which is a major barrier to participation in DR programs [148]. To address this complexity, mathematical optimization which has already been long proven in the analysis of large international power systems can be applied to L-MES. However, data preparation, model formulation, scenario definition, and result presentation require relevant experience and expertise to which the decision-makers in the companies often do not have access.

Contribution. The aim of this chapter is to develop and demonstrate DRAF, an open-source Python decision support framework that automates process steps to make mathematical optimization methodology more accessible to a broader user group, including academics in applied sciences, consulting engineers, and decision-makers in companies. DRAF provides insights and decision support for optimizing DR-related design and operation of L-MESs, using multi-objective MILP optimization to quantify the cost and CE reduction potential of existing and future flexibility options. Targeted at researchers in the energy field and decision-makers in the commercial and industrial sector, DRAF is designed to be portable, maintainable, editable, and extensible. The source code can be found at <https://github.com/DrafProject/draf> [267].

Chapter structure. The remainder of this chapter is organized as follows. First, the most important elements and components of DRAF are described in Section 4.2 referencing to the extensive appendix with screenshots (Appendix D.1) and component templates (Appendix D.2). Second, the application of DRAF to three different simplified real-world case studies is demonstrated in Section 4.3. This is followed by a discussion and conclusion in Section 4.4.

4.2 Materials and methods – The Demand Response Analysis Framework (DRAF)

4.2.1 Overview

Fig. 4.1 shows the main functional elements of DRAF. One can see that DRAF provides a toolbox for every step of a typical energy system analysis and optimization process of an L-MES decision maker. More specifically, DRAF is designed to answer the three questions illustrated in Fig. 4.2.

FIGURE 4.1: Schematic representation of DRAF’s toolboxes, including examples, and their relationship to the energy system analysis and optimization process, as well as their integration with external resources and data. For example, parameterization is supported by DRAF through the parameter preparation tool `TimeSeriesPrepper`, which, e.g., provides electricity prices using the tool `Elmada` as an external resource.

FIGURE 4.2: Key questions addressed by DRAF.

The general architecture of DRAF is presented in Fig. 4.3. A typical use case is described in the following. First, a user imports and analyzes time series data of, e.g., electricity and natural gas historically purchased by the analyzed L-MES operator using the `DemandAnalyzer`. Informed by the findings of the analyses, the user then instantiates a `CaseStudy` object of the desired analysis year and the country/address/coordinates of the L-MES. Subsequently, a first reference scenario including a model is added to the case study using component templates and the model generator. While `DataBase` is used here to provide and describe default parameters, the `TimeSeriesPrepper` prepares relevant time series such as the

day-ahead market prices, dynamic CEFs, or PV profiles. Different scenarios are then added by duplicating the reference scenario and changing specific parameters. After the model is solved by an external MILP solver, the results are stored in the Scenario object. Finally, all parameters and results can be visualized either for each scenario (ScenarioPlotter) or for all scenarios in the case study (CaseStudyPlotter). The interconnected classes and modules allow for a fluent, explorative analysis process using the dot operator, e.g., while `cs.scens` returns an overview of all defined scenarios, `cs.scens.sc2.res.P_PV_fi_T.plot()` plots the feed-in PV power of the scenario `sc2`. DRAF handles metadata, i.e., parameters can be stored together with a description, the unit, and the source. This motivates the input of metadata which can be used in plotting and exporting, prevents misunderstandings, and helps to document the meaning of an optimization model.

FIGURE 4.3: Software architecture of DRAF. The user interacts with DRAF via Jupyter notebooks. To carry out an analysis, the user initiates a CaseStudy and defines scenarios using the scenario generator, component templates, and the parameter preparation tools (DataBase and TimeSeriesPrepper). The model generator builds optimization models from the model definition consisting of data and logic. After the optimization, the results can be plotted either. After optimization, the results can be plotted via CaseStudyPlotter or ScenarioPlotter using convenient dot notation (e.g., `cs.plot.tables()`, see Fig. D.3).

There are other energy modeling frameworks that also consider flexible demand. However, they do not focus on the modeling of L-MESs such as individual commercial or industrial distributed energy resources. Since they are very generic, they technically allow the modeling of individual industrial sites, however, this abstraction comes with the cost of higher computational complexity and increased familiarization time with the tool for the user. Also, they do not provide easy access to necessary market information such as wholesale prices, dynamic emission factors, technology investment costs, etc. Versatility and portability are important aspects of DRAF. Both are ensured through a modular structure of DRAF that can be used as a generalized framework which can easily be adapted to specific applications.

4.2.2 Python as high level programming language

For the development of DRAF, the open-source general-purpose programming language Python [268] 3.9 was chosen. A general-purpose programming language allows all steps of the analysis process from market data acquisition to data preparation, model building, scenario definition, and result visualization to be defined and reproducibly documented in a single environment. Since 2010, Python has become a standard for new energy system models [196]. At the time of writing, Python is the most popular easy-to-use high-level programming language [269]. It has rich libraries for data handling and visualization (e.g., Pandas [270], Matplotlib [271], or Plotly [272]). The open-source optimization modeling language Pyomo [273] provides access to important MILP solvers such as Gurobi [274]. But most importantly, Python has a vibrant community that supplies help and solutions to almost any problem that might occur in the future.

4.2.3 Time series analysis tools

As can be seen from Fig. 4.1, the Time Series Analysis Tools refer to a DRAF toolbox. The included tools `DemandAnalyzer` and `PeakLoadAnalyzer` are described in the following.

DemandAnalyzer. Often DR analyses are based on a time series of historic energy demands, e.g., the electricity demand of the year before. Before starting the modeling process, an analysis of this time series is helpful to validate the correct time-series length and to get key metrics like the peak-to-average ratio, load percentiles, or usage patterns. DRAF provides such an analysis with the `DemandAnalyzer`. Fig. D.1 shows a screenshot of an example time series analysis.

PeakLoadAnalyzer. Based on the `DemandAnalyzer` object, the `PeakLoadAnalyzer` can be used, see screenshot in Fig. D.2. It shows the peak loads above a user-defined threshold and the cost reduction potential that originates from a given peak load price.

4.2.4 Parameter preparation tools

The Parameter Preparation Tools is a toolbox (see Fig. 4.1) that supports the preparation of parameters for the optimization model.

4.2.4.1 TimeSeriesPrepper

DRAF's `TimeSeriesPrepper` allows the user to prepare time series such as the ambient air temperature, renewable electricity generation profiles, CEFs, and day-ahead market prices from basic input data such as an address that converts to geographic coordinates, the analyzed year, and the time step width.

CEFs and electricity prices. In DRAF, CEFs and day-ahead prices for most European national electricity systems are automatically calculated for the given year and frequency with the open-source tool `Elmada` [261] described in Chapter 3. The latest `Elmada` version, v0.1.0 [275], supplies hourly and quarter-hourly time series for 30 European countries mainly using data from the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E) transparency platform [242]. For the CEFs, the user can choose between XEFs and MEFs depending on the analysis question. For the electricity prices, the user can choose between day-ahead spot market prices which are referred to as RTP, TOU pricing, and a flat price. In TOU, if not stated otherwise, time steps are grouped into high price and low price times, where high price times apply between 8:00 to 20:00 during workdays. The high/low price is defined by the mean of RTP during high/low price times, respectively. The flat price is the annual mean of the RTPs.

PV power profiles. If the user does not provide PV profiles for the analyzed location, DRAF uses the Global Solar Energy Estimator (GSEE) [276] to generate PV profiles from the geographic coordinates (or a valid address), global and diffuse radiation as well as ambient temperature time series. For Germany only, DRAF checks for available weather data from the nearest weather station from [277] and downloads it in the background. This functionality may be extended to other countries as data become available.

Electrical and thermal load profiles. The `TimeSeriesPrepper` module of DRAF also provides functions to create electrical and thermal load time series. In the electrical case, standard load profiles from [278] are used while considering public holidays from the given region with the Python `holidays` package [279]. For thermal load profiles, ambient temperature data from [277] are used to approximate heating and cooling demand time series.

DataBase. The reasoning behind the `DataBase` is to pragmatically provide the user with an expandable library of technical and market-related parameters together with metadata

such as units, descriptions, and scientific sources. Some of the values are used in the component template definitions in Appendix D.2.

4.2.5 Component-based model generator

To avoid code repetition, and to make DRAF and the code written by the user maintainable, extensible, and adaptable, the toolbox Model Generator (see Fig. 4.1) is implemented that creates model constructs in a lazy fashion, see Algorithm 1. Furthermore, the model generator keeps the model as light as possible, creating only the dimensions, parameters, optimization variables, and constraints that are needed. This allows the provision of adaptable and extensible component templates without limiting the user's freedom to build any other MILP model.

A component class consists of the two functions `param_func` and `model_func` that define the component. The `param_func` defines dimensions, parameters, variables, and collectors for a given scenario. The `model_func` later uses these objects to build constraints and to connect the component to other components by contributing linear expressions to their collectors. The following listings show examples of these functions. The first listing defines a simple PV component. Note that, dimensions and collectors are not needed for this simple PV component. The second listing shows relevant parts of the `Main` component which defines general relationships that do not originate from a specific technical component.

```

class PV(Component):
    def param_func(self, sc:Scenario):
        # sc.dim(...) (Dimensions could be defined here if applicable)
        sc.param("c_PV_inv_", data=460, doc="Inv. costs", unit="EUR/kW_peak")
        sc.param("P_PV_max_", data=500, doc="Max. peak power", unit="kW_peak")
        sc.param("P_PV_profile_T", data=getProfile(), unit="kW_el",
                doc="Elec. power of 1kW_peak per time step")
        sc.var("P_PV_CAPn_", doc="New capacity", unit="kW_peak")
        sc.var("P_PV_OC_T", doc="Own consumption", unit="kW_el")
        sc.var("P_PV_FI_T", doc="Feed-in", unit="kW_el")
        # sc.collector(...) (Collectors could be defined here if applicable)

    def model_func(self, sc:Scenario, m:Model, d:Dims, p:Params, v:Vars, c:Collectors):
        m.addConstr(v.P_PV_CAPn_ <= p.P_PV_max_)
        m.addConstrs(
            (p.P_PV_profile_T[t] * v.P_PV_CAPn_ == v.P_PV_FI_T[t] + v.P_PV_OC_T[t] for t in d.T)
        )

        # The PV component submits to three different collectors:
        c.C_inv_["PV"] = v.P_PV_CAPn_ * p.c_PV_inv_
        c.P_EL_source_T["PV"] = lambda t: v.P_PV_OC_T[t]
        c.P_EG_feedin_T["PV"] = lambda t: v.P_PV_FI_T[t]

```

```

class Main(Component):
    def param_func(self, sc:Scenario):
        sc.collector("C_inv_", doc="Total investment costs", unit="EUR")
        sc.collector("P_EL_source_T", doc="Power sources", unit="kW_el")
        sc.collector("P_EL_sink_T", doc="Power sinks", unit="kW_el")
        ...

    def model_func(self, sc:Scenario, m:Model, d:Dims, p:Params, v:Vars, c:Collectors):
        # Investment cost aggregation using a collector:
        m.addConstr(v.C_inv_ == sum(c.C_inv_.values()))

        # Electricity balance using two collectors:
        m.addConstrs((sum(f(t) for f in c.P_EL_source_T.values())
                    == sum(f(t) for f in c.P_EL_sink_T.values())
                    for t in d.T))
        ...

```

For adding constraints and objective functions, the user can choose between Pyomo and GurobiPy syntax. While Pyomo supports different solvers, GurobiPy is limited to the commercial solver Gurobi but builds models with less computational effort.

Component interdependencies are considered using so-called collectors which collect linear expressions across components and aggregate them in another component. For example, the

collector for investment costs are defined in the `Main` component with `sc.collector("C_inv_")`, then the components PV and fuel cell (FC) contribute to it with `c.C_inv_["PV"] = ...` and `c.C_inv_["FC"] = ...`. Finally, the `Main` component uses the collector to aggregate the investment costs with `sum(c.C_inv_.values())`. Collectors can collect scalar values, e.g. to aggregate investment costs of different components to total costs, or collect functions to access multi-dimensional vectors, e.g., to build an electricity balance for each time step, see Fig. 4.4. If a component uses a collector, the constraints of that component must be built after the constraints of all components that contribute to that collector. This dependency restricts the order of submodel creation which is resolved by executing a topological sort. This makes components reusable, so the user can conveniently choose from different storage and conversion technology components and modeling options such as the consideration of investments or minimal part-load behavior without inflating the model with overhead constructs. The user defines optimization models by using component templates (see Appendix D.2) and/or self-written technology components.

Algorithm 1: Model generation

Input : Case study configuration Ω including year, frequency, modeling horizon, geo coordinates, if investment is considered, etc.; User-selected components C ; Scenario definitions D

Output : Case study S including scenarios and parametrized optimization models

```

1 Initialize case study  $S$  with configuration  $\Omega$ 
  // Build scenarios with defined parameters and variables:
2 for each scenario definition  $d$  in  $D$  do
3   if  $d$  is based on a base scenario then
4     | Initialize scenario  $s$  as a copy of the respective base scenario
5   else
6     | Initialize a new scenario  $s$ 
7   Define and/or update parameters and variables in  $s$  using  $C$ ,  $\Omega$ , and  $d$ 
8   Add  $s$  to case study  $S$ 
  // Build optimization model for each scenario:
9 Sort components  $C$  topologically considering component interdependencies
10 for each scenario  $s$  in case study  $S$  do
11   | Initialize optimization model  $m$  and add to scenario  $s$ 
12   | Initialize optimization variables from variable definitions of  $s$ 
13   for each component  $c$  in  $C$  do
14     | Set objective function and constraints of component  $c$  to model  $m$  using
15     | parameters, optimization variables and collectors of  $s$ 
    | Register linear expressions to collectors

```

4.2.6 Component templates

DRAF provides a set of component templates so users do not need to start from scratch. The model is assembled from the `Main` component and multiple technology components. The

FIGURE 4.4: An example where collectors (circles) induce component interdependencies. The `Main` component collects operating and investment costs and the two sides of the electricity balance for each time step. The electricity grid (EG) component collects for each time step electricity that is fed into the grid – here, the contributors are the fuel cell (FC) and the photovoltaic system (PV). This separate feed-in collector is important for the reusability of the EG component. The electricity demand (eDem) only affects the electricity balance sinks. The component interdependencies are considered within model generation through topology sort. This ensures that all submodels contributing to a collector are built before that collector is executed.

`Main` component includes the objective function and all general sets, parameters, variables, and balances. Technology components are, e.g., energy demands, conversion and storage technologies, and interfaces to external entities such as the electricity grid.

4.2.6.1 The component template `Main`

The `Main` component is a special component template that consists of the definition of the objective function and general balances and constraints. The `Main` component yields a deterministic multi-objective combined design and operation problem, which is described in the following. The formulation is partly based on previous work [280] and [281]. By default, DRAF works with equidistant time steps and assumes perfect foresight. The temporal resolution is defined by the user and not restricted, however, hourly or quarter-hourly resolution is required if the functionality of the `TimeSeriesPrepper` module is used, see Section 4.2.4.1. The default modeling horizon is one year, but can be customized. General sets are discrete time steps $t \in \mathcal{T} := \{t_1, \dots, t_{|\mathcal{T}|}\}$, components $j \in \mathcal{J} := \{\text{eDem}, \text{EG}, \text{PV}, \text{BES}, \dots\}$, and flow types $i \in \mathcal{D} := \{\text{electricity}, \text{heat 1}, \text{heat 2}, \text{cool 1}, \text{cool 2}, \text{product 1}, \dots\}$. In the following, optimization variables are denoted with **bold** symbols and are non-negative continuous variables unless stated differently.

The objective function of the MILP is to minimize the weighted sum of the TAC \mathbf{C}^{TOT} and the annual CEs \mathbf{CE}^{TOT} :

$$\text{minimize } \mathbf{Z} := (1 - \alpha)\pi^{\text{C}}\mathbf{C}^{\text{TOT}} + \alpha\pi^{\text{CE}}\mathbf{CE}^{\text{TOT}} + \sum_j \mathbf{X}_j^{\text{penalty}} \quad (4.1)$$

where α is the Pareto weighting factor $\in [0..1]$ and π^C, π^{CE} are the Pareto normalization factors which can be identified by a simple algorithm to enable a more even distribution of the Pareto points, see Fig. 4.13. $\mathbf{X}_j^{\text{penalty}}$ is a general penalty term which is only used in rare cases when there is an incentive that is not related to costs or CEs, e.g., to model uncontrolled BEV charging (in Appendix D.2.6) where the incentive is to charge based on time constraints.

The annualized total costs \mathbf{C}^{TOT} are the sum of the annual operating costs, the annualized investment costs, and the maintenance costs of all components $j \in \mathcal{J}$:

$$\mathbf{C}^{\text{tot}} = \underbrace{\sum_j \mathbf{C}_j^{\text{op}}}_{\text{operation costs}} + \underbrace{\sum_j \mathbf{C}_j^{\text{invAnn}}}_{\text{annualized investment costs}} + \underbrace{\sum_j \mathbf{C}_j^{\text{rmi}}}_{\text{maintainance costs}} \quad (4.2)$$

$$\mathbf{C}^{\text{TOT}} \in \mathbb{R}, \quad \mathbf{C}_j^{\text{op}} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{J}|}$$

The total CEs \mathbf{CE}^{TOT} are the sum of yearly operating CEs of all components $j \in \mathcal{J}$:

$$\mathbf{CE}^{\text{TOT}} = \sum_j \mathbf{CE}_j \quad (4.3)$$

$$\mathbf{CE}^{\text{TOT}} \in \mathbb{R}, \quad \mathbf{CE}_j \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{J}|}$$

Time-step average flow values such as electrical power, thermal energy flow of a specific temperature level, or a product flow are generically denoted with $\Phi_{i,j,t}$. Balances are defined by equating the sum of all input flows $\Phi_{i,j,t}^{\text{source}}$ with the sum of all output flows $\Phi_{i,j,t}^{\text{sink}}$, for all flow types $i \in \mathcal{D}$:

$$\sum_j \Phi_{i,j,t}^{\text{source}} = \sum_j \Phi_{i,j,t}^{\text{sink}} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, i \in \mathcal{D} \quad (4.4)$$

4.2.6.2 Technology component templates

Appendix D.2 contains the mathematical formulation of all component templates. Note that besides conversion and storage technologies, demands, and market interfaces of commodities such as electricity (Appendix D.2.1) or fuels (Appendix D.2.2) are also individual component templates.

Most of the collectors exist within the Main component templates, a few in others, e.g.:

$$\mathbf{P}_t^{\text{EG,sell}} = \sum_j \mathbf{P}_{t,j}^{\text{sell}} \quad (\text{see EG component Appendix D.2.1}) \quad (4.5)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_f^{\text{Fuel}} = \sum_j \mathbf{F}_{f,j} \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F} \quad (\text{see Fuel component Appendix D.2.2}) \quad (4.6)$$

The total annualized investment costs $\mathbf{C}_j^{\text{invAnn}}$ and the maintainance costs $\mathbf{C}_j^{\text{rmi}}$ are usually defined within storage and conversion components:

$$\mathbf{C}_j^{\text{invAnn}} = k_j^{\text{af}}(r, N^j) c_j^{\text{inv}} \mathbf{P}^{j,\text{capn}} \quad (4.7)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_j^{\text{rmi}} = k_j^{\text{rmi}} c_j^{\text{inv}} \mathbf{P}^{j,\text{capn}} \quad (4.8)$$

$$(4.9)$$

where j stands for the component j , c_j^{inv} are the specific investment costs, and $\mathbf{P}^{j,\text{capn}}$ the new capacities. $k_j^{\text{af}}(r, N^j)$ are the component-specific annuity factors defined in Eq. (4.10) following, e.g., [282] where r is the calculatory interest rate and N^j is the operation life in years for component j .

$$k_j^{\text{af}}(r, N^j) = \frac{r(1+r)^{N^j}}{(1+r)^{N^j} - 1} \quad (4.10)$$

For the component templates additional sets are defined: Fuel types $f \in \mathcal{F} := \{\text{biogas, naturalgas}\}$, condensing temperature levels $c \in \mathcal{C} := \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{C}|\}$, heating temperature levels $h \in \mathcal{H} := \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{H}|\}$, cooling temperature levels $n \in \mathcal{N} := \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{N}|\}$, and thermal demand temperature levels $l \in \mathcal{L} := \mathcal{H} \cup \mathcal{N}$.

4.2.7 Scenario generation and optimization

The scenario generator in DRAF provides convenient scenario generation. Scenarios can either be created manually or in batches. For manual scenario creation, an existing object is cloned with `sc = cs.add_scen(based_on=<scen_id>)` which parameters can be subsequently updated with `sc.update_params(param1=value1, param2=value2, ...)`, see also Algorithm 1. The batch scenario creation using `cs.add_scens()` can be seen as sensitivity analysis which automatically creates a scenario for each combination of given parameters and parameter values. E.g., this is useful for optimizing the system for different energy and carbon prices. When solving optimization models for a case study, the user can choose to solve the scenarios in parallel (`cs.optimize(parallel=True)`) using the distributed execution framework Ray [283] or serially to rely on the parallelization of the solver.

4.2.8 Visualization

DRAF provides a rich interactive visualization toolbox built into the `CaseStudy` and `Scenario` classes (see Fig. 4.1). The dot notation allows convenient plotting since the data and metadata are internally fetched. E.g., after optimizing multiple scenarios, `cs.plot.pareto()` plots the Pareto front of all scenarios in the case study, similar to Fig. 4.13 and `cs.scens.sc3.plot.sankey()` plots the Sankey diagram of scenario `sc3`, see Fig. D.4. Interactive parameter and result exploration are available thanks to the diverse capabilities of IPython [284] and Plotly [272], see also Fig. D.5.

4.3 Case studies and results

In the following, DRAF's features are demonstrated in three case studies that are considered to be of interest to the reader. The case studies are based on real companies in southern Germany with modified values for data protection reasons. In Case Study 1, the production schedule of a cement plant is optimized considering BPDR. This case study was selected as it illustrates DRAF's support for flexible industrial production processes. In Case Study 2, the design of a BES and a PV system at an industrial site is optimized considering multiple flexibility applications and differentiating between existing and new technologies. Case Study 3 covers a more sophisticated superstructure for a greenfield L-MES. This last case study demonstrates multi-objective optimization, the value of the scenario generator, and the consideration of multiple temperature levels. The code for the presented case studies is available on https://github.com/DrafProject/draf_demo_case_studies. The calculations were performed using DRAF v0.2.0 [267].

4.3.1 Case Study 1: Price-based DR potential of industrial production process

In the first case study, which is based on the previous work [285] and [76], DRAF is applied to the problem of quantifying the cost and CE reduction potential of BPDR of a cement milling process. A similar case study is detailed in Chapter 6.

The setup of the case study is shown in Fig. 4.5. There are two electric cement mills that turn cement clinker into three different cement sorts which are stored in separate silos to serve a given cement demand. For each time step, the cement mills can either be powered down or produce one compatible cement sort in full-load with a sort and machine-specific production efficiency, see Fig. 4.6 left. Machine 1 is compatible with sorts 1 and 3, and Machine 2 is compatible with Sorts 2 and 3, see Fig. 4.5. The cement clinker supply is not a

FIGURE 4.5: Setup of cement case study

FIGURE 4.6: Left: Machine and cement-sort-specific production efficiencies; Right: Cement demand and fixed electricity demand.

bottleneck in the production process, so it is modeled as unrestricted. The cement demand was generated by breaking down the total monthly demand into the working hours of the plant, see Fig. 4.6 right. A MILP model was built using DRAF’s component-templates Main, EG, pDEM, PP, and PS (see Appendices D.2.1 and D.2.12 to D.2.14) to minimize the TAC C^{TOT} of the system for 8,760 hourly time steps from the year 2019. Therein, cement mills are represented by machines, cement clinker by raw material, and cement silos by product storages. Dynamic TOU and RTP pricing schemes, and XEFs are prepared by DRAF’s TimeSeriesPrepper described in Section 4.2.4.1. The peak power price is $\text{€}50/\text{kW}_p$. A standard load profile for continuous production was scaled to the annual energy of 5 GWh and used as fixed electricity demand. The cement mills have nominal capacities of 3.5 MW each and a minimum part-load factor of 1. Each machine start-up and sort-change costs $\text{€}10.00$ due to inefficient operation associated with it. Cement Mill 1 is unavailable due to revisions from 15th to 16th of March, and Cement Mill 2 from 15th to 16th of February. Each cement silo has a capacity and initial filling of 5kt and a minimum filling level of 1kt. Since part-load operation is not possible, the deviation between the last and the initial filling level is evaluated with a factor k and penalized via the operating costs. k is composed of the worst efficiency and three times the average electricity price of the year. Thus, the deviation is minimized without introducing infeasibility. For brevity, investment in storage extension is not allowed, even though this would be possible with the model and would be an interesting analysis.

Despite the technical constraints and the small price spreads of 2019 the load shifting led to savings of €149k (1.9% of electricity costs) and 1.4k t_{CO₂eq} (9.2% of operating CEs) per year. However, these are theoretical values as complete foresight was assumed. The results for ten of the 365 optimized days are shown in Fig. 4.7. The plots show that while the silo filling levels look similar, the scheduling of the cement sorts between the two scenarios differs substantially on an hourly basis. The electricity price is the main factor in the production decision. Exceptions are due to sort-switching and start-up costs. The Pearson correlation coefficient r between the electricity price and the purchased electricity for the whole year is -0.29 with TOU pricing scheme and -0.58 with RTP, see Fig. 4.8. Since Machine 1 is more efficient than Machine 2, the most energy-intensive Sort 1 is only produced on Machine 1. Sort 1 is only produced on Machine 1 and Sort 2 only on Machine 2. The electrical peak demand was not lowered.

FIGURE 4.7: Results of Case Study 1: Resulting production plans, price schemes, and silo filling levels for ten sample days in April. Top: Reference scenario with time-of-use pricing scheme. Bottom: Scenario with hourly German day-ahead market prices.

4.3.2 Case Study 2: Design optimization of a multi-use BES and PV system

Fig. 4.9 shows the setup and problem of Case Study 2.

For the inflexible electricity demand, anonymized real industrial data of the year 2020 are used which are analyzed in Fig. D.1. Further input parameters are dynamic day-ahead market prices plus €62.3/MWh electricity taxes and levies and €100/kW peak electricity price. Specific investment cost forecasts for 2022 for PV and BES were taken from [286] with the values €384/kW_p and €209/kWh, respectively.

FIGURE 4.8: Correlations between purchased electricity and real-time-prices for both scenarios.

FIGURE 4.9: Setup and problem of Case Study 2. Setup: A company that can buy electricity from the grid and sell it to the grid, has an existing $300 \text{ kW}_{\text{peak}}$ PV system, $1,000 \text{ m}^2$ additionally available rooftop space for the installation of a new PV system, and an inflexible electricity demand. Problem: The design (nominal capacity/power) of the BES and the new PV is to be optimized assuming optimal charging and discharging of the BES considering peak shaving, RTPs through hourly wholesale prices, and the optimization of self-consumption.

TABLE 4.1: Capacities and investment costs of Case Study 2.

Scenario	CAP _x		CAP _n		C^{inv} [k€]		$C^{\text{inv,ann}}$ [k€/a]	
	BES	PV	BES	PV	BES	PV	BES	PV
REF	0	300	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
optBes	0	300	233.4	0.0	48.8	0.0	4.3	0.0
optPV	0	300	0.0	153.8	0.0	59.1	0.0	4.6
optBesPv	0	300	265.6	153.8	55.5	59.1	4.8	4.6

TABLE 4.2: Peak reductions of Case Study 2.

Scenario	P^{max}	$P^{\text{max,redution}}$		W^{buy}	W^{sell}
REF	1,445 kW	0 kW	0.0%	7.122 GWh/a	0.000 GWh/a
optBes	1,330 kW	115 kW	0.1%	7.130 GWh/a	0.000 GWh/a
optPV	1,445 kW	0 kW	0.0%	6.952 GWh/a	0.000 GWh/a
optBesPv	1,320 kW	125 kW	0.1%	6.960 GWh/a	0.000 GWh/a

FIGURE 4.10: Resulting electricity balance of Case Study 2. Top: Stacked area plot of electricity balance. Energy sources are positive. Energy usage is negative. Bottom: Real-time prices.

Four scenarios were modeled: REF (reference scenario), optBES (allows BES), optPV (allows new PV), and optBesPv (allows both). Tables 4.1 and 4.2 as well as Fig. D.3 show the results of Case Study 2. Fig. 4.10 shows the resulting electricity balance and the RTP of scenario optBesPv for one example week (Monday–Sunday).

4.3.3 Case Study 3: Multi-objective design and operational optimization of thermal-electric sector coupling

The third case study demonstrates the optimization of the design and operation of a more sophisticated industrial L-MES. This time it is a greenfield project, i.e., there are no existing technologies. Besides the inflexible electricity demand, the L-MES incorporates cooling and heating demands at different temperature levels. Fig. 4.11 shows an overview and the superstructure of the analyzed L-MES. Up to 20 MWh/h of electricity can be bought from and sold to the grid with hourly prices and XEFs. Assuming a plant-wide optimization with perfect foresight on XEFs, electricity prices, and PV yield profiles, Pareto-optimal design and operational configurations are to be identified that fulfill the thermal and electrical energy demands. The following component templates from Appendix D.2 are used: cDem, hDem, eDem, EG, Fuel, PV, BES, CHP, HOB, HP, P2H, H2H1, TES, and Main. The scheme in Fig. 4.12 provides details on the modeling of the different temperature levels.

Seven scenarios are modeled: The reference scenario REF and the six scenarios sc2, sc3, ..., sc7. REF only allows heat-only-boilers (HOBs) and cooling machines that are modeled using the HP component by allowing only heat transfers from the cooling demands to the ambient. The scenarios sc2 to sc7 allow all technologies of the superstructure and all HP operating modes. They differ from each other only by their Pareto weighting factor α .

FIGURE 4.11: Setup and superstructure of Case Study 3.

FIGURE 4.12: Scheme with details on modeling different temperature levels for Case Study 3. The HPs can choose between three source and sink temperature levels, respectively. The evaporation and condensation temperatures are calculated assuming a 5 K temperature difference for heat exchange. The coefficient of performance is calculated from the evaporation and condensation temperatures. Assuming the installation of multiple HPs, multiple parallel operation modes, i.e., temperature combinations between evaporation and condensation, can exist, however, for the calculation of the annualized investment costs, the capacities of all HPs are aggregated, which significantly reduces the model complexity.

For more details on HP modeling, see Appendix D.2.10.

The α value for the scenarios sc2 to sc7 is 0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1, respectively, i.e., sc2 optimizes TAC ($\alpha = 0$), scenarios sc3 to sc6 optimize Pareto efficiency ($0 < \alpha < 1$), and sc7 optimizes CEs ($\alpha = 1$).

Fig. 4.13 shows the TAC and annual CEs of the resulting scenarios and Fig. 4.14 shows the resulting capacities, cost types, and distribution of the electricity exchange with the electricity grid. Due to the multi-objective optimization, the scenarios sc3 to sc7 are Pareto-efficient, i.e., one objective value cannot be decreased without increasing the other. One can see that with increasing α values, i.e., increasing focus on CEs within the objective function, the investment cost and the annualized investment cost are increasing, too. Compared to REF, sc2, and sc3 have lower TACs than REF by 36% and 9%, respectively, since higher annualized investment and maintenance costs are overcompensated by savings in operating costs. Additionally, sc2 and sc3 can reduce CEs by 49% and 66%, respectively compared to REF. Comparing sc2 and sc3 to REF produces no conflict of objectives since REF is not on the Pareto frontier. The scenarios sc4 to sc7 have no economic advantage over REF, however, they do have an environmental advantage over REF. Scenarios sc3 and sc5 can be regarded as good trade-offs when looking at all available Pareto-efficient solutions. Scenario sc7 represents the highest possible CE savings with 87%, however, the TACs are 41 times higher than in REF. Since in sc7 TACs are not considered, capacities are set to the highest possible value that was put in place for each technology, e.g., 1 GWh for BES and 100 MWh for each TES. This is an unrealistic behavior that could be avoided by considering Scope 3 CEs which include the CEs of the production of the energy technologies analogous to the annualized investment costs within the calculation of TACs. However, it demonstrates how Scope 1 and 2 CEs can be reduced by increasing the system's flexibility. As can be seen in Fig. 4.14 bottom, in sc7 the technical upper limit of 20 MW of electrical power drawn from the grid is exploited during hours of low CEFs, which would stabilize the grid when there is a surplus of renewable energy. Screenshots of Sankey diagrams for REF and sc3 are shown in Fig. D.4.

FIGURE 4.13: Pareto-optimal configuration scenarios of Case Study 3. The dotted line approximates the Pareto frontier. REF is not on the Pareto front since both objectives can be improved, e.g., in sc2 or sc3. The broken y-axis is used to fit in the minimal-emission scenario sc7 ($\alpha = 1$), which has more than 41 times higher TAC than REF. The scenario sc3 has 9% less TAC than the REF whilst also reducing CE by two-thirds.

FIGURE 4.14: Results per scenarios of Case Study 3. Top: Capacities, investment costs, and operating costs. Middle left: Thermal energy storage (TES) capacities per temperature levels. Middle right: TAC per cost types: operating costs (op), maintenance costs (RMI), and annualized investment costs (ann_inv). Bottom: Distribution of the electricity bought from the grid (negative=sold electricity).

4.4 Conclusions

DRAF, an open-source multi-objective decision support tool for L-MESs, was developed, described, and demonstrated. By providing vital information about the environmental and economical potential of innovative energy technologies and services, DRAF lowers investment barriers of L-MES decision-makers. It considers load flexibility, energy efficiency, electrification, and their interdependencies in an integrated model without neglecting critical aspects such as multiple temperature levels or DR of production processes. DRAF considers flexible electricity sources and sinks across the whole energy conversion chain of an L-MES such as an industrial site. While providing useful pre-configured components that allow complex DR analyses with just a few lines of code, the tool setup does not restrict the users' freedom to build any possible MILP model. DRAF is needed since the existing software for potential identification of MESs is either (a) too generic to be practicably applied to L-MESs, (b) leaves out essential aspects such as temperature levels or the access to dynamic emission factors, or (c) is not open-source.

Three case studies demonstrate how different settings and applications can be modeled within DRAF. Case Study 1 shows how PBDR of a production process can reduce costs and operating CEs. Case Study 2 demonstrates a simple design and operational optimization problem for a PV and multi-use BESS. The more sophisticated design optimization of Case Study 3 demonstrates the consideration of multiple temperature levels, the selection of heat sources and sinks for the HP, and the results of a multi-objective pareto analysis to select the optimal trade-off between economic considerations and the reduction of CEs.

Appendix: Screenshots of DRAF output and model details of component templates. Appendix D offers screenshots of exemplary DRAF output. Furthermore, it details the model formulations of 17 component templates.

Chapter 5

From prosumer to flexumer: Case study on the value of flexibility in decarbonizing the multi-energy system of a manufacturing company

Abstract. Digitalization and sector coupling enable companies to turn into flexumers. By using the flexibility of their multi-energy system (MES), they reduce costs and carbon emissions while balancing the electricity grid. However, to identify the necessary investments in energy conversion and storage technologies to leverage demand response (DR) potentials, companies need to assess the value of flexibility. Therefore, this chapter quantifies the flexibility value of a production company's MES by optimizing the synthesis, design, and operation of a decarbonizing MES considering self-consumption optimization, peak shaving, and integrated DR based on hourly prices and carbon emission factors (CEFs). The detailed case study of a beverage company in northern Germany considers vehicle-to-X of electrical industrial forklifts, power-to-heat on multiple temperatures, wind turbines, photovoltaic systems, and energy storage systems (thermal, electrical, and hydrogen). Novel data-driven metrics to evaluate the intensity of price-based and CEF-based DR are proposed and applied. The results reveal that flexibility usage reduces decarbonization costs (by 19–80% depending on electricity and carbon removal prices), total annual costs, operational carbon footprint, energy-weighted average prices and CEFs, and fossil energy dependency. The results also suggest that a net-zero operational carbon emission MES requires flexibility, which, in an economic case, is provided by a combination of different flexible technologies and storage systems that complement each other. While the value of flexibility depends on various market and consumer-specific factors such as electricity or carbon removal prices,

this chapter highlights the importance of demand flexibility for the decarbonization of MESs.

Acknowledgments. The contents of this chapter are based on the paper *From prosumer to flexumer: Case study on the value of flexibility in decarbonizing the multi-energy system of a manufacturing company* [287]. Markus Fleschutz is the primary author of this paper. The research was performed as part of the MeSSO Research Group at the Munster Technological University (MTU) and in relation to the project WIN4climate as part of the National Climate Initiative financed by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK) on the basis of a decision by the German Bundestag (No. 03KF0094A). It was additionally funded by the MTU Risam Scholarship Scheme .

5.1 Overview and context

FIGURE 5.1: Day-ahead spot market price and daily price spread of the market zone Germany-Luxembourg for 2019–2023. Prices sourced from [242].

Increasing flexibility incentives. Despite the worldwide expansion of vRESs, the wholesale electricity prices of the last decades have offered few incentives for flexibility [288]. However, since mid-2021, European electricity prices skyrocketed as a result of increased carbon and fuel prices. The natural gas prices were especially driven by the COVID-19 pandemic and the Russian invasion of Ukraine, but also by technical issues, a longer winter, and lower wind and hydro generation [289]. Additionally, in countries with substantial vRES shares, not only the level of wholesale electricity prices has increased, but also the price fluctuation due to the merit order effect [290]. For example, in the German day-ahead market, mean daily price spreads (i.e., the difference between the lowest and highest price of each day) increased over six-fold between 2019 and 2022 and over threefold between 2019 and 2023, see Fig. 5.1. Interestingly, in 2023, the average daily price spread was 1.03 times the average price. This means that shifting a unit of energy from the most expensive hour

of the day to the cheapest hour, on average, saved more money than it costs to generate that unit of energy.

Summary of literature review. In the review of relevant literature in Section 2.2, it is observed that prior research has explored the potential of DR strategies to reduce both costs and CEs in current industrial energy systems. These studies show notable potential for diminishing CEs and operational expenses. This potential could be further amplified if the integration of flexibility markets is incorporated at the initial design phase of these systems. However, a significant gap in existing research is the lack of empirical data to substantiate this theory.

Contribution. Consequently, this chapter identifies an unexplored area in the literature: Assessing the financial impact of including flexibility considerations during the design and retrofit stages of MESs, in contrast to traditional planning methodologies. The novelty of this work is the evaluation of the economic effect of considering flexibility potentials in the design and retrofit stage of industrial energy supply systems with respect to various decarbonization objectives. With respect to this objective, the contributions of this chapter are fourfold:

1. Develop a synthesis, design, and operation optimization MILP model that considers flexibility applications such as self-consumption optimization, price-based and CEF-based voluntary DR, and peak shaving when planning investments to decarbonize existing MESs.
2. Propose and demonstrate new metrics to evaluate the cost and carbon footprint reduction potential by leveraging the flexibility potentials with respect to the energy-weighted average price and the energy-weighted average CEs.
3. Conduct a case study of an industrial energy supply system and evaluate the cost and CE reduction potential by leveraging the flexibility potentials to decarbonize the existing supply system.
4. Support the hypothesis that considering flexibility potentials in the design stage significantly reduces the decarbonization costs.

Chapter organization. The remainder of this chapter is organized as follows. First, the case study is explained in Section 5.2.1. Subsequently, the optimization model is described in Section 5.2.2 and the case study data in Section 5.2.3. The scenarios and contexts are defined in Section 5.2.4. In Section 5.2.5, the evaluation metrics are defined. In Section 5.3, the results of the analysis are presented and discussed. Finally, Section 5.4 concludes this chapter.

5.2 Materials and methods

5.2.1 Case study

The MES of a beverage company in northern Germany is considered. Fig. 5.2 shows a schematic depiction of the case study. This company has already invested in renewable infrastructure and is working towards net zero CEs.

FIGURE 5.2: Overview scheme of the case study. It shows the external energy supply (left), the company’s multi-energy system (MES) (center) including conversion and storage technologies, the energy demand of the company (right), and the energy flows between the components. Grayed-out energy flows or components such as the thermal energy storage (TES) or the power-to-heat (P2H) currently do not exist but are possible to implement. In the status quo of the MES, the electricity demand is provided by a photovoltaic (PV) system, a combined heat and power (CHP) system based on natural gas, and the electricity grid (EG). There are no energy storage systems except the battery electric vehicles (BEVs; here: forklift trucks) but they are charged unidirectionally at full power until fully charged. The cold demand is served by the cooling machine (electric heat pump (HP) without using the hot side to serve heat demands). The heat demands on both temperature levels are met by the CHP and a natural gas-fueled heat-only boiler (HOB).

Energy demands. The company has an electricity demand and three different thermal energy demands with the following flow and return temperature levels in °C: Cooling demand (7/12), space heat demand (75/55), and process heat demand (95/75). The author calculated the hourly inflexible electricity demand that is independent of flexible operation and stays the same for all scenarios:

$$P_t^{\text{eDem}} = \tilde{P}_t^{\text{EG,buy}} + \tilde{P}_t^{\text{PV,OC}} - \tilde{P}_t^{\text{BEV,drive}} - \tilde{P}_t^{\text{CM}} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (5.1)$$

where $\tilde{P}_t^{\text{EG,buy}}$, $\tilde{P}_t^{\text{PV,OC}}$, and $\tilde{P}_t^{\text{BEV,drive}}$ are the historic data for the purchased electricity from the electricity grid (EG), the PV energy consumed from the onsite PV system, and the

electricity consumption of the BEVs, respectively. \tilde{P}_t^{CM} is an approximation of the cooling machine. Fig. 5.3 presents key metrics of the three thermal demands and the inflexible electricity demand. It can be seen that the cold demand has a seasonal pattern peaking in summer, while the heat demands are more stable throughout the year. Electricity demand is slightly higher during the summer months due to the increased beverage production.

FIGURE 5.3: Description of the electricity (elec.) and thermal energy (75/55, 95/75, 7/12) demand time series. **a)** Annual energy sums, **b)** violin plots showing annual distribution, **c)** monthly average demand, **d)** average week and 95% confidence interval.

Existing technologies. The company runs an onsite 307kW_p PV system. For the analyses, the author used the historical measured electricity generation of the year 2019, see Section 5.2.2.3. Based on available roof space, an additional PV capacity of up to $2,770\text{kW}_p$ can be built with the same profile and efficiency. A cooling machine with 860kW cooling power exists on site that can recool with 10°C well water. The company owns a CHP with 410kW_{th} nominal heating power and a $1,620\text{kW}_{th}$ heat-only boiler (HOB). Both run on natural gas and supply heat at the $97/75$ temperature level. There are 24 Li-ion forklift batteries with a net capacity of 81.1kWh each.

5.2.2 Optimization model

5.2.2.1 General

To quantify the value of flexibility for this company, a deterministic MILP model is formulated using technology components of DRAF, described in Chapter 4. An overview of the model is shown in Fig. 5.4. Most used technology components are detailed in Appendix D.2. However, model parts that are crucial (cost and carbon balances) or not described in Chapter 4 such as WT, pressurized H₂ storage (H₂S), proton exchange membrane fuel cell (FC), proton exchange membrane electrolyzer (Elc), and DAC are described in this section. Perfect foresight is assumed and one year with 8,760 hourly time steps $t \in \mathcal{T}$ is modeled, so $\Delta t = 1$ h. Optimization variables are indicated in bold and are non-negative continuous variables if not specified.

FIGURE 5.4: Main technical model features

The objective function of the MILP problem is the minimization of the **TAC** in $\text{k€}/\text{yr}$ and the penalty term $\mathbf{X}^{\text{penalty}}$ to model conventional charging. The **TAC** include capital expenditures (**CapEx**) and operating expenses (**OpEx**), see Eq. (5.3).

$$\text{minimize } \mathbf{TAC} + \mathbf{X}^{\text{penalty}} \quad (5.2)$$

$$\mathbf{TAC} = \mathbf{CapEx} + \mathbf{OpEx} \quad (5.3)$$

$$\mathbf{TAC}, \mathbf{OpEx} \in \mathbb{R}$$

The **CapEx** represent the annualized investment costs for all technical components in the technology set \mathcal{I} :

$$\mathbf{CapEx} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} a(r, n_i) c_i^{\text{inv}} P_i^{\text{capn}} \quad (5.4)$$

where c_i^{inv} are the specific investment costs and P_i^{capn} the new nominal capacity of technology $i \in \mathcal{I}$. $a(r, n_i)$ is the annuity factor of component i as function of the discount rate r and the economic life n_i in years, see Eq. (5.5).

$$a(r, n_i) = \frac{r(1+r)^{n_i}}{(1+r)^{n_i} - 1} \quad (5.5)$$

The **OpEx** represent the operating costs of the first year:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{OpEx} = & \mathbf{C}^{\text{RMI}} + \mathbf{C}^{\text{EG,buy}} - \mathbf{R}^{\text{EG,sell}} + \mathbf{C}^{\text{EG,NF}} \\ & + \mathbf{C}^{\text{WT,NF}} + \mathbf{C}^{\text{NG}} + \mathbf{C}^{\text{NG,tax}} + \mathbf{C}^{\text{DAC}} \end{aligned} \quad (5.6)$$

$$\mathbf{C}^{\text{EG,buy}}, \mathbf{C}^{\text{EG,sell}} \in \mathbb{R}$$

$$\mathbf{C}^{\text{DAC}} = \mathbf{CE}^{\text{DAC}} c^{\text{DAC}} \quad (5.7)$$

where \mathbf{C}^{RMI} are the repair, maintenance, and inspection (RMI) costs, $\mathbf{C}^{\text{EG,buy}}$ are the costs of purchased electricity, $\mathbf{R}^{\text{EG,sell}}$ are the revenue of sold electricity, $\mathbf{C}^{\text{EG,NF}}$ and $\mathbf{C}^{\text{WT,NF}}$ are the network fees of purchased electricity and self-consumed electricity from the WT, respectively, \mathbf{C}^{NG} are the costs of purchased natural gas, $\mathbf{C}^{\text{NG,tax}}$ are the carbon tax costs due to the purchased natural gas, \mathbf{C}^{DAC} are the costs for carbon removal, \mathbf{CE}^{DAC} are the removed CEs, and c^{DAC} are the specific costs of carbon removal.

The total operational carbon footprint of the first year, \mathbf{CE} , is calculated through:

$$\mathbf{CE} = \underbrace{\Delta t \varepsilon^{\text{NG}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} P_t^{\text{NG,buy}}}_{\text{Scope 1 (direct)}} + \underbrace{\Delta t \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \varepsilon_t^{\text{elec}} P_t^{\text{EG,buy}}}_{\text{Scope 2 (indirect)}} - \underbrace{\mathbf{CE}^{\text{DAC}}}_{\text{carbon removal}} \quad (5.8)$$

where ε^{NG} is the CEF for natural gas and $\varepsilon_t^{\text{elec}}$ denote the hourly electricity CEFs.

TABLE 5.1: Technology parameters

Technology	Spec. inv. costs c_{inv}^{inv} (€/base)	Base	RMI costs c^{RMI} (%/yr)	Econ. life n (yr)	Input	Efficiency η (%)	Output	C rate λ (kW/kWh)	
Conversion	CHP	589.46 [291]	kW _{el}	18	25	natural gas	40	elec.	-
	—	-	-	-	-	natural gas	45	heat	-
	Elc	1,295 [133]	kW _{el}	3.8	14	elec.	71	H ₂	-
	FC	1,684 [133]	kW _{el}	3.8	14	H ₂	50	elec.	-
	—	-	-	-	-	H ₂	34	heat	-
	HOB	57.13 [292]	kW _{th}	18	15	natural gas	90	heat	-
	HP	387 [133]	kW _{th,cond}	2.5	18	elec., heat	50 ^b	heat	-
	P2H	100 [293]	kW _{th}	0	30	elec.	90	heat	-
	PV	460 [286]	kW _p	2	25	- given profile -	-	elec.	-
WT	1,682 [294]	kW _p	1	20	- given profile -	-	elec.	-	
Storage	BES	600 [295]	kWh _{el}	2	20	elec.	95 _{cycle} ^c	elec.	0.7
	BEV	-	-	-	-	elec.	95 _{cycle}	elec.	0.7
	H ₂ S	10 [133]	kWh _{H₂}	0	23	H ₂	90 _{cycle}	H ₂	- ^d
	TES	28.71 [296]	kWh _{th}	0.1	30	heat	99.5 _{time}	heat	0.5

^a Based on investment costs

^b Exergy efficiency $\eta^{HP,Carnot}$ (ratio of reaching ideal Carnot COP)

^c Additionally, $\eta^{self}=0.002\%/h$ applies due to self-discharge [297]

^d The C rate of H₂S is determined by the Elc and FC capacities.

The electricity grid (EG) is defined by the following constraints:

$$C^{EG,buy} = \Delta t \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} P_t^{EG,buy} (c_t^{elec} + c^{EG,addon}) \quad (5.9)$$

$$P_t^{EG,buy} \leq \hat{P}^{EG,buy} \leq P^{EG,buy,max} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (5.10)$$

$$C^{EG,NF} = \hat{P}^{EG,buy} c^{EG,buy} \quad (5.11)$$

$$R^{EG,sell} = \Delta t \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} P_t^{EG,sell} c_t^{elec} \quad (5.12)$$

$$P_t^{EG,sell} \leq P^{EG,sell,max} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (5.13)$$

where $P_t^{EG,buy}$ and $P_t^{EG,sell}$ are the purchased and sold electrical power, respectively, c_t^{elec} and $c^{EG,addon}$ is the dynamic and fixed electricity energy price component, respectively, $\hat{P}^{EG,buy}$ is the installed power capacity, $P^{EG,buy,max}$ and $P^{EG,sell,max}$ are the maximum purchase and selling power, and $c^{EG,buy}$ is the peak price that is weighted with $\hat{P}^{EG,buy}$, the peak power of the year.

5.2.2.2 Technology overview

Fig. 5.8 depicts the conversion and storage technologies used in the case study and an overview of their main parameters is given in Table 5.1.

5.2.2.3 Energy conversion technologies

The conversion technologies CHP, HP, Elc, FC, HOB, and P2H are modeled with a linear input-output relationship

$$P_t^{\text{in}} = \eta P_t^{\text{out}} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (5.14)$$

$$P_t^{\text{out}} \leq P^{\text{cap}} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (5.15)$$

where some technologies have multiple outputs, see also Table 5.1. Further constraints are detailed in Appendix D.2, more specifically: D.2.7 (CHP), D.2.10 (HP), D.2.8 (HOB), D.2.9 (P2H).

5.2.2.4 Energy storage technologies

The BES system model is described in Appendix D.2.3. The H₂S and the TES are formulated analogously. The description of the BEV model is shown in Appendix D.2.6.

5.2.3 Data for the case study

For general parameters used in the case study, please see Table E.1.

Electricity grid prices. The purchased electricity $P_t^{\text{EG, buy}}$ is limited to $P^{\text{EG, buy, max}}$ of 20 MW. For the cost of electricity purchase, a RTP tariff, as is now offered by more and more electricity providers is assumed. The tariff consists of a time-dependent energy price components c_t^{elec} , a time-independent energy price component $c^{\text{EG, addon}}$, and a power price component $\hat{c}^{\text{EG, buy}}$, see Eq. (5.11). For c_t^{elec} , historic hourly day-ahead electricity prices of the year 2019 are assumed. These are shown in Fig. 5.5 top, which were sourced from the ENTSO-E transparency platform [242] via the Python package Elmada [261]. An $c^{\text{EG, addon}}$ of €62.28/MWh is assumed which consists of €27.19/MWh taxes and levies based on [298] and €35.09/MWh network costs and sales. It does not include the German Renewable Energies Act levy (EEG Umlage), which is no longer due since July 2022. Additionally, the company has to pay a power price of $\hat{c}^{\text{EG, buy}}$ of €70/kW_p. The sold electricity $P_t^{\text{EG, sell}}$ is limited to $P^{\text{EG, sell, max}}$ of 20 MW and compensated with c_t^{elec} , see Eqs. (5.12) and (5.13).

Electricity grid carbon emission factors. The analysis in this chapter includes short-term load shifting, for which MEFs should be used as demonstrated in Chapter 3 if the impact on CEs is explicitly examined. However, since the environmental DR potentials in this analysis are modeled implicitly and inseparable from the investment decisions the

author takes an attributional approach, thus using electricity XEFs for $\varepsilon_t^{\text{EG}}$. National dynamic XEFs, shown in Fig. 5.5 bottom, were calculated using the XEF_EP method of Elmada [261]. This method uses fuel type-specific generation data from the ENTSO-E transparency platform [242] and fuel type-specific CE intensities from [252]. Electricity purchased from the EG was evaluated with XEFs, while the negative CEs through grid feed-in from own vRESs were not compensated.

FIGURE 5.5: Day-ahead spot market prices (top) and XEFs (bottom) for the German electricity market of the year 2019.

Natural gas grid. Natural gas can be purchased for €43/MWh with 0.240 t_{CO2eq} per MWh [299] CE intensity. The carbon tax ($c^{\text{NG,tax}}$) of €55/t_{CO2eq} has to be paid.

Electrical heat pump (HP). The HP has two heat sources $n \in \mathcal{N}$ (cold demand with 7°C and the well water with 10°C) and two heat sinks $c \in \mathcal{C}$ (the well water and the space heat demand with 75°C). This results in three possible combinations of source-sink temperature levels defining the operating mode: Cold demand to well, cold demand to heat demand, and well to heat demand. The evaporation and condensation temperatures ($\vartheta_{t,n}^{\text{HP,eva}}$, $\vartheta_{t,c}^{\text{HP,cond}}$) were calculated assuming a 5°C temperature difference to consider heat exchange for both evaporator and condenser.

Photovoltaic (PV). The PV electricity generation time series per kW_p installed capacity is an exogenous variable. The author used historic measurements of the case study company for the year 2019 in an aggregated form, see Fig. 5.6 top. The capacity factor for 2019 is 0.10.

FIGURE 5.6: Historic electricity generation profile per kW_p installed capacity of the case study PV system (top) and the Kelmarsh 6 WT (bottom).

Wind turbine (WT). The WT electricity generation time series per kWh_p installed capacity is an exogenous variable, see Fig. 5.6 bottom. The hourly profile for 2019 is aggregated from the open data of the Kelmarsh 6 [300], a 2.04 MW Senvion MM92 WT located in the Kelmarsh wind farm in the United Kingdom which is used as a proxy for northern Germany. The capacity factor for 2019 is 0.33. For used WT electricity, an electricity price add-on $c^{\text{EG,addon}}$ is paid. Unused WT electricity is sold at the day-ahead market price, assuming that the guarantees of origins are sold for a negligible price, so there are no negative CEs. Investment in partial WTs (shareholder) is possible.

Battery electric vehicle (BEV). In the case study, the author models multiple forklift trucks as a special form of BEVs. To reduce model complexity, the capacity of 12 batteries is aggregated that had similar availability patterns resulting in two batteries with 973.2 kWh capacity each. Two representative availability time series based on the real empirical data

from the battery energy management system are used. Fig. 5.7 indicates the number of available batteries for charging across the year.

FIGURE 5.7: Number of available batteries throughout the year 2019. The numbers and percentages in brackets indicate how often an availability appears. While all batteries are available in 2,187 hours (25% of the year), no battery is available in 2,090 hours (24%).

5.2.4 Scenario and context definition

5.2.4.1 Scenario definition

Seven scenarios are modeled: One unoptimized reference scenario (REF), three optimized non-decarbonization scenarios (noFlex, someFlex, fullFlex), and three optimized decarbonization scenarios (noFlex_d, someFlex_d, fullFlex_d). The scenario definition is summarized in Fig. 5.8 and described in the following:

- **REF:** This scenario represents the unoptimized status quo, also described in Fig. 5.2. Electricity demand is covered by the EG, the PV, and the CHP. BEVs are charged unidirectionally at full power until fully charged. Heat demands are met by the CHP and the HOB. The cold demand is served by the cooling machine which was modeled as a HP with 1,147 kW on the hot side and in a restricted mode so that heat in the condenser is only transferred to the well water. It is assumed that the cooling machine only exists in the REF scenario and must be replaced in other scenarios, to make the results comparable between them. There are no energy storage systems. Investments are not considered.
- **noFlex:** Investments in the conversion technologies WT, PV, HP, P2H are allowed. According capacities are optimally designed. The smart HP mode selection is deactivated by disallowing heat transfer from cold to heat demand. Fuel switching is deactivated by fixing the CHP operation to the CHP operation in REF. Smart/bidirectional BEV charging and investments in storage systems are deactivated.

↓ Possible options	Scenarios →			
	REF	noFlex, noFlex_d	someFlex, someFlex_d	fullFlex, fullFlex_d
Conversion tech. investments ^a	X	✓	✓	✓
Use of existing flexibility ^b	X	X	✓	✓
Storage tech. investments ^c	X	X	X	✓

^a WT, PV, HP, and P2H

^b smart/bidirectional BEV charging, fuel switching, and smart HP mode selection

^c BES, TES (on all temperature levels), and H₂S (including Elc and FC)

FIGURE 5.8: Definition of scenarios

- **someFlex**: Additionally to **noFlex**, some flexibility sources can be used: BEVs can be charged smartly/bidirectionally. For each time step heat supply can be chosen to be gas-based (HOB, CHP) and/or electricity-based (HP, P2H), since the restriction to the CHP operation is removed. However, storage investments are still deactivated.
- **fullFlex**: Additionally, investments in the following storage technologies are allowed: BES, TES (on all three temperature levels), and H₂S including Elc and FC with waste heat utilization on the 75/55 temperature level.
- **noFlex_d**, **someFlex_d**, **fullFlex_d**: Decarbonization scenarios based on **noFlex**, **someFlex**, and **fullFlex**, respectively. Scope 1 and 2 carbon neutrality is enforced. Natural gas is strictly forbidden to prevent investments in and operation of fossil-based infrastructure. Electricity-based CEs must be removed with the specific carbon removal costs c^{DAC} .

FIGURE 5.9: Distribution of day-ahead electricity market prices of 2019, 2021, and 2022 (top, until October) and the used 2019 profile that was scaled to 2021 levels (bottom).

5.2.4.2 Context definition

The author models all scenarios for the three contexts defined in Table 5.2. c_{base} is the base context with electricity price data of 2019 and specific carbon removal costs c^{DAC} of $\text{€}222/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2\text{eq}}$ – the specific costs of direct air capturing [301]. In c_{strict} , electricity price data of 2019 is used but c^{DAC} is set to $\text{€}10,000/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2\text{eq}}$. If this high price is paid, the onsite decarbonization is not viable. This context applies when a company does not plan to rely

TABLE 5.2: Definition of contexts

Context	Carbon removal price c^{DAC}	Electricity price c_t^{elec}
c_base	€222/t _{CO₂eq}	2019 data
c_strict	€10,000/t _{CO₂eq}	2019 data
c_scaled	€222/t _{CO₂eq}	2019 data scaled to 2021

on carbon removal or on the carbon reductions of the electricity grid. In `c_scaled`, c^{DAC} is €222/t_{CO₂eq} but the electricity prices are scaled to 2021 levels. By picking the year 2019 as base year, the quantified value of flexibility is underestimated due to the relatively low price spreads on the day-ahead market, see Fig. 5.1, however, energy demands do not feature anomalies from the COVID-19 pandemic. Therefore, in `c_scaled`, the day-ahead market prices of the year 2019 are scaled to roughly match the mean, the standard deviation, and the extreme points of the prices of 2021, see Fig. 5.9. All other time series such as energy demands, vRES profiles, and electricity grid CEFs are kept unchanged. By avoiding the combination of time series from different years, correlations between day-ahead market prices, thermal loads, and renewable energy generation are maintained. Also, the 2022 price distribution is not used since the author assumes that they are overestimating the potential due to short-term consequences of the Russian invasion of Ukraine.

5.2.5 Evaluation metrics

5.2.5.1 Evaluation of DR based on prices and CEFs

Through penalizing or constraining CEs in a MES model considering PBDR, CEFs can work as an additional DR incentive. E.g., if Scope 1 CEs are forced to be zero and Scope 2 CEs are penalized with a carbon price of €222/t_{CO₂eq}, the effective DR incentive is the sum of electricity prices and carbon price-weighted CEFs, presented in Fig. 5.10.

To evaluate DR based on electricity prices and CEFs, multiple related metrics are defined. The energy-weighted average price (EWAP_s) and energy-weighted average CEF (EWACEF_s) are defined in Eqs. (5.16) and (5.17). For a scenario s , they measure the price and CEF of the average unit of purchased electricity respectively. While the EWAP is the total purchased electricity costs (excluding network charges, taxes, and levies) divided by the total purchased electrical energy, the EWACEF is the quotient of the total carbon footprint due to purchased electricity and the total purchased electrical energy. EWAP and EWACEF can be interpreted as the inability of the MES to react to the electricity prices and CEFs,

FIGURE 5.10: Financial DR signal that consists of electricity prices of Fig. 5.5 plus the CEFs of Fig. 5.5 weighted by a carbon (removal) price of $222\text{€}/\text{tCO}_{2\text{eq}}$.

respectively.

$$\underbrace{\text{EWAP}_s}_{\text{in } \text{€}/\text{MWh}} = \frac{\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} c_t^{\text{elec}} \mathbf{P}_{t,s}^{\text{EG, buy}} \Delta t}{\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \mathbf{P}_{t,s}^{\text{EG, buy}} \Delta t} \quad (5.16)$$

$$\underbrace{\text{EWACEF}_s}_{\text{in } \text{tCO}_{2\text{eq}}/\text{MWh}} = \frac{\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \varepsilon_t^{\text{elec}} \mathbf{P}_{t,s}^{\text{EG, buy}} \Delta t}{\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \mathbf{P}_{t,s}^{\text{EG, buy}} \Delta t} \quad (5.17)$$

For comparison, the time-weighted average price (TWAP) and the time-weighted average CEF (TWACEF) are defined:

$$\underbrace{\text{TWAP}}_{\text{in } \text{€}/\text{MWh}} = \frac{\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} c_t^{\text{elec}} \Delta t}{\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \Delta t} \quad (5.18)$$

$$\underbrace{\text{TWACEF}}_{\text{in } \text{tCO}_{2\text{eq}}/\text{MWh}} = \frac{\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \varepsilon_t^{\text{elec}} \Delta t}{\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \Delta t} \quad (5.19)$$

In simple terms, TWAP is the average price, EWAP is the average paid price, TWACEF is the average CEF, and EWACEF is the average accounted CEF. While TWAP and TWACEF only look at the electricity market results c_t^{elec} and $\varepsilon_t^{\text{elec}}$, EWAP and EWACEF also look at the profile of the demand-side electricity purchase $\mathbf{P}_t^{\text{EG, buy}}$.

Next, the π_s -rate and the ε_s -rate of scenario s are defined by normalizing EWAP_s with TWAP and EWACEF_s with TWACEF:

$$\pi_s = \frac{\text{EWAP}_s}{\text{TWAP}} \quad (5.20)$$

$$\varepsilon_s = \frac{\text{EWACEF}_s}{\text{TWACEF}} \quad (5.21)$$

The π -rate has three advantages over EWAP. Firstly, it considers the price profile c_t^{elec} independently of the units, i.e., a European case study using € can be compared to an American using \$. Secondly, it is relative to the average price allowing comparison between time frames with different price levels, e.g., the years 2019 and 2021. Thirdly, it indicates if the EWAP_s is over the TWAP ($\pi_s > 100\%$) or under ($\pi_s < 100\%$). In the case of $\pi_s < 100\%$, the respective electricity purchase profile are more market-serving than a flat load profile because it aligns with the price fluctuations in the market. The same advantages apply analogously to the ε -rate.

The time-based cost–emission ratio (TCER), is the scenario-independent ratio of the average electricity prices to the average CEF:

$$\underbrace{\text{TCER}}_{\text{in } \text{€}/\text{tCO}_{2\text{eq}}} = \frac{\text{TWAP}}{\text{TWACEF}} \quad (5.22)$$

A TCER of $\text{€}100/\text{tCO}_{2\text{eq}}$, e.g., means that if a load is reduced equally over all time steps, $\text{€}100$ is saved for each reduced ton of CEs. On an energy-specific price-emission diagram with flexibility metrics Fig. 5.11, TCER is the gradient of the line between the origin and the intersection between the TWAP and the TWACEF.

FIGURE 5.11: Energy-specific price-emission diagram to illustrate flexibility metrics.

In contrast, the energy-based cost-emission ratio (ECER) of scenario s is the ratio of EWAP_s to EWACEF_s :

$$\underbrace{\text{ECER}_s}_{\text{in } \text{€}/\text{tCO}_{2\text{eq}}} = \frac{\text{EWAP}_s}{\text{EWACEF}_s} \quad (5.23)$$

On an EWAP - EWACEF plot, the ECER_s is the gradient of the line between the origin and the scenario s , see Fig. 5.11.

Next, the ECER for two scenarios, s and s_b , are defined where s_b is the baseline scenario without flexibility:

$$\underbrace{\text{ECER}_{s, s_b}}_{\text{in } \text{€}/\text{tCO}_{2\text{eq}}} = \frac{\text{EWAP}_{s_b} - \text{EWAP}_s}{\text{EWACEF}_{s_b} - \text{EWACEF}_s} \quad (5.24)$$

$ECER_{s,s_b}$ can be also interpreted as the ratio of electrical energy cost savings to CE savings of scenario s compared to the baseline scenario s_b . E.g., an $ECER_{a,b}$ of €150/t_{CO₂eq} means that on average €150 is saved for each reduced ton of CE. On the EWAP-EWACEF plot, $ECER_{s,s_b}$ represents the gradient of the line between s and s_b , see Fig. 5.11. When assessing DR, i.e., the modification of $P_t^{EG, buy}$, $ECER_{s,s_b}$ can be interpreted as how strongly cost reduction is weighted relative to carbon footprint reduction.

Finally, based on the previous metrics, the normalized gradients ω_s and ω_{s,s_b} are defined:

$$\omega_s = \frac{\pi_s}{\varepsilon_s} = \frac{ECER_s}{TCER} \quad (5.25)$$

$$\omega_{s,s_b} = \frac{\pi_s - \pi_{s_b}}{\varepsilon_s - \varepsilon_{s_b}} \quad (5.26)$$

They have the same advantages over $ECER_s$ then the π -rate has over EWAP.

The metrics defined in Section 5.2.5.1 can be applied to any price and load dataset. Also, they can be applied to a subset of data, e.g., months or weekdays. It is worth mentioning that while the EG feed-in also impacts the stability of the EG and the electricity markets, the evaluation of EG feed-in is beyond the scope of this chapter.

5.2.5.2 Evaluation of decarbonization costs

To evaluate the additional cost of achieving net-zero carbon footprint, the decarbonization costs C_s^{decarb} are calculated:

$$C_s^{decarb} = TAC_{s_d} - TAC_s \quad (5.27)$$

where the scenarios s_d and s represent the cost optimal MES with and without enforcing net-zero carbon footprint, respectively.

5.3 Results

In this section, the results of the three contexts are described sequentially and discussed at the end. The MILP models were solved to global optimality (MIP gap=0) using Gurobi 9.5.1. The calculation time for one optimization run with seven scenarios was between 10 and 80 minutes depending on the context.

5.3.1 Results of **c_base** (base context)

Figs. 5.12 to 5.15 and E.1 to E.6 and Table 5.3 show the results of the base context **c_base**.

The Sankey plots in Fig. E.6 provide an overview of the resulting annual energy sums of the MES for each scenario. It can be seen that the heat demands were partly electrified in the non-decarbonization scenarios and fully electrified in the decarbonization scenarios.

TABLE 5.3: Capacities for newly invested components for the c_base context.

Technology → Scenario ↓, Unit →	PV kW _P	WT kW _P	HP kW _{th,cond}	P2H kW _{th}	TES kWh _{th}
noFlex	1,356	0	918	105	0
someFlex	2,853	0	907	197	0
fullFlex	3,028	0	760	222	3,216
noFlex_d	3,077	2,183	1,723	485	0
someFlex_d	3,077	2,140	1,049	863	0
fullFlex_d	3,077	2,344	899	1,082	14,675

Table 5.3 shows the resulting new capacities. Additional PV capacity was installed in all non-REF scenarios. In contrast to the decarbonization scenarios, in the non-decarbonization scenarios the upper limit of 3,077 kW_P was not chosen. WTs were only selected in the decarbonization scenarios ranging from 2,140 kW_P to 2,344 kW_P. HPs were selected in all non-REF scenarios ranging from 760 kW_{th} in fullFlex to 1,723 kW_{th} in noFlex_d. P2Hs were built in all non-REF scenarios increasing from 105 kW_{th} in noFlex to 1,082 kW_{th} in fullFlex_d. TESs were optimal in fullFlex (3,216 kWh_{th}) and fullFlex_d (14,675 kWh_{th}). Whereas in fullFlex, the largest TES was built on the cooling temperature level, in fullFlex_d the largest was built on the process heat temperature level. No BES or H₂S was selected.

The annual balances for costs, carbon footprint, peak power, and energy streams of all scenarios and their deviations compared to noFlex and noFlex_d are displayed in Fig. 5.12.

In subfigures a) and b), it can be seen that adding flexibility reduces TACs and CEs. Specifically, someFlex has 10.4% less TACs and a 17.1% smaller carbon footprint than noFlex, and fullFlex has 11.7% less TACs and a 20.1% smaller carbon footprint than noFlex. In the decarbonization case (..._d), the TAC reductions were even more pronounced, with someFlex_d having 6.5% less and fullFlex_d having 15.0% less TACs than noFlex_d.

Subfigures c) and d) show that while someFlex has 67.4% higher CapEx, it has 19% lower OpEx than noFlex. Similarly, someFlex_d has 78% higher CapEx but 21.8% lower OpEx than noFlex_d. Interestingly, someFlex_d has lower CapEx and OpEx, while fullFlex_d has 6.5% higher CapEx and 26.7% lower OpEx than noFlex_d.

In subfigures e) and f), it can be seen that while the purchased electricity $W^{\text{EG,buy}}$ was comparable for all scenarios, the electricity purchase peak $\hat{P}^{\text{EG,buy}}$ in someFlex and fullFlex was reduced by over 50% compared to noFlex, and in someFlex_d and fullFlex_d by 24.2% and 54.9% respectively, compared to noFlex_d.

FIGURE 5.12: Annual results of the c_base context. **a)** Total annualized costs (TACs), **b)** operational CEs, **c)** OpEx, **d)** CapEx, **e)** electricity consumption (+) and supply (-), **f)** electricity purchase peaks, **g)** heat pump (HP) operation. **Note:** Percentages refer to noFlex or noFlex_d.

FIGURE 5.13: Pareto plots and decarbonization costs C_s^{decarb} for the three contexts. Note that the results of the non-decarbonization scenarios for c_{base} and c_{strict} are identical. Percentages are based on noFlex.

Subfigure g) shows that while in REF, the HP was only used in cooling mode, in the noFlex scenarios, the HP was also used for heating. In someFlex and someFlex_d, most of the cooling energy was used for heating, and in the fullFlex scenarios, this share was increased, so only a small fraction of the cooling energy is lost to well water.

Fig. E.5 shows the electricity balance for one week in May across all scenarios for c_{base} , as well as the day-ahead electricity price c_t^{elec} . In scenarios someFlex and fullFlex, the system switches from natural gas (CHP) to electricity (P2H) during periods of high PV supply. In all scenarios with flexibility, V2X activity can be seen in times of low PV and WT energy supply and/or high electricity prices. High activity levels of flexible loads (HP, P2H, BEV) can be seen during times of high PV and WT energy supply, and/or low electricity prices. In fullFlex_d, own renewable energy is almost entirely used and not fed-in. Comparing

fullFlex with noFlex, it can be seen how the profile of electricity being purchased from the grid is shaved.

Fig. E.3 presents the number of full V2X discharges per year. Interestingly, fullFlex and fullFlex_d feature less discharges than someFlex and someFlex_d.

Fig. 5.13a depicts the pareto plot and the decarbonization costs C_s^{decarb} for the c_base context. The figure shows that $C_{\text{someFlex}}^{\text{decarb}}$ was 2% and $C_{\text{fullFlex}}^{\text{decarb}}$ 19% lower than $C_{\text{noFlex}}^{\text{decarb}}$.

The additional flexibility is also leveraged for price-based and CEF-based DR, allowing optimization of electricity purchases against electricity prices and CEFs, respectively. The effectiveness of this approach is evaluated by the EWAP and EWACEF metrics, which are shown in Fig. 5.14a for all scenarios, in addition to the annual sum and peak of electricity purchases. It can be seen that with increasing flexibility, electricity purchase decreases in volume ($W^{\text{EG,buy}}$), peak ($\hat{P}^{\text{EG,buy}}$), carbon intensity (EWACEF), and price (EWAP), resulting in more cost-effective and environmentally friendly electricity purchases.

Furthermore, the graph reveals that the dark blue arrow (representing non-decarbonization scenarios) crosses the TWAP line, indicating that in someFlex and fullFlex, the EWAP is lower than the TWAP, while in noFlex, the EWAP is higher than the TWAP. This finding clearly demonstrates that the increased flexibility effectively reduced the average paid price (EWAP) below the average price (TWAP).

Fig. 5.15 shows the gradients of line_{TCER} and line_{ECER} in Fig. 5.14. As expected, the gradient in the decarbonization case is lower than in the non-decarbonization case.

5.3.2 Results of c_strict (strict decarbonization context)

The results of the c_strict context are shown in Figs. 5.13 to 5.17, E.1, E.2, E.4 and E.7 and Table E.2. They are summarized as follows:

In c_strict, the use of flexibility led to a 12% and 80% reduction in decarbonization costs for someFlex and fullFlex, respectively, compared to noFlex. This is shown in Fig. 5.13b. Even with a high carbon removal price of €10,000/t_{CO₂eq} in noFlex_d and someFlex_d, significant amounts of electricity-based CEs needed to be removed to achieve carbon neutrality, while in fullFlex_d carbon removal was not necessary, see Fig. 5.16b. This demonstrates that strict decarbonization without energy flexibility is infeasible, at least when the 2019 power plant mix is assumed.

In fullFlex_d, strict decarbonization was possible without carbon removal by investing in energy storage technologies, such as BES, TES, and H₂S, see Fig. E.7, Fig. 5.16b, and Table E.2. While the BES stored mainly solar energy for a few hours, the TES stored

FIGURE 5.14: Bubble plot of EWAP and EWACEF of purchased electricity for the three contexts. The dark blue and light blue arrows indicate the increase in flexibility for non-decarbonization and decarbonization scenarios, respectively. The solid gray lines inside the arrows connect noFlex and fullFlex and have the gradient $ECER_{fullFlex(_d), noFlex(_d)}$. The dashed and dotted lines indicate the context-independent TWAP and TWACEF, respectively. The bubble color corresponds to the peak electricity purchase power $\hat{P}^{EG, buy}$, while the bubble size represents the total electricity purchase volume $W^{EG, buy}$. Note that the results for the non-decarbonization scenarios of c_base and c_strict are identical.

FIGURE 5.15: Comparison of the gradients of the lines in Fig. 5.14. Top: Absolute gradients in €/tCO_{2eq} with TCER as comparison (i.e., gradient of line_{TCER} Fig. 5.14). Bottom: Gradients relative to TCER in %.

energy for a few days, and the H₂S stored energy for multiple days or weeks, see Fig. 5.17. The reason for this is H₂ storage chains (Elc, H₂S, FC) feature higher kW-costs and lower kWh-costs than BESs. Through the storage technologies (BES, TES, H₂S) the WT capacity of noFlex_d and someFlex_d can be reduced from over 19 MW_p to 5.3 MW_p, see Table E.2. By comparing Fig. 5.17 bottom and Fig. 5.6, it can be seen that the H₂S is completely discharged to cover several days of low solar and wind generation in the mid of July.

In Fig. 5.14b, the long blue arrow represents a broad range of EWAP and EWACEF values for the decarbonization scenarios. In noFlex_d and someFlex_d, the metrics (EWAP, EWACEF, $\hat{P}^{EG, buy}$, and $W^{EG, buy}$) showed only slight differences compared to c_{base}. However, in fullFlex_d, these metrics were significantly lower than in the other scenarios. This indicates that in fullFlex_d, the flexibility was not only utilized to optimize self-consumption and reduce electricity purchases but also to take advantage of lower electricity prices and CEFs.

The fullFlex_d scenario resulted in 71.9% fewer TACs than noFlex_d. Notably, through the use of flexibility, CapEx was reduced by 54.6%, primarily due to a lower WT capacity, and OpEx was reduced by 86.5%, mainly due to the avoidance of carbon removal costs.

5.3.3 Results of c_scaled (scaled electricity price context)

The results of the c_scaled context are shown in Figs. 5.13 to 5.15, 5.18, E.1, E.2, E.4 and E.8 and Table E.2.

FIGURE 5.16: Annual results of the c_strict context. **a)** Total annualized costs (TACs), **b)** operational CE, **c)** OpEx, **d)** CapEx, **e)** electricity consumption (+) and supply (-), **f)** electricity purchase peaks, **g)** heat pump (HP) operation. **Note:** Percentages refer to noFlex or noFlex_d.

FIGURE 5.17: Energy filling level of BES (top), 97/75-TES (middle), and H₂S (bottom) in scenario fullFlex_d of context c_strict.

In `c_scaled`, the decarbonization costs of `someFlex` were 2% and for `fullFlex` 37% lower than in `noFlex`, as shown in Fig. 5.13c. In contrast to `c_base`, in `c_scaled` a small BES was selected in `fullFlex` and the maximum possible PV capacity of 3.077 MW_p was chosen in the non-decarbonization scenarios (`noFlex`, `someFlex`, and `fullFlex`), as reported in Table E.2.

The TACs for the non-decarbonization scenarios were significantly lower compared to other contexts, even resulting in negative values for `someFlex` and `fullFlex`, as illustrated in Fig. 5.13c.

This implies that the company's MES combined with offshore WTs can be considered as a profitable business model with an internal return rate of over $r=10\%$, assuming the

FIGURE 5.18: Annual results of the *c_scaled* context. **a)** Total annualized costs (TACs), **b)** operational CE, **c)** OpEx, **d)** CapEx, **e)** electricity consumption (+) and supply (-), **f)** electricity purchase peaks, **g)** heat pump (HP) operation. **Note:** Percentages refer to noFlex or noFlex_d.

level and fluctuations of electricity prices in 2021 and the feasibility of WT installation. However, due to the limited maximum feed-in capacity of 20 MW, as shown in Fig. E.2, WT capacities between 19–22 MW_p were chosen (Table E.2), with most of the energy sold on the day-ahead market.

Adding flexibility to the system resulted in lower values for EWAP, EWACEF, $\hat{P}^{\text{EG, buy}}$, and $W^{\text{EG, buy}}$, as shown in Fig. 5.14c. The high WT capacities resulted in low levels of $W^{\text{EG, buy}}$ for all optimized scenarios compared to REF.

Moreover, Fig. 5.15 revealed that in `c_scaled`, the ECER were more than three times the TCER for both decarbonization and non-decarbonization cases. In other words, the modification of $P_t^{\text{EG, buy}}$ in `c_scaled` proportionately reduced more costs than carbon footprint.

5.3.4 Discussion of the results

When comparing all scenarios and contexts, the following results are striking:

1. In all contexts analyzed, the addition of flexibility resulted in significant reductions in both TACs and carbon footprint. TAC reductions ranged from 10.4 to 189.6%, although the latter figure was based on the already low TAC of €0.10M/yr in the `c_scaled noFlex` scenario. The second-highest relative TAC decrease occurred in the decarbonization case of `c_strict`, where `fullFlex_d` was the only scenario to achieve carbon neutrality without carbon removal since flexibility increased the self-consumption which eliminated the need for expensive carbon removal. While the `someFlex` scenarios showed 7.9–17.1% carbon footprint reductions compared to `noFlex`, the `fullFlex` scenarios showed 17.1–20.1%.
2. Investments in storage and bidirectional charging of industrial trucks in the `fullFlex` scenario led to a 19% reduction in decarbonization costs in `c_base` (assuming $c^{\text{DAC}} = \text{€}222/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2\text{eq}}$ and 2019 electricity prices). This reduction increased to 37% in `c_scaled` (assuming $c^{\text{DAC}} = \text{€}222/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2\text{eq}}$ and 2019 electricity prices scaled to 2021 levels), and further increased to 80% in `c_strict` (assuming $c^{\text{DAC}} = \text{€}10,000/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2\text{eq}}$ and 2019 electricity prices).
3. With current CEFs, the MES could technically only achieve strict Scope 1 and 2 net zero carbon footprint (`c_strict`) when using the full flexibility potential (`fullFlex_d`) of different mutually complementary energy storage technologies, one of them being H₂S which aligns with the results of Petkov and Gabrielli [133]. However, due to the high CapEx, it seems rather unrealistic, even if the full flexibility potential is considered. Assuming electricity grid decarbonization, as indirectly incorporated in

c_base and c_scaled through a significant price of €222/ t_{CO_2eq} for electricity-based CEs, full decarbonization appears feasible, particularly when factoring in the entire scope of flexibility potential. When comparing FULLFLEX_D to REF, TACs increased by 55% in C_BASE and decreased by 65% in C_SCALED . However, the economic benefits of C_SCALED primarily stem from wind power feed-in, as shown in Fig. E.2. In any circumstance, the results demonstrate that both the existing and the added flexibility through storage and sector coupling are highly valuable, particularly for decarbonization, and can be utilized for multiple purposes. These include price- and CEF-based DR, peak shaving, and self-consumption optimization.

4. In all cases, $\hat{P}^{EG,buy}$, $W^{EG,buy}$, π -rate, and ε -rate reduced with increasing flexibility (see Fig. E.1), i.e. price- and CEF-based DR is used together with peak shaving and self-consumption optimization. All scenarios, except the $c_strict_fullflex_d$, had an ε -rate over 100%, which means, the average accounted CEF (EWACEF) was higher than the average CEF (TWACEF). In the case of REF, the reason for this was the high electrical and thermal energy demand at business hours, where CEFs tend to be above average. REF and $noFlex_d$ for all contexts had π and ε -rates above 100%. This means their electricity purchase profiles were less market-serving than a flat load profile.

All the dark blue arrows in Fig. 5.14 crossed the TWAP line from above. This means by using flexibility in the non-decarbonization case, the π -rate decreased from above 100% to below 100%. In other words, the average paid price (EWAP) fell below the average price (TWAP).

5. The DR evaluation metrics proposed in Section 5.2.5.1 are simple, tangible, and useful for comparing and visualizing the intensity of price- and CEF-based DR in a meaningful way. As shown in Fig. 5.14, the results demonstrate the effectiveness of these metrics. The metrics EWAP and EWACEF are especially tangible since they have the same units as the prices and CEFs, respectively, and can be compared to the TWAP and TWACEF, respectively. The metrics π -rate and ε -rate stand out when comparing scenarios under different contexts, and are normalized to TWAP and TWACEF, respectively, making them independent of the level of prices and CEFs. However, when evaluating price- and CEF-based DR, it is important to consider $\hat{P}^{EG,buy}$ and $W^{EG,buy}$ to account for interactions with peak shaving and self-consumption optimization. Additionally, the TCER and ECER metrics measure the dominance of prices versus CEFs as a signal for DR and can be interpreted as gradients in a price-CEF diagram.
6. The results of c_scaled confirm the expectation that high and fluctuating electricity prices encourage the activation of existing flexibility and investments in vRESs and

energy storage systems. For instance, the V2X activity was found to be up to 2.7 times higher in `c_scaled` compared to `c_base` and `c_strict`. Specifically, `someFlex_d` in `c_scaled` had 498 full V2X discharges per year (1.36 per day), as shown in Fig. E.3. This indicates that energy shock scenarios similar to those experienced in 2022, which may not be rare in times of political instability, could be an opportunity for flexumers to realize value. Therefore, it would be interesting to quantify the value of being a flexumer in such price shock scenarios.

5.4 Conclusions

This chapter presents a comprehensive analysis of the value of flexibility in decarbonizing a production company's MES. The results indicate that the energy flexibility of a MES, enabled by storage and sector coupling, offers significant benefits for companies, especially when pursuing a net-zero carbon footprint. It can be used for multiple purposes, including price- and CEF-based DR, peak shaving, and self-consumption optimization. The results indicate that considering flexibility applications during the planning or retrofit stage of MESs could lead to reductions of 7%–190% in total cost and 8%–20% of operational carbon footprint. Decarbonization costs could be reduced by 19%–80% when aiming for a net-zero operational carbon footprint.

The findings also indicate that the MES could technically already achieve strict Scope 1 and 2 net zero carbon footprint when using the full flexibility potential of different mutually complementary energy storage technologies. Moreover, the chapter presented DR evaluation metrics that are simple, tangible, and useful for comparing and visualizing the intensity of price- and CEF-based DR. In the case study, they show that regardless of electricity prices and decarbonization ambitions, greener, cheaper, and less electricity is purchased when energy flexibility is used.

Overall, this chapter highlights the significant potential of energy flexibility in reducing costs, carbon footprint, and fossil fuel dependency for manufacturing companies. The results may provide insights for companies and organizations looking to decarbonize their energy systems. Additionally, these findings underscore the importance of taking into account future electricity price fluctuations, decarbonization goals, and the company's assessment of future carbon removal in the planning of sustainable MESs. Furthermore, this chapter demonstrates the multifaceted techno-economic interactions of modern sustainable MESs and, therefore, highlights the importance of integrated models for planning and flexibility potential evaluation. With the right tools and frameworks in place, manufacturers can better optimize their energy consumption, reduce their environmental impact, and achieve long-term sustainability goals.

Appendix: Detailed parameters and results. Appendix [E](#) provides detailed parameters and further results such as the nominal capacities of new technologies, heatmaps of purchased and sold electricity patterns, or Sankey diagrams of the annual energy sums.

Chapter 6

Electricity cost reduction potential of industrial processes using real-time pricing in a production planning problem

Abstract. Within this chapter, the author proposed a mixed-integer linear programming formulation for price-based demand response. This formulation, through the modeling of multiple machines, storage units, and types of production, is applicable not only for optimizing electricity purchases, thereby resulting in electricity cost savings, but also for addressing production planning problems. As a case study, the model is applied to the machine scheduling of two cement mills, comparing a time-of-use pricing scheme with a real-time pricing scheme. The optimization resulted in a 13% annual reduction in electricity costs for the two cement mills.

Acknowledgments. The contents of this chapter are based on the paper *Electricity Cost Reduction Potential of Industrial Processes using Real Time Pricing in a Production Planning Problem* [285]. Markus Fleschutz is the primary author of this paper. This publication has been produced within the context of the Interflex4Climate project which is funded by the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety of the Federal Republic of Germany (BMUB) as part of the National Climate Initiative.

6.1 Overview and context

PBDR programs, such as RTP, wherein an energy consumer responds to hourly price signals, requires load control infrastructure, communication technology, and market access. Nevertheless, particularly energy-intensive companies are well-equipped to meet these challenges. Moreover, compared to other sectors, the industrial sector offers greater savings potential due to their substantial electricity demand.

Based on the literature review in Chapter 2, prior research in the field of electricity cost management has primarily focused on broad strategies for energy efficiency and conservation, with limited emphasis on the intricacies of production planning in relation to dynamic electricity pricing. While some studies have touched upon the potential of load shifting and DR, there remains a significant gap in applying these concepts specifically to production planning in industrial settings. This gap is particularly evident in the context of optimizing electrical load curves in response to hourly electricity pricing, a critical aspect for energy-intensive industries seeking cost-effective and sustainable operations.

In this chapter, the author proposes a production planning model aimed at reducing companies' electricity costs and contributing to a reliable electricity system. This is achieved by optimizing the shape of the companies' electrical load curve in response to hourly price signals. By serving a forecasted demand for finished or intermediate products and adhering to technical, production-technological, and process-related constraints, the model strategically shifts machine load to hours with lower electricity prices.

6.2 Materials and methods

For the sake of simplicity, the model comprises only those components of a production process that are most relevant for DR. As outlined in Fig. 6.1, there are two types of storages: The α -storage stores the semi-finished goods in order to decouple the process under investigation from the pre-process. Since the author accounts for only one raw material for the observed process there is also only one instance of α -storage. There are a number of n β -storages that store the n different sorts of finished goods. There are a number of k machines that can produce every sort. However, not more than one sort can be produced per time step and machine.

FIGURE 6.1: Schematic representation of DR-relevant components and its connections through flow of electricity and goods.

6.2.1 Mathematical modeling

The problem is formulated as a MILP problem. Thereby the combinatorial problem assigning the sorts to the machines can be formulated using binary decision variables while global optimality within acceptable computation time is ensured due to linear formulation. Furthermore, the model relies on a perfect foresight modeling approach in order to keep the model solvable. All optimization variables are indicated in bold and are non-negative continuous variables if not stated otherwise.

The objective function consists of the minimization of the operation costs C^{op} caused by the process under investigation

$$\text{minimize } C^{\text{op}} = \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (C_t^{\text{el}} + C_t^{\text{SU}}) \quad (6.1)$$

with the electricity costs

$$C^{\text{el}} = \mathbf{E}_t^{\text{el}} c_t \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (6.2)$$

and the costs for machine start-ups

$$C_t^{\text{SU}} = c^{\text{SU}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \mathbf{Y}_{t,m}^{\text{SU}} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (6.3)$$

where $t \in \mathcal{T}$ are the time steps, and $m \in \mathcal{M}$ the machines. \mathbf{E}_t^{el} is the hourly electricity demand in MWh/h, c_t the corresponding electricity price in €/MWh, c^{SU} the cost per start-up, and $\mathbf{Y}_{t,m}^{\text{SU}}$ the binary start-up indicator.

The optimization problem is subject to the following constraints, which derive from the abovementioned boundary conditions:

- The balance of electrical energy demand of the machines

$$\mathbf{E}_t^{\text{el}} = \Delta t \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \mathbf{Y}_{t,s,m}^{\text{op}} p_m^{\text{el,max}} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (6.4)$$

where Δt is the time step width in hours (here: 1 hour); $s \in \mathcal{S}$ are the sorts; $p_m^{\text{el,max}}$ is the maximum electrical power demand of machine m ; and $\mathbf{Y}_{t,s,m}^{\text{op}}$ is the binary operation indicator which is defined through a Big-M formulation

$$\dot{\mathbf{G}}_{t,s,m}^{\text{p}} \leq \mathbf{Y}_{t,s,m}^{\text{op}} w \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S}, m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (6.5)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{G}}_{t,s,m}^{\text{p}}$ is the produced product flow and w is a sufficiently large number.

- The limit of production volume on machine m per time step t

$$\dot{\mathbf{G}}_{t,s,m}^{\text{p}} \leq \mathbf{Y}_{t,s,m}^{\text{op}} \frac{p_m^{\text{el,max}}}{\xi_s^{\text{el}}} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S}, m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (6.6)$$

where ξ_s^{el} is the sort-specific electricity demand.

- The production restriction of only one sort per machine and time step

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \mathbf{Y}_{t,s,m}^{\text{op}} \leq 1 \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (6.7)$$

- The balance of β -storage

$$\mathbf{SOC}_{t,s}^{\beta} = \mathbf{SOC}_{t-1,s}^{\beta} + \Delta t \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \dot{\mathbf{G}}_{t,s,m}^{\text{p}} - \Delta t \dot{\mathbf{G}}_{t,s}^{\text{dem}} \quad \forall t \in \{\mathcal{T} \setminus t_0\}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (6.8)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{G}}_{t,s}^{\text{dem}}$ are the demanded product flows, $\mathbf{SOC}_{t,s}^{\beta}$ are the filling levels of the β -storages that are pre-defined for the first and last time step

$$\mathbf{SOC}_{t,s}^{\beta} = \Phi_s^{\beta,\text{init}} \quad \forall t \in \{t_0, t_{|\mathcal{T}|}\}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (6.9)$$

and restricted by the limits $\Phi_s^{\beta,\text{min}}$ and $\Phi_s^{\beta,\text{cap}}$.

$$\Phi_s^{\beta,\text{min}} \leq \mathbf{SOC}_{t,s}^{\beta} \leq \Phi_s^{\beta,\text{cap}} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (6.10)$$

- The definition of the start-up and shut-down indicators $\mathbf{Y}_{t,s,m}^{\text{SU}}$ and $\mathbf{Y}_{t,s,m}^{\text{SD}}$.

$$\mathbf{Y}_{t_0,s,m}^{\text{SU}} - \mathbf{Y}_{t_0,s,m}^{\text{SD}} = 0 \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (6.11)$$

$$\mathbf{Y}_{t_0,s,m}^{\text{SU}} - \mathbf{Y}_{t_0,s,m}^{\text{SD}} = y_{t_0,s,m}^{\text{op}} - y_{t_0-1,s,m}^{\text{op}} \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (6.12)$$

- The restriction that a machine cannot start up and shut down in the same time step

$$\mathbf{Y}_{t,s,m}^{\text{SU}} + \mathbf{Y}_{t,s,m}^{\text{SD}} \leq 1 \quad \forall t \in \{\mathcal{T} \setminus t_0\}, s \in \mathcal{S}, m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (6.13)$$

- The restriction to a minimum up and downtime $\tau^{\min\text{UT}} / \tau^{\min\text{DT}}$

$$\sum_{q=t-\tau^{\min\text{UT}}+1}^t \mathbf{Y}_{q,s,m}^{\text{SU}} \leq \mathbf{Y}_{t,s,m}^{\text{OP}} \quad \forall [\tau^{\min,\text{UT}}..t^{\text{end}}], s \in \mathcal{S}, m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (6.14)$$

$$\sum_{q=t-\tau^{\min\text{DT}}+1}^t \mathbf{Y}_{q,s,m}^{\text{SD}} \leq 1 - \mathbf{Y}_{t,s,m}^{\text{OP}} \quad \forall [\tau^{\min,\text{UT}}..t^{\text{end}}], s \in \mathcal{S}, m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (6.15)$$

where q is a subset of \mathcal{T} .

6.3 Results – Cement Case Study

Within a case study, the model is applied to the cement milling process of a cement plant with 9 sorts of cement (product types), two cement mills with 2.5 MW of installed electric power each and a minimum up-time of 2 hours (see Fig. 6.2). Two different pricing schemes are compared: A TOU pricing scheme, which includes peak and off-peak rates, and an RTP pricing scheme, which uses hourly day-ahead market price signals. The pre-process involves the raw mill, the α -storage refers to the clinker storage, and the β -storages are the cement storages.

FIGURE 6.2: Case study cement milling process: Schematic representation of adopted DR model (DR-relevant components and its connections through flow of electricity and goods).

Anonymized data of the year 2015 from a German cement plant are used for TOU electricity prices, production and storage capacities, and cement demand. Fig. 6.3 shows the seasonal distribution of the cement demand over all cement sorts. With the cement demand peaking in summer, it qualitatively fits with the annual course of PV generation (compare to Fig. 6.4).

The problem with 8760 time steps was solved using Gurobi 7.0.0 on a server computer (12 x 2.40 GHz CPU and 126 GB available RAM) within one hour. Fig. 6.5 presents the results of the MILP for both pricing schemes over one week (168 hourly time steps). It shows the electricity demand and the sorts produced at a time for both cement mills. The week

FIGURE 6.3: Total cement demand over all sorts.

FIGURE 6.4: Annual distribution of PV electricity generation in Germany in 2016. Data from [302].

FIGURE 6.5: Comparison of machine scheduling between TOU and RTP. TOU peak hours are on business days from 8:00 to 20:00.

includes a public holiday on May 1st and a weekend. With the change from a TOU-based to an RTP-based machine scheduling, the resulting electrical loads are shifted from RTP peak hours to RTP off-peak hours. The graph shows that the TOU-based production program differs significantly from the RTP-based production program during the noon hours of business days and in times when RTP peaks coincide with the off-peak times of the TOU scheme (e.g., Saturday night).

The Figs. 6.6 and 6.7 show the results of the MILP for one year (8760 time steps) as heatmaps. The upper heatmaps display the pricing scheme, while the lower heatmaps show

FIGURE 6.6: Peak/off-peak price scheme (top) and according optimized machine scheduling (bottom).

FIGURE 6.7: Day-ahead electricity prices (top) and according optimized machine scheduling (bottom).

FIGURE 6.8: Difference between the RTP and TOU pricing scheme (top) and difference between the according optimized production plans (bottom).

the electricity demand of both cement mills according to the optimized production plan.

Fig. 6.8 shows the differences between both the pricing schemes and the corresponding production plans. In the lower heatmap, the load shifts from the TOU (purple) to the RTP production plan (green) are illustrated. Over the entire year, 5.8 GWh are shifted to times of with lower day-ahead market prices, which accounts for 25% of the annual energy consumption.

For this case study, an hourly resolved optimization over one year resulted in an electricity cost reduction of 13% for the analyzed process.

6.4 Conclusion and outlook

Within this chapter, a MILP formulation for price-based DR was proposed and applied to a cement plant. Through integrated modeling of multiple machines and sorts, the formulation can be used as basis for dynamic machine scheduling.

The results revealed that by activating an RTP-based DR program in the industrial sector, 25% of the energy could be shifted in a market-friendly way into times with low spot market prices and high shares of vRESs, without violating product-technical requirements. This approach creates a win-win situation. On one hand, the flexibility of industrial processes can be used cost-effectively for the integration of vRESs. On the other hand, energy costs for industrial companies can be lowered.

Chapter 7

Industrial grid fees vs. demand response: A case study of a multi-use battery in a German chemical plant

Abstract. Industrial DR is indispensable for providing operational flexibility to the electricity grid and for integrating the increasing shares of fluctuating renewable energy sources. In Germany and other countries, however, investments and the activation of operational flexibility are inhibited by regulatory systems that were not designed for the renewable energy era but instead, the fossil energy era. Two examples are fixed peak-demand grid fees (FGFs) and the intensive grid usage (IGU) of the Electricity Network Fee Regulation Ordinance in Germany. This chapter, therefore, analyzes to what extent the necessary expansion of industrial price-based DR is hampered by FGFs and IGU using a real-world industrial case study. For this, a design and operation optimization model of a local energy system including a photovoltaic system (PVS) and a multi-use battery energy storage system (BESS) is parametrized with anonymized data of a German chemical plant. The results show that FGFs and IGU hinder the provision of market-serving operational flexibility since flat demand profiles are rewarded. Under current market conditions, FGF and IGU provide investment incentives for BESS but discourage investment in PVSs. For BESS prices of €100/kWh and below, FGFs and IGU even impede investments in BESSs.

Acknowledgments. The contents of this chapter are based on the paper *Industrial grid fees vs. demand response: A case study of a multi-use battery in a German chemical plant* [303]. Markus Fleschutz is the primary author of this paper. This work was conducted in the context of the project WIN4climate, funded by the German Federal Ministry for

Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK) (No. 67KF0094A). It was additionally funded by the MTU Risam Scholarship Scheme.

7.1 Overview and context

Industrial DR plays a vital role in compensating the fluctuating feed-in of increasing renewable energy shares by activating demand-side flexibility [59, 304]. However, in Germany and other European countries, the necessary expansion of industrial DR is hampered by the structure of current electricity network fees. Examples from Germany are the FGFs and the Electricity Network Fee Regulation Ordinance that provides individual network charges for intensive grid usage (IGU) which rewards high and uniform consumption behavior of industrial electricity consumers and therefore inhibits the activation of flexibility [34, 305]. Vallés et al. [306] recommend cost-reflective network tariff structures such as capacity charges and dynamic tariffs.

The technical capabilities of modern Li-Ion battery technologies allow one BESS to be used for multiple flexibility applications [307, 308]. The stacking of different values can open up further revenue sources and improve the economic potential of a BESS [309]. Despite significantly decreasing prices for Li-Ion BESSs, a BESS may even be economically infeasible if it is only used for one application [310]. As there are several BESS applications that are mostly combinable, many of the combinations have not yet been scientifically investigated [311].

Based on the literature review presented in Chapter 2, the literature lacks studies that analyze how much flexibility remains unused as a result of the structure of current electricity network fees. Therefore, this chapter quantifies the economical flexibility potential that is hampered by FGFs and IGU within a representative case study of an industrial chemical plant in Germany. Therein, linear programming is applied to optimize the design and operation of a local industrial energy system considering a stationary Li-Ion BESS and a PVS. Multiple scenarios investigate investment incentives for BESSs and PVSs and how market rules affect the provision of flexibility. In different scenarios, multiple flexibility applications namely peak shaving, IGU optimization, and energy arbitrage are considered with and without FGF and assuming different BESS prices. For each scenario, the costs and carbon footprint of the electricity consumption and the optimal BESS and PVS designs is compared. Finally, Pearson correlation coefficients between the purchased electricity and day-ahead market prices as well as CEFs are calculated.

The remainder of this chapter is organized as follows. In Section 7.2, the problem is formulated and the data described. Section 7.2.3 describes the analyzed scenarios of

the case study. The results are presented in Section 7.3 before conclusions are drawn in Section 7.4.

7.2 Materials and methods

The calculations were conducted using DRAF, described in Chapter 4.

7.2.1 Model

The model is a linear program which is described in the following. All optimization variables are indicated in bold and are non-negative continuous variables. Time steps are denoted with $t \in \mathcal{T}$.

7.2.1.1 Objective Function

The objective function of the linear program is to minimize the **TAC** which consists of the operating costs for the first year \mathbf{C}^{op} , the repair, maintenance, and inspection (RMI) costs for the first year \mathbf{C}^{RMI} , and the annualized investment costs $\mathbf{C}^{\text{invAnn}}$:

$$\text{minimize } \mathbf{TAC} = \mathbf{C}^{\text{op}} + \mathbf{C}^{\text{RMI}} + \mathbf{C}^{\text{invAnn}} \quad (7.1)$$

with

$$\mathbf{C}^{\text{op}} = \mathbf{C}^{\text{EG, buy}} + \mathbf{C}^{\text{EG, peak}} \quad (7.2)$$

$$\mathbf{C}^{\text{RMI}} = k^{\text{BES, RMI}} \mathbf{C}^{\text{BES, inv}} + k^{\text{PV, RMI}} \mathbf{C}^{\text{PV, inv}} \quad (7.3)$$

$$\mathbf{C}^{\text{invAnn}} = a(r, N^{\text{BES}}) \mathbf{C}^{\text{BES, inv}} + a(r, N^{\text{PV}}) \mathbf{C}^{\text{PV, inv}} \quad (7.4)$$

where $a(r, N^i) = \frac{r(1+r)^{N^i}}{(1+r)^{N^i} - 1}$ is the annuity factor of component i as function of the calculatory interest rate r and the operation life N^i in years. Operating CEs are not part of the objective function but are quantified as

$$\mathbf{CE} = \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \varepsilon_t^{\text{EG}} \mathbf{P}_t^{\text{EG, buy}}. \quad (7.5)$$

7.2.1.2 Constraints

Electricity balance. The electricity balance ensures that the power sources (EG, PV, and BESS discharge) equal the power sinks (BES charging and fixed electrical demand).

$$\mathbf{P}_t^{\text{EG,buy}} + \mathbf{P}_t^{\text{PV}} + \mathbf{P}_t^{\text{BES,out}} = \mathbf{P}_t^{\text{BES,in}} + \mathbf{P}_t^{\text{dem}} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (7.6)$$

Electricity grid (EG). Eq. (7.7) calculates the total cost of buying electrical energy where the purchased electricity per time step is weighted with a time-dependent and a fixed price component. Eq. (7.8) defines the power-related electricity costs while Eq. (7.9) ensures the peak power, $\mathbf{P}^{\text{EG,peak}}$, to be the highest power drawn from the EG of the year. The time step width Δt is 0.25 hours. The value of k^{igu} is 0.2 if IGU is considered and 1.0 otherwise. Electricity cannot be sold to the EG.

$$\mathbf{C}^{\text{EG,buy}} = \Delta t \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (c_t^{\text{EG}} + c^{\text{EG,addon}}) \mathbf{P}_t^{\text{EG,buy}} \quad (7.7)$$

$$\mathbf{C}^{\text{EG,peak}} = k^{\text{igu}} c^{\text{EG,peak}} \mathbf{P}^{\text{EG,peak}} \quad (7.8)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_t^{\text{EG,buy}} \leq \mathbf{P}^{\text{EG,peak}} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (7.9)$$

Photovoltaic (PV). See Appendix D.2.5.

Battery energy storage (BES). See Appendix D.2.3.

7.2.2 Data for the case study

General. All data were sourced in Germany during the year 2020. Time series were prepared in quarter-hourly resolution. A calculatory interest rate r of 6% was assumed.

Electricity demand. A quarter-hourly resolved electricity demand of a company in a German chemical park was used. For data protection reasons, the load profile was slightly modified in amplitude and multiplied by a low level of white noise. Through this, the load profile was adjusted to have less than 7,000 full load hours to create the incentives for IGU optimization.

Electricity grid (EG). Electricity day-ahead market prices were used for c_t^{EG} . Dynamic electricity XEFs were used for $\varepsilon_t^{\text{EG}}$ to calculate the CEs for each scenario. In both cases,

the data were accessed using the Python package Elmada [261] described in Chapter 3. The value of $c^{\text{EG,addon}}$ is €0.06228/kWh.

Photovoltaic system (PVS). PVS power production time series for a flat roof were calculated via the GSEE tool [276] based on historical air temperature and solar radiation data from the German Meteorological Service (DWD) weather stations 4177 and 5906 located in Mannheim and Rheinstetten, respectively. Arbitrarily chosen reference coordinates (latitude = 49.013, longitude = 8.392) were used to calculate the position of the sun. An available flat roof area of 8,000 m² for PVS and a specific space requirement of 6.5 m²/kW_p was assumed, which resulted in a theoretically possible PVS peak power of 1.23 MW_p. Other parameters were: $c^{\text{PV,inv}} = \text{€}460/\text{kW}_p$, $N^{\text{PV}} = 25$ years, $k^{\text{PV,RMI}} = 2\%$.

Battery energy storage system (BESS). For the BESS, specific investment costs $c^{\text{BES,inv}}$ of €720/kWh_{el} (default), €300/kWh_{el}, €200/kWh_{el}, and €100/kWh_{el} were assumed. Other parameters were: $\eta^{\text{BES,time}} = 99.998/\text{h}$, $\eta^{\text{BES,dis/ch}} = 97.468\%$, $N^{\text{BES}} = 20$ years, $k^{\text{BES,in/outpercap}} = 0.7$, $k^{\text{BES,ini}} = 0$, $k^{\text{BES,RMI}} = 2\%$. The sources and further descriptions for most of the parameters can be found in Chapter 4.

7.2.3 Analyzed scenarios

TABLE 7.1: Definition of main scenarios

Scenario name	BESS allowed	PVS allowed	IGU enforced
REF	no	no	no
BES	yes	no	no
PV	no	yes	no
BES_PV	yes	yes	no
BES_PV_IGU	yes	yes	yes

Five main scenarios were modeled that are defined in Table 7.1. In addition to the default BESS price of €720/kWh, the scenario variants BES300, BES200, and BES100 are defined with BESS prices of €300/kWh, €200/kWh, and €100/kWh, respectively. These main scenarios were further divided into FGF and no grid fee (NGF). Fixed peak-demand grid fees were assumed to be €100/kW_p for the eleven FGF scenarios and €0/kW_p for the NGF scenarios.

7.3 Results

The problems have been solved to global optimality using Gurobi 9.5 solver through the Python interface. Figs. 7.1, 7.2, 7.3, 7.4 and 7.5 present the results of the 18 analyzed case study scenarios. Fig. 7.1 gives an overview of the resulting effects on $P_t^{\text{EG, buy}}$ (a, b, d), the costs and CE (c), and the underlying optimal PVS and BESS capacities (e). Fig. 7.2 shows the distribution of $P_t^{\text{EG, buy}}$. It can be seen that the minima of $P_t^{\text{EG, buy}}$ vary by more than 1 MW while the medians stay within the range of 0.5 MW. In the FGF scenarios with specific BESS prices of €300/kWh or lower, a clear cut of the upper tail of the load curve can be observed. Fig. 7.4 presents the TAC components. What stands out is that in all scenarios, energy cost for purchased electricity was the largest TAC component followed by grid fee and CapEx for PVS. Reduced grid fees can be clearly seen in the IGU scenarios. Fig. 7.3 shows the effect on TAC and CEs and some economical performance indicators in an annotated heatmap. To facilitate the comparison of comparable scenarios, Fig. 7.5 additionally shows the results of Fig. 7.1 grouped by assumed specific BESS price. Note that the TAC reduction is not plotted in Fig. 7.5, since FGF-REF and NGF-REF have different TACs, see Fig. 7.4, so the reductions are not comparable.

The following observations of these results are striking:

1. The maximum PVS capacity (dotted yellow line) is the optimal PVS capacity for all scenarios where a PVS was allowed except for the scenario BES_PV_IGU_FGF where an 838 kW_p PVS was chosen instead of a 1231 kW_p. This corresponds to a reduction in the optimal capacity of 32%.
2. For BESS prices of €200/kWh or higher, the optimal BESS capacity in the IGU case is higher than in the case without IGU. However, for a BESS price of €100/kWh, the reverse is true.
3. The IGU scenarios have the highest TAC savings.
4. In all FGF scenarios where a BESS was selected, the peak load is reduced compared to REF.
5. BES100_PV is the only scenario where the peak power increased compared to REF.
6. Only the BES100 scenarios show optimal BESS capacities of more than 1 MWh.
7. In the FGF case, a BESS is selected in all scenarios where a BESS is allowed.
8. Although, in the NGF case, a BESS is selected in only one scenario (BES100_PV_IGU), it has the largest dimensioning among all scenarios, and the peak power is increased by 70%.

FIGURE 7.1: Results of the FGF (top) and the NGF (bottom) scenarios. The columns are: **a)** Pearson correlation coefficient of purchased electricity $P_t^{\text{EG, buy}}$ with electricity prices c_t , carbon emission factors $\varepsilon_t^{\text{EG}}$, and onsite PVS generation P_t^{PV} , respectively; **b)** Average deviation of $P_t^{\text{EG, buy}}$ between a given scenario and REF; **c)** Percentage reductions of total annualized cost (TAC) and carbon emissions (CE) based on REF; **d)** Percentage change of peak power P^{peak} and full load hours t^{use} based on REF; **e)** Capacities of BESS (in MWh) and PVS (in MW_p). PVS capacity limit (1.23 MW_p) indicated as yellow dotted line.

FIGURE 7.2: Violin plots showing the distribution of $P_t^{\text{EG, buy}}$

	Total annualized		Absolute savings		Relative savings		C_inv	C_invAnn	C_op	EAC	PP	DPP	IRR
	Costs	Emissions	Costs	Emissions	Costs	Emissions							
FGF													
REF	1,805 k€	6,264 t	0 k€	0 t	0.00%	0.00%	0 k€	0 k€/a	1,805 k€/a	nan €/t	nan a	nan a	nan%
BES	1,805 k€	6,264 t	0 k€	0 t	0.00%	0.00%	0 k€	0 k€/a	1,805 k€/a	-171 €/t	0.0 a	0.0 a	nan%
PV	1,742 k€	5,928 t	63 k€	336 t	3.48%	5.37%	566 k€	44 k€/a	1,687 k€/a	-187 €/t	5.3 a	6.5 a	19.5%
BES_PV	1,742 k€	5,928 t	63 k€	336 t	3.48%	5.37%	566 k€	44 k€/a	1,687 k€/a	-187 €/t	5.3 a	6.5 a	19.5%
BES300_PV	1,742 k€	5,928 t	63 k€	336 t	3.48%	5.37%	566 k€	44 k€/a	1,687 k€/a	-187 €/t	5.3 a	6.5 a	19.5%
BES200_PV	1,742 k€	5,928 t	63 k€	336 t	3.48%	5.37%	566 k€	44 k€/a	1,687 k€/a	-187 €/t	5.3 a	6.5 a	19.5%
BES100_PV	1,741 k€	5,757 t	64 k€	507 t	3.53%	8.09%	857 k€	70 k€/a	1,655 k€/a	-126 €/t	6.4 a	8.4 a	15.6%
NGF													
REF	2,083 k€	6,264 t	0 k€	0 t	0.00%	0.00%	0 k€	0 k€/a	2,083 k€/a	nan €/t	nan a	nan a	nan%
BES	2,083 k€	6,259 t	0 k€	5 t	0.02%	0.08%	69 k€	6 k€/a	2,075 k€/a	-64 €/t	10.9 a	18.1 a	7.3%
PV	2,020 k€	5,928 t	63 k€	336 t	3.02%	5.37%	566 k€	44 k€/a	1,965 k€/a	-187 €/t	5.3 a	6.5 a	19.5%
BES_PV	2,020 k€	5,918 t	63 k€	346 t	3.05%	5.52%	695 k€	56 k€/a	1,950 k€/a	-183 €/t	5.8 a	7.4 a	17.4%
BES300_PV	2,012 k€	5,919 t	71 k€	345 t	3.43%	5.51%	620 k€	49 k€/a	1,950 k€/a	-207 €/t	5.1 a	6.3 a	20.0%
BES200_PV	2,008 k€	5,907 t	75 k€	358 t	3.61%	5.71%	644 k€	51 k€/a	1,944 k€/a	-210 €/t	5.1 a	6.3 a	20.2%
BES100_PV	1,992 k€	5,787 t	91 k€	477 t	4.37%	7.62%	843 k€	68 k€/a	1,907 k€/a	-191 €/t	5.3 a	6.5 a	19.5%
BES_PV_IGU	1,830 k€	6,022 t	253 k€	242 t	12.13%	3.87%	552 k€	45 k€/a	1,775 k€/a	-1,043 €/t	1.9 a	2.0 a	55.8%
BES300_PV_IGU	1,809 k€	5,892 t	274 k€	373 t	13.17%	5.95%	769 k€	62 k€/a	1,731 k€/a	-736 €/t	2.3 a	2.5 a	45.5%
BES200_PV_IGU	1,802 k€	5,893 t	281 k€	371 t	13.50%	5.92%	701 k€	56 k€/a	1,732 k€/a	-758 €/t	2.1 a	2.3 a	50.0%
BES100_PV_IGU	1,794 k€	5,875 t	289 k€	390 t	13.87%	6.22%	672 k€	53 k€/a	1,727 k€/a	-741 €/t	2.0 a	2.1 a	52.9%

FIGURE 7.3: Results of the FGF (top) and the NGF (bottom) scenarios as an annotated heatmap. Legend: **C_inv**: investment costs, **C_invAnn**: annualized investment costs, **C_op**: operating costs, **EAC**: emissions avoidance costs, **PP**: static payback period, **DPP**: discounted payback period, **IRR**: internal rate of return for 15 years. For DPP and IRR, a 6% discount rate was assumed.

FIGURE 7.4: Total annualized cost (TAC) components

FIGURE 7.5: Case study results grouped by BESS prices

9. A negative correlation between the purchased electricity and the electricity prices can only be observed in BES100 scenarios.
10. The lowest operational CEs occur in the BES100_PV scenario of the NGF case closely followed by the same scenario of the FGF case.
11. The operational CEs in BES_PV_IGU_FGF are lower than in BES_PV_FGF and in BES_PV_NGF. This holds for BESS prices of €720/kWh and €100/kWh, but not for BESS prices of €300/kWh and €200/kWh.

For the particular case in this chapter the following statements can be made based on the observations above:

- From 1): PVSs are economical even without BESSs. IGU reduces the optimal PVS capacity by 32% with current BESS prices of €720/kWh. For lower BESS prices, IGU does not reduce the optimal PVS capacity.
- From 2): IGU increases the optimal BESS capacity for BESS prices of €200/kWh or higher.
- From 7): A BESS is economical due to peak shaving.

- From 5) and 9): Peak shaving through FGF is a stronger incentive than the possibilities of energy arbitrage through spot market optimization.
- From 4), 7), and 8): Energy arbitrage as a single BESS use is uneconomical for prices of €200/kWh or higher.
- From 10): Load flexibility can help to reduce the operational CE footprint when dynamic CEFs are used.
- From 9) and 11): IGU imposes little impediment to the investment in and the activation of market-serving and emission-reducing demand-side flexibility at BESS prices and electricity prices for the year 2020. However, at low BESS prices of approximately €100/kWh, market-serving and emission-reducing behavior is strongly inhibited by the incentives of IGU. The same is expected to be true for more volatile electricity prices with higher daily price spreads, however, this scenario was not analyzed within this thesis.

7.4 Conclusions

This chapter analyzed how FGFs and IGU hinder the usage of industrial demand-side flexibility for the integration of renewable energy sources. For this, the design and operation of a local energy system of an energy-intensive industrial company was optimized including a BESS and a PVS, and showed the results of 18 different model configurations. The results show that in certain circumstances, IGU and FGFs hinder the investment in PVSs. Regarding flexibility, IGU and FGFs incentivize BESSs but hinder the usage of its flexibility to support the market and to help integrate renewable energy sources. And when BESS prices are low enough to make energy arbitrage economical for companies, the IGU also inhibits investments in BESSs. The results provide key insights into the economic interrelationships of different incentives, such as spot market prices, FGFs, and IGU from the perspective of an industrial electricity consumer.

In this chapter, demand-side flexibility was considered using a BESS as flexibility source. However, similar results are expected for flexible loads, which sometimes are referred to as virtual batteries, knowing that they tend to have more technical and production restrictions than BESSs which are built specifically to store electrical energy. The results can be transferred to other IGU companies to a certain extent, since IGU is only applicable to companies with a relatively uniform load, which excludes striking load patterns and an electricity demand of more than 10 GWh/a.

On the one hand, the results show that IGU and FGFs can provide investment incentives for BESSs, which can also be used to alter the grid-purchased electricity profile to optimize

self-consumption and engage in energy arbitrage. On the other hand, the results also show that IGU reduces investment incentives for on-site PVSs and that the FGFs hinder the provision of operational flexibility to the electricity grid.

Chapter 8

Impact of landing interruptions on the optimal design and operation of green hydrogen hubs

Abstract. This chapter investigated the implications of landing interruptions in the optimal design of a green hydrogen (H_2) and ammonia import hub that includes energy conversion and storage systems. A mixed-integer linear program is proposed to optimize the H_2 hub's design and operation considering ammonia and H_2 storage systems, ammonia cracker, proton-exchange-membrane electrolyzer with excess heat utilization and relevant factors such as demand variability and energy prices. Next, the model is applied to the case study of an H_2 import hub in Karlsruhe, Germany comparing scenarios with and without landing interruptions. According to the results, a hub that is not explicitly designed to handle landing interruptions could only meet 47% of the demand during the time of the interrupted landing. Moreover, the findings demonstrate that the consideration of landing interruptions significantly influenced the optimal design, albeit resulting in a marginal increase of only 0.8% in total annualized costs.

Acknowledgments. The contents of this chapter are based on the accepted paper *Industrial grid fees vs. demand response: A case study of a multi-use battery in a German chemical plant* [312]. Markus Fleschutz is the primary author of this paper. This work was performed as part of the MeSSO Research Group at the Munster Technological University (MTU) and in relation to the project H2iPort KA MOD funded by the Ministry of the Environment, Climate Protection and the Energy Sector Baden-Württemberg. It was additionally funded by the MTU Risam Scholarship Scheme. Fig. 8.1 uses icons from flaticon.com.

8.1 Overview and context

Green hydrogen (H_2) will play a crucial role in the global transition to carbon-neutral energy. H_2 can be converted into derivatives such as ammonia (NH_3) to increase volumetric energy density for storage and transport [313]. Production costs for green NH_3 are expected to decrease to €370–450/t by 2030 [314]. Consequently, H_2 import hubs are gaining attention especially in areas with no access to H_2 pipeline systems. These hubs might include systems for energy storage, energy conversion, and onsite vRES-based H_2 generation to increase flexibility and exploit synergy effects, as shown in Fig. 8.1. However, climate change increases the probability of extreme river water levels, which cause landing interruptions due to unsafe shipping. Such landing interruptions can impact the design and operation of these hubs. If not considered in the design phase of an H_2 import hub, landing interruptions can lead to unmet demands and, as a consequence, to unpredictable high follow-up costs. To ensure stable electricity systems and secure provision of clean energy, understanding how these landing interruptions change the optimal design of H_2 import hubs is essential. This chapter fills a literature gap by exploring the implications of such landing interruptions on the design and operation of an H_2 import hub. More specifically, it is analyzed how the optimal design and operation of the conversion and storage technologies of an H_2 import hub at a river change if a two-week landing interruption is considered due to low water levels. For this purpose, a MILP model is proposed to determine the cost-optimal design and operation of these technologies and apply it to a case study in Karlsruhe, Germany.

Egerer et al. [315] examined the potential of green NH_3 as an H_2 carrier in global energy trade and presented an optimization model for assessing the cost-effective and scalable trade of green NH_3 . The model was applied to a case study of large-scale NH_3 import from Australia to Germany in 2030 and showed that green NH_3 can be cost-competitive with gray NH_3 if CO_2 prices are high enough. D’Amore-Domenech et al. [316] compared three green H_2 sea transport options: submarine H_2 pipelines, liquid H_2 shipping, and compressed H_2 shipping. Their conclusion was that for mass flows of less than $100 \text{ kt}_{H_2}/\text{yr}$ and distances of 800–2,500 km, compressed H_2 shipping was the most cost-effective option. In [317], the onsite H_2 production in Stuttgart, Germany was compared to an import scenario where the H_2 is produced in Sines, Portugal, liquefied, transported to the port of Hamburg, Germany, evaporated, and further transported to Stuttgart. The results suggested that despite the energy-intensive H_2 liquefaction process, the import option is slightly cheaper. However, wind turbines were not considered as an electricity source for the electrolyzer.

H_2 electrolyzers can stabilize electricity markets with high shares of vRES [318], stabilize the market value [319], and even provide grid-forming services such as frequency or voltage

regulation [320]. In line with this, the European Union mandates that H₂ electrolyzers must be connected to new renewable electricity generation facilities [321].

The reviewed papers highlight the importance of considering various transportation options and the adaptable nature of electrolyzers. However, to the best of the author’s knowledge, no study has yet analyzed the impact of landing interruptions on H₂ import hubs.

The remainder of this chapter is organized as follows: Section 8.2.1 outlines the model formulation and details the case study, while Section 8.2.2 discusses the assumed data. The results are presented in Section 8.3, and the chapter concludes in Section 8.4.

8.2 Materials and methods

8.2.1 Optimization model

A MILP was formulated which yielded the total-cost-minimal synthesis, design, and operation of conversion and storage infrastructure to meet a given H₂ demand considering vRES and landfall constraints (Rhine low water). The energy system model assumed perfect foresight. It was formulated using Python and GurobiPy within the version 0.3.1 of DRAF described in Chapter 4. Fig. 8.1 shows the superstructure of the H₂ hub model.

FIGURE 8.1: Superstructure of the model. Acronyms used in the modeling are indicated in bold. Energy balances are denoted in circles.

8.2.1.1 Objective function

All optimization variables are indicated in bold and are non-negative continuous variables if not stated otherwise. Equations are valid for all indices of the relevant sets. General indices and sets are hourly time steps $t \in \mathcal{T} := \{1, 2, \dots, 8760\}$ and technologies $j \in \mathcal{J} := \{\text{PV}, \text{OnPV}, \text{WT}, \text{EL}, \text{HP}, \text{NC}, \text{NL}, \text{HL}, \text{BES}, \text{TES}, \text{NS}, \text{HS}\}$. The objective function of the MILP problem is the minimization of the **TAC** including **CapEx**, the repair, maintenance, and inspection costs (**RMI**) and the **OpEx**:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize } \quad & \mathbf{TAC} := \mathbf{CapEx} + \mathbf{RMI} + \mathbf{OpEx} \\ & \mathbf{TAC}, \mathbf{OpEx} \in \mathbb{R} \end{aligned} \quad (8.1)$$

The **CapEx** are the annual depreciation costs for investments, and the **RMI** are the annual share based on the RMI cost factor k_j^{RMI} :

$$\mathbf{CapEx} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} a_j c_j^{\text{CapEx}} \hat{P}_j \quad (8.2)$$

$$\mathbf{RMI} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} k_j^{\text{RMI}} c_j \hat{P}_j \quad (8.3)$$

where $a_j = \frac{r(1+r)^{N_j}}{(1+r)^{N_j}-1}$ is the annuity factor, N_j is the operation life, c_j^{CapEx} are the specific investment costs, and \hat{P}_j is the capacity of technology $j \in \mathcal{J}$.

The **OpEx** consist of the purchase of NH_3 , H_2 , and H_2O and the revenue earned by selling excess electricity on the day-ahead market:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{OpEx} = & \Delta t \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} c^{\text{NH}_3} \dot{H}_t^{\text{NL}} + \Delta t \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} c^{\text{H}_2} \dot{H}_t^{\text{HL}} + c^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \mathbf{m}^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \\ & - \Delta t \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} c_t^{\text{EG}} (\mathbf{P}_t^{\text{OnPV,sell}} + \mathbf{P}_t^{\text{PV,sell}} + \mathbf{P}_t^{\text{WT,sell}}) \end{aligned} \quad (8.4)$$

where c^{NH_3} , c^{H_2} , and $c^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ are the NH_3 , H_2 , and H_2O prices, respectively; $\dot{H}_t^{\text{NL/HL}}$ denote the landed NH_3/H_2 energy flow; and $\mathbf{m}^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is the annual H_2O consumption mass.

8.2.1.2 Constraints

The modeling of the technologies is based on Chapters 4 and 5 but is mostly also described here for the readers' convenience.

Energy balances. As shown in Fig. 8.1, there are four energy balances, NH₃, H₂, electricity, and heat:

$$\dot{H}_t^{\text{NL}} + \dot{H}_t^{\text{NS,out}} = \dot{H}_t^{\text{NC,in}} + \dot{H}_t^{\text{NS,in}} \quad (8.5)$$

$$\dot{H}_t^{\text{HL}} + \dot{H}_t^{\text{HS,out}} + \dot{H}_t^{\text{EL}} + \dot{H}_t^{\text{NC,out}} = \dot{H}_t^{\text{HS,in}} + \dot{H}_t^{\text{Dem}} \quad (8.6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} P_t^{\text{OnPV,oc}} + P_t^{\text{PV,oc}} + P_t^{\text{WT,oc}} + P_t^{\text{BES,out}} \\ = P_t^{\text{BES,in}} + P_t^{\text{NC}} + P_t^{\text{EL}} + P_t^{\text{HP}} \end{aligned} \quad (8.7)$$

$$\dot{Q}_t^{\text{EL}} + \dot{Q}_t^{\text{TES,out}} = \dot{Q}_t^{\text{TES,in}} + \dot{Q}_t^{\text{HP,in}} \quad (8.8)$$

Conversion technology constraints. Similar to Chapter 5, the conversion technologies were generally modeled with a linear input-output relationship:

$$P_t^{\text{in}} = \eta P_t^{\text{out}} \quad (8.9)$$

$$P_t^{\text{out}} \leq \hat{P} \quad (8.10)$$

where $P_t^{\text{in/out}}$ are the input and output energy flows, respectively, η is the efficiency, and \hat{P} is the capacity. Note that some technologies have multiple outputs or inputs.

The constraints for the NH₃ landing (NL) are shown in Eqs. (8.11) and (8.12) and the constraints for the H₂ landing (HL) are analogous.

$$\dot{H}_t^{\text{NL,out}} \leq k_t^{\text{NL,avail}} \hat{H}^{\text{NL}} \quad (8.11)$$

$$\dot{H}_t^{\text{NL,out}} = \eta^{\text{NL}} \dot{H}_t^{\text{HL,in}} \quad (8.12)$$

The Proton exchange membrane electrolyzer (EL) was modeled with the following constraints:

$$P_t^{\text{EL}} \leq \hat{P}^{\text{EL}} \quad (8.13)$$

$$\dot{H}_t^{\text{EL}} = \eta^{\text{EL,H}} P_t^{\text{EL}} \quad (8.14)$$

$$\dot{Q}_t^{\text{EL}} = \eta^{\text{EL,th}} P_t^{\text{EL}} \quad (8.15)$$

$$m^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = \frac{k^{\text{EL,H}_2\text{O}}}{e^{\text{H}_2}} \Delta t \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \dot{H}_t^{\text{EL}} \quad (8.16)$$

where $k^{\text{EL,H}_2\text{O}}$ is the specific water consumption per kg of produced H₂, $c^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is the water price, and e^{H_2} is the gravimetric energy density of H₂ (=33.3 kWh/kg).

The constraints for the NH₃ cracker (NC) are:

$$\dot{H}_t^{\text{NC,out}} \leq \hat{H}^{\text{NC}} \quad (8.17)$$

$$\dot{H}_t^{\text{NC,out}} = \dot{H}_t^{\text{NC,in}} \eta^{\text{NC}} \quad (8.18)$$

$$P_t^{\text{NC}} = \dot{H}_t^{\text{NC,out}} k^{\text{NC,el}} \quad (8.19)$$

The HP model of Chapter 4 was used.

Storage technology constraints. The battery energy storage (BES) constraints are:

$$\begin{aligned} E_t = \Delta t \left(\eta^{\text{ch}} P_t^{\text{in}} - \frac{P_t^{\text{out}}}{\eta^{\text{dis}}} \right) \\ + (1 - \eta^{\text{self}} \Delta t) \begin{cases} k^{\text{ini}} \hat{E} & \text{if } t = t_0 \\ E_{t-1} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (8.20)$$

$$P_t^{\text{in}} \leq \lambda^{\text{in}} \hat{E} \quad (8.21)$$

$$P_t^{\text{out}} \leq \lambda^{\text{out}} \hat{E} \quad (8.22)$$

$$E_t \leq \hat{E} \quad (8.23)$$

$$E_{t|\tau_1} = k^{\text{ini}} \hat{E} \quad (8.24)$$

The NH₃ storage (NS), H₂ storage (HS), and the TES were formulated analogously to the BES. The initial and final energy filling levels of BES, NS, HS, and TES were set to 0%, 70%, 70%, and 50%, respectively.

8.2.2 Data for the case study

An H₂ demand of 220 GWh/yr was assumed for the year 2025, which represents approximately 20% of the projected H₂ demand for the state of Baden-Württemberg in 2025, as reported in [322]. To capture the slightly seasonal profile of H₂ demand, a profile based on ambient air temperature (see Fig. 8.4) was considered. The key techno-economic parameters for the relevant technologies are listed in Table 8.1. The purchase prices for H₂, NH₃, and H₂O were set to €160/MWh [315], €100/MWh [315], and €2/t_{H₂O}, respectively. To investigate the impact of landing interruptions, the scenario IL was considered, where landing availability for NH₃ and H₂ was set to zero for the first two weeks of August. This scenario was compared against the reference scenario REF, where landing was assumed to be available throughout the year.

TABLE 8.1: Technology data: Specific investment costs c^{CapEx} , maintenance factor k^{RMI} , operation life N , efficiency η .

Tech- nology	Ref- erence	c^{CapEx} (€/kW(h))	k^{RMI} (%/yr)	N (years)	η (%)
(On)PV	[286, 323]	460	2	25	14.9 ^b
WT	[315]	1,260	1	20	32.9 ^b
EL	[133]	1,295	3.8	14	75 ^c
HP	[315]	572	3	25	50 ^d
NC ^a	[315]	832	4	30	79 ^e
NL		500	2	40	99
HL		500	2	40	99
BES	[324, 325]	300	2	20	95 ^f
TES	[315]	20	1.5	30	100 ^g
NS	[315]	500	2	40	99 ^h
HS	[315]	500	2	40	99 ^h

^a including an H₂-compressor

^b capacity factor

^c 75%_{H₂} system efficiency, 14%_{thermal} at 57°C, 9 kg_{H₂O}/kg_{H₂}

^d exergy efficiency (ratio of reaching ideal Carnot COP)

^e additional electricity consumption $k^{\text{NC,el}}$ of 0.077 kWh_{el}/kWh_{H₂}

^f 95% cycle efficiency and self-discharge η^{self} of 0.002%/h [297]

^g 100% cycle efficiency and self-discharge of 0.7% per day [326]

^h 99% cycle efficiency and no self-discharge

Photovoltaic (PV). The model used an hourly PV electricity generation profile in kW per installed kW_{peak} obtained from the GSEE tool [276], using input data that included the coordinates of the Karlsruhe port (49.015, 8.327) and hourly weather data from the nearest national weather stations, specifically air temperature data from Rheinstetten and global solar irradiation data from Mannheim. The profile was scaled to a capacity factor of 14.9%, which was calculated for Karlsruhe in 2019, assuming a 30° south tilt and 10% system loss, based on data from [327]. A possible onsite (i.e., without network charges) PV capacity of 7.69 MW_{peak} was assumed.

Wind turbine (WT). WTs were modeled with a given electricity generation profile described in Chapter 5 with a capacity factor of 32.9%. The above mentioned network charges apply.

Electricity grid (EG). For offsite WTs and PV, a network charge of €42.56/MWh_{el} is assumed. For the EG feed-in, German day-ahead market prices of the year 2019 were used, see Fig. 8.2. The year 2019 was chosen due to the anomalies of the years 2021 and 2022 resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine. The data was drawn from

the ENTSO-E transparency platform [242] via the Python module Elmada [261] described in Chapter 3.

FIGURE 8.2: Historic day-ahead market price for Germany of the year 2019.

Electric heat pump (HP) and district heating network (DHN). The temperature levels for the HP were $\mathcal{I}:=\{\text{RW}, \text{EL}\}$ for input and $\mathcal{O}:=\{\text{winter}, \text{summer}\}$ for output. For the heat flow between the EL and the HP, the model assumes a constant temperature of 57°C. Additionally to the heat from the EL, the Rhine river can be used as a heat source. For the temperature of the Rhine, monthly average water temperature values of 2022 were taken from the station Bad-Honnef [328], see Fig. 8.3.

FIGURE 8.3: Assumed temperature of the Rhine water.

The feed-in of thermal energy into the district heating network is specified in Table 8.2.

TABLE 8.2: Parameter for district heating network feed-in.

Season	Feed-in tariff	Temperature
Summer (May–Sep)	€40/MWh	80°C
Winter (Oct–Apr)	€60/MWh	120°C

8.3 Results

The problems were solved with a MIP gap of 0.1 using Gurobi 9.5 solver. Table 8.4 shows the capacities determined by the solver. The IL scenario had higher capacities than the REF scenario for all technologies except WT, EL, and HL. The scenarios show small differences in vRES capacities (0–4%), medium differences in conversion technologies (14–45%), and

TABLE 8.3: Total costs and its components in M€/yr.

Scen.	TAC	CapEx	RMI	OpEx
REF	35.99	7.04	1.96	26.98
IL	36.27 (+0.8%)	7.45 (+6.3%)	2.12 (+8.2%)	26.70 (-1.0%)

TABLE 8.4: Resulting capacities for the two scenarios REF and IL.

Group	Techn.	Unit	REF	IL	Difference
vRES	OnPV	MW _{peak}	7.69	7.69	0%
	PV	MW _{peak}	32.02	32.87	+3%
	WT	MW _{peak}	7.92	7.63	-4%
Conversion	EL	MW _{el}	3.55	2.61	-26%
	HP	MW _{th,out}	0.93	1.35	+45%
	NC	MW	22.22	25.31	+14%
	HL	MW	22.16	18.25	-18%
	NL	MW	25.05	29.29	+17%
Storage	BES	MWh _{el}	1.92	2.85	+49%
	TES	MWh _{th}	0.76	13.53	+1,677%
	HS	MWh	110.27	256.13	+132%
	NS	MWh	2,454.55	8,586.08	+250%

FIGURE 8.4: Resulting H₂ and NH₃ energy flows (top) and storage filling levels (bottom) for the two scenarios REF (left) and IL (right).

FIGURE 8.5: Conversion technology capacity factors (top) and annual electricity balance (bottom). Note: Percentages are based on REF.

high differences in storage technologies (49–1,677%). The conversion technology capacity factors, see Fig. 8.5 top, decreased even for the technologies EL and HL whose capacities have decreased. Fig. 8.5 bottom shows the annual electricity balance of the two scenarios. It can be seen that in IL, the EL requires less power but the NC and the feed-in are increased compared to REF.

The resulting system behavior is illustrated in Figs. 8.4 and 8.6. Examining Fig. 8.4, the notable gap in the landed NH_3 immediately captures attention as well as the simultaneous NS discharge due to the landing interruption in the first two weeks of August. Several additional key observations can be made from Fig. 8.4, progressing from top to bottom: 1) In both scenarios, electricity was primarily sold during excess PV electricity generation. 2) In the IL scenario, the EL operated during landing interruption periods, while in the preceding weeks, it showed fewer operating hours compared to the REF scenario. 3) During the summer months in the IL scenario, Rhine water (RW) was preferred over the EL as an HP heat source, especially during daytime. 4) The NC operation profiles for both scenarios are quite similar. 5) The impact of the landing interruption on the HL operation is barely noticeable due to its low utilization rate. 6) H_2 was mainly landed when the NC was not operating, which reduced H_2 storage costs. 7) In the REF scenario, the TES exhibited two distinct cycle patterns namely multi-day in winter and single-day in summer while the IL scenario features a multi-day pattern throughout the year.

Table 8.3 presents the TAC and its contributions: CapEx, RMI, and OpEx. While CapEx

FIGURE 8.6: Heatmaps of relevant time series from 0% (white) to 100% (black). y-axis: daily hours from 1 (top) to 24 (bottom) with 4-hourly ticks; x-axis: days of the year from left to right with monthly ticks.

and RMI costs increased by 6.3% and 8.2%, respectively, OpEx partly offset this with a 1.0% decrease, primarily due to selling electricity generated by PV and selling heat using river water as an HP heat source. As a result, the TAC only increased by 0.8% which means that if H₂ is sold to a customer without a margin, the landing interruptions increase the price by €1.3/MWh (0.8%) from €163.6/MWh to €164.9/MWh. However, these values are based on optimal planning and operation under perfect foresight.

With the capacities of the REF scenario, the H₂ hub could have supplied only 3.4 GWh (47%) of the 7.3 GWh H₂ demand during the landing interruption, even under ideal conditions with 100% storage levels at the beginning of the landing interruption.

8.4 Conclusions

This chapter investigated the impact of landing interruptions on the optimal design of an H₂ import hub using a MILP model. Landing interruptions that are not considered in the design of an H₂ import hub can lead to unmet demands and to unpredictable high follow-up costs. In the investigated case, without considering the landing interruptions within the planning stage, only 47% of the H₂ demand during the time of landing interruptions could have been met by the H₂ import hub. The results show that the consideration of landing interruptions significantly impacts the optimal design of an H₂ import hub. This leads to up to 45% capacity differences in conversion technologies and up to 16x higher storage capacities. If the annual two-week landing interruption is integrally considered during the planning stage, the H₂ import hub can meet the demands with only 0.8% higher total annual costs. The findings have important implications for the design and the operation of H₂ import hubs, particularly in regions prone to landing interruptions. By considering landing interruptions in the system design, H₂ import hubs can improve their resilience and reduce the risk of supply chain disruptions. The methodology can also be used to inform policy decisions related to the development of H₂ infrastructure.

Chapter 9

The hidden cost of using time series aggregation for modeling low-carbon industrial energy systems: An investors' perspective

Abstract. Time series aggregation (TSA) is commonly used in energy system optimization to reduce model complexity and computational expenses by selecting periods to represent the entire time series. TSA's accuracy has traditionally been assessed by comparing the objective values between the original and TSA models (assumed error). However, evaluating TSA from an investor's standpoint involves analyzing the performance of TSA-based energy system designs using the original time series. Therefore, we introduce the hidden error and total error, novel error metrics, to evaluate the financial implications of TSA through backtesting the TSA-based system designs using the original time series. Our analysis extends to the effects of carbon removal prices and the choice between marginal and grid-mix emission factors on TSA's performance. We find that traditional error metrics inadequately capture TSA-induced financial losses. We demonstrate that for ambitious emission reduction targets, the hidden error, which had not been identified previously, is up to 29 times the error identified by prior error evaluation approaches. Consequently, TSA should be applied cautiously, particularly when outcomes are vital for investment decisions and when lower TSA rates yield computationally feasible models, highlighting the need to consider comprehensive error metrics in TSA applications for more accurate energy system optimization.

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9.1 Overview and context

Motivation. Today's industrial energy systems need to reduce CEs rapidly to align with the global climate goals set in the Paris Agreement 2015. MILP is especially promising and widely used to determine the cost-optimal design of such sustainable energy systems [330]. However, in contrast to conventional systems, systems characterized by fluctuating energy resources and storage require high temporal resolutions. The need for distributed, connected MESs adds further dimensions, which makes the modeling of low-carbon energy systems computationally complex, especially, when discrete characteristics are considered. To reduce a model's complexity and maintain its computational tractability, TSA methods are widely used where redundant information is removed by clustering the original input time series into representative periods such as typical days.¹ TSA reduces the complexity of system design optimization problems and, consequently, computational complexity. But, this comes at the cost of simulation accuracy. The results of the original model and the TSA model differ in terms of the decision variables (system design variables such as the storage capacity) and the objective function (costs such as CapEx or OpEx). Typically, the accuracy of the TSA is evaluated using statistical metrics of the time series (*a priori* TSA error) or by assessing the *a posteriori* TSA error of the objective function, which is referred to as the *assumed error*. However, from an investor's perspective, the interesting question is: How does the system design identified using the TSA method perform across the entire time series, and how close is this design to the optimal design? To address this question, the system design identified by the TSA method must be backtested on the original time series.

Background. TSA methods have demonstrated adequacy for regional energy system models, which also bear the greatest potential for complexity reduction due to their high level of model complexity. Compared to L-MESs, the TSA error is particularly small, owing to the smoothing effect of the regional aggregation of renewable energy time series [218]. However, sustainable L-MESs exhibit intricate sector coupling and cross-linking, leading to

¹Convention: The terms *typical* and *representative* are used synonymously. Typical days are typical periods with a period length of one day.

heightened model complexity. This complexity further intensifies when considering energy storage and load flexibilization, sometimes to a degree that necessitates the application of complexity reduction methods for computational tractability. This raises a question: Is TSA an adequate method for reducing computational complexity while preserving a high level of accuracy in determining the optimal system design for highly flexible, sector-coupled, and decarbonized MESs? This chapter answers the above question by combining different mentioned approaches and by analyzing TSA-induced errors of a local industrial MES considering energy flexibility through real-time pricing, dynamic CEFs, and different specific costs for DAC, referred to as DAC price.

Literature review. Section 2.5 provides a detailed literature review on TSA for energy system models, showing that various TSA methods have been proposed and comparatively evaluated. The existing literature assesses TSA adequacy by examining the *a priori* TSA error or the *a posteriori* error of the objective function or design of the reduced-complexity problem. However, this literature review identifies a research gap in analyzing the real consequences of using TSA-based approaches for investment decision support. More specifically, only two studies were found that evaluated TSA by backtesting the TSA-based design on the full-year model. The literature shows that the *a priori* TSA error does not necessarily correlate with the *a posteriori* error of the objective function or system design variables. However, the hypothesis that the *a posteriori* error of the TSA-based optimization model (*assumed error*) correlates with the *a posteriori* error of the operation optimization problem of the full time series with fixed design variables (*total error*) has yet to be proven.

Contributions. This chapter answers the following question: Is TSA an adequate method to reduce computational complexity while preserving a high level of accuracy when determining the optimal system design for highly flexible, sector-coupled, and decarbonized MESs within a volatile market environment? It is shown that the *total TSA-induced error* does not necessarily correlate with the assumed TSA-induced error. Furthermore, the findings show that the cost of external CE mitigation has a significant impact on the deviation of these errors. This chapter calculates the investor's TSA-induced hidden cost to evaluate the adequacy of using TSA for low-carbon industrial MESs considering flexibility. To this end, the TSA-based MES design is backtested with the original time series model. To the best of the author's knowledge, this is the first study to evaluate the adequacy of TSA for low-carbon industrial energy systems by backtesting the TSA-based MES design with the original model. More specifically, the contributions of this chapter are:

1. A new terminology describing three different *a posteriori* TSA-induced error metrics.

2. Calculation of these error metrics for a real-world industrial case study for different Pareto-optimal TSA hyperparameters.
3. Analysis of the impact of DAC prices on the outcome of the optimal MES and the adequacy of TSA.
4. Investigation of the effect of considering MEFs instead of XEFs for the adequacy of using TSA for MES models.

Chapter organization. The remainder of the chapter is structured as follows: In Section 9.2.1, the case study is described. Section 9.2.2, details the TSA approach used, the optimization model, and the technology data. Furthermore, the new terminology of *a posteriori* TSA-induced errors is defined. The results of the different analyses are described and discussed in Section 9.3. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 9.4.

9.2 Materials and methods

9.2.1 Case study and market data

For the analysis, a case study of a light-industrial company was used which is described in Fig. 9.1. The case study is detailed in Chapter 5. All components and parameters from Chapter 5 were used, but for simplicity, the forklift trucks were omitted. The most important data are described again in the following for convenience: The inflexible electricity, cooling, and lower and upper-temperature heating demands are described in Chapter 5 and are 5.2, 1.5, 4.8, and 2.1 GWh per year, respectively. National dynamic XEFs and MEFs were calculated for the year 2019 using the methods `XEF_EP` and `MEF_PP` of the Python package `Elmada` [261] which is described in Chapter 3. The historic hourly day-ahead electricity price of the year 2019 was used, ranging from €-90 to €121 per MWh, accessed from the ENTSO-E transparency platform [242] via `Elmada` [261]. The purchase of natural gas is priced at €43/MWh and an additional carbon tax of €55/t_{CO₂eq} assuming a CE intensity of 0.240 t_{CO₂eq} per MWh [299]. The year 2019 was selected to avoid anomalies from the COVID-19 pandemic and the Russian invasion of Ukraine. A DAC price of €800/t was assumed, which is currently offered commercially [331].

9.2.2 Methodology

This section describes the TSA method, the optimization model, and the technology data and defines the TSA-induced errors.

FIGURE 9.1: Superstructure of the industrial case study including supply and demand, all existing and possible (greyed out) energy technologies and the energy flows between them. In the current MES, the electricity demand is met without storage through a combination of a photovoltaic (PV) system, a natural gas-fired combined heat and power (CHP) system, and the electricity grid (EG). The cooling demand is served by a cooling machine (i.e., an electric heat pump (HP) without utilizing the hot side for heating purposes). Both the space and the process heat demand are satisfied by the CHP system and a heat-only boiler (HOB) powered by natural gas. Scheme adapted from Chapter 5.

9.2.2.1 Used TSA approach

This chapter applies the hierarchical TSA method from the Time Series Aggregation Module (TSAM) v2.2.2 [332] considering typical days, segmentation, and extreme periods. The number of typical periods and the number of segments per typical period are shown in Table 9.2. Other hyperparameters were selected to the best of the author's knowledge: As suggested by [234], the original time series' value distribution is preserved (TSAM argument `representationMethod = "durationRepresentation"`). The day with the highest cooling demand and the day with the highest upper heating demand were each forced to be cluster centers (TSAM argument `extremePeriodMethod = "replace_cluster_center"`).

9.2.2.2 Optimization model

The energy system models were formulated using the TSA branch of version v0.3 of DRAF [333] described in Chapter 4. The model is described in Chapter 5 and adapted to use typical days, segments, and seasonal storage [219]. Differing from Chapter 5, battery electric vehicles are not modeled to avoid side effects. The objective of the model is to minimize TACs while ensuring energy balances, and technical constraints. Perfect foresight is assumed for demands, renewable energy generation, prices, and CEFs. The superstructure of the model is depicted in Fig. 9.1.

TABLE 9.1: Main technology parameters.

Technology	Specific inv. costs c^{inv}	RMI costs c^{RMI}	Economic life N	Efficiency η
CHP	€589/kW _{el} [291]	18%	25a	40%
Al-Elc	€708/kW _{el} [335]	3.8%	14a	71%
FC	€1,684/kW _{el} [133]	3.8%	14a	50%
HOB	€57.13/kW _{th} [292]	18%	15a	90%
HP	€387/kW _{th,cond} [133]	2.5%	18a	50%
P2H	€100/kW _{th} [293]	0%	30a	90%
PV	€460/kW _p [286]	2%	25a	given profile
WT	€1,682/kW _p [294]	1%	20a	given profile
BES	€500/kWh [324]	2%	20a	95% _{cycle}
H ₂ S	€10/kWh _{H₂} [133]	0%	23a	90% _{cycle}
TES	€28.71/kWh _{th} [296]	0.1%	30a	99.5% _{time}

Decarbonization. To distinguish between different decarbonization degrees, a non-decarbonization scenario s and a decarbonization scenario s_d is introduced. In contrast to s , the net operating CEs of s_d must be zero which is ensured by a CE constraint. A slack variable is introduced to quantify the demand for carbon removal.

Lost thermal load. In the backtest, the sequential optimization of design and operation with different time series can lead to an insufficient thermal energy supply. To handle these infeasibilities and quantify the unmet demand, slack variables are introduced into the thermal energy balance for each time step and temperature level. As per Chapter 5, slack variables in the objective function are penalized outside of the TAC balance. This allows the slack variable to quantify the lost load without affecting the results of the optimization. The penalty is set to €10,000/kWh to ensure that the slack variable quantifies only the load that could not otherwise be met. *A posteriori*, the cost of lost cooling is evaluated at €2/kWh and added to the operating costs.²

Technology data. Table 9.1 shows the main technology parameters used in the model. Please see Chapter 5 for a more detailed description of the input parameters.

9.2.2.3 Definition of TSA-induced errors

In this chapter, three different TSA-induced errors are considered, which are defined in this section: The *assumed error*, the *hidden error*, and the *total error*. Fig. 9.2 is a graphical overview of their definition, inter-relationships, and calculation process.

²This is based on the assumption of €9,000 rental costs for a 300 kW_{th} mobile chiller for 2 months and an expected consumption of 4,500 kWh [334].

Let s_{orig} (original model) be a design and operation optimization model parameterized with the original (i.e., non-aggregated) time series. Further, let s_{TSA} (TSA model) be a variant of it that uses temporally aggregated time series instead of the original time series. Finally, a third model s_{BT} (backtest model) is instantiated that evaluates the performance of the TSA-based system design on the original time series.

Each error is defined as the difference between the results of two different models. The *assumed error* is the TAC difference between the original model and the TSA model while the *hidden error* is the TAC difference between the TSA model and the backtest model:

$$\text{assumed error} = \Delta\text{TAC}_{\text{orig.} \rightarrow \text{TSA}} = \text{TAC}_{\text{TSA}} - \text{TAC}_{\text{orig.}} \quad (9.1)$$

$$\text{hidden error} = \Delta\text{TAC}_{\text{TSA} \rightarrow \text{BT}} = \text{TAC}_{\text{BT}} - \text{TAC}_{\text{TSA}} \quad (9.2)$$

The *total error* is the TAC difference between the backtest model and the original model:

$$\text{total error} = \Delta\text{TAC}_{\text{orig.} \rightarrow \text{BT}} = \text{TAC}_{\text{BT}} - \text{TAC}_{\text{orig.}} \quad (9.3)$$

Moreover, the *total error* can be described as the sum of the other two errors:

$$\underbrace{\Delta\text{TAC}_{\text{orig.} \rightarrow \text{BT}}}_{\text{total error}} = \underbrace{\Delta\text{TAC}_{\text{orig.} \rightarrow \text{TSA}}}_{\text{assumed error}} + \underbrace{\Delta\text{TAC}_{\text{TSA} \rightarrow \text{BT}}}_{\text{hidden error}} \quad (9.4)$$

Note that the error metrics can be negative, e.g., when the mismatch between renewable electricity generation and consumption is underestimated through TSA, the *assumed error* is negative since the TAC of the TSA model is smaller than the TAC of the original model.

If an investor makes an investment decision based on the results of a TSA-based model, it is the *total error* that is most relevant for the investor. Therefore, in this chapter, the *total error* is also referred to as the TSA-induced investor's loss.

9.3 Results

This section contains the results of various analyses which are structured into model input analysis (Section 9.3.1) and model output analysis (Section 9.3.2).

Note that in the following, a distinction is made between CEs (before carbon removal) and carbon footprint (after carbon removal).

9.3.1 Model input analysis (*a priori*)

FIGURE 9.2: Definition of TSA-induced error metrics (top) and its calculation process (bottom).

9.3.1.1 Autocorrelation

As a first indicator of TSA adequacy, the autocorrelation coefficients of the model input time series are calculated for different lags, particularly for the 24 (daily) and 168 (weekly) hours lags, as shown in Fig. 9.3. It can be observed that the PV profile features both high daily and weekly autocorrelation values. The autocorrelation of the wind profile decreases with increasing lag. For the energy demands, especially electricity, the weekly autocorrelation is higher than the daily while for all other time series, it is vice versa. For both the 24-hour lag and the 168-hour lag, the autocorrelation value is moderate for electricity prices and XEFs but low for MEFs.

9.3.1.2 Pareto-optimal TSA hyperparameters

To cover a wide range of TSA reductions, an exponential sequence of reduction factors is used. More precisely, $\alpha \in \{1, \dots, 10\}$ is defined as the number of times the original number of total time steps is halved. Then, the TSA reduction factors are mapped to

FIGURE 9.3: Autocorrelation coefficients of input time series for different lags.

TABLE 9.2: Used reduction factors, TSA input parameters, and aggregation error.

α	TSA factor $2^{-\alpha}$	Reduction $1 - 2^{-\alpha}$	Max. no. of time steps $\bar{N}_{\mathcal{K}} \cdot \bar{N}_{\mathcal{G}}$	No. of typical days $N_{\mathcal{K}}$	No. of segments $N_{\mathcal{G}}$	TSA error RMSE
0	1	0%	8760	365	24	0%
1	2^{-1}	50%	4380	365	12	2.9%
2	4^{-1}	75%	2190	365	6	6.0%
3	8^{-1}	87.5%	1095	365	3	9.1%
4	16^{-1}	93.75%	547	182	3	11.8%
5	32^{-1}	$\sim 96.88\%$	273	91	3	13.8%
6	64^{-1}	$\sim 98.44\%$	136	68	2	15.2%
7	128^{-1}	$\sim 99.22\%$	68	68	1	16.1%
8	256^{-1}	$\sim 99.61\%$	34	34	1	16.8%
9	512^{-1}	$\sim 99.80\%$	17	17	1	17.6%
10	1024^{-1}	$\sim 99.90\%$	8	8	1	18.2%
modeler's choice			for $N_{\mathcal{T}} = 8760$	Pareto-optimal, depend on input data		

Pareto-optimal hyperparameters, namely, the number of typical periods and the number of segments per typical period, using the algorithm proposed by Hoffmann et al. [234]. Table 9.2 shows for each α value, the corresponding reduction factor, the resulting Pareto-optimal hyperparameters, and the *a priori* TSA error.

Fig. 9.4 visualizes the Pareto-optimal hyperparameters when all time series are aggregated

together (total) and when they are aggregated individually. In general, it is observed that N_K -reductions are preferred over N_G -reductions. Interestingly, when going from $\alpha = 1$ to $\alpha = 2$ this still holds true for time series with a high daily autocorrelation such as the PV profile and the electricity price. As a consequence, the preference for N_G -reductions over N_K -reductions is reinforced in the total aggregation which leads to extreme Pareto-optimal hyperparameters, as in the case of $\alpha = 7$, which consists of 68 typical days with only one segment each.

FIGURE 9.4: Pareto-optimal TSA hyperparameters for $\alpha \in \{0, \dots, 10\}$.

Fig. 9.5 and Fig. 9.6 show the TSA-induced profile approximation for three α values for PV and Wind, respectively. Since the reduction of the number of segments is preferred over the reduction of typical days, a significant deviation is seen especially for the PV profile with $\alpha = 10$ where the original time series is approximated with only one segment per typical day.

Fig. 9.7 shows the monthly average values of the wind and PV profiles for the different α values. By preserving the value distribution during TSA, the annual averages are correctly assumed regardless of α . However, TSA tends to underestimate the specific WT and PV electricity production in the summer months (March – September) and overestimate it in the winter months.

9.3.2 Model output analysis (*a posteriori*)

This section analyzes the results of the optimization models. The models were solved on an Apple M1 Pro (10 CPU cores at 3.22 GHz, 16 GB of RAM) with a MIP-Gap of 0.1% using the Gurobi solver 10.0.0.

FIGURE 9.5: Heatmaps of PV profile for $\alpha \in \{0, 5, 6, 7, 10\}$.

FIGURE 9.6: Heatmaps of WT profile for $\alpha \in \{0, 5, 6, 7, 10\}$.

FIGURE 9.7: Specific electricity production profiles of PV and WT: Monthly average for different α values compared to annual average values.

FIGURE 9.8: Calculation times for different α values of s and s_d .

9.3.2.1 Impact of Pareto-optimal TSA

Here, the optimization model outcomes for the non-decarbonization case s and the decarbonization case s_d are analyzed, as well as for different Pareto-optimal TSA hyperparameters (different α values). To direct the reader's eye, the differences between the scenario names and the original models are marked in bold.

Calculation time. Fig. 9.8 shows the calculation time for the non-decarbonization (τ) and for the decarbonization case (τ_d). As expected, the parameter preparation times were constant. The time to run the TSA algorithm and to initialize the model and variables fell monotonically relative to decreasing model complexity. However, it is striking, that the

TABLE 9.3: Effect of TSA on MES design. New energy conversion and storage capacities of the non-decarbonization case s and the decarbonization case s_d for different α values.

Scenario	Conversion capacity (kW)						Storage capacity (kWh)		
	Elc	FC	HP	P2H	PV	WT	BES	H2S	TES ¹
s ($\alpha=0$)	0	0	763	221	2,647	0	0	0	3,276
s ($\alpha=1$)	0	0	760	218	2,645	0	0	0	3,354
s ($\alpha=2$)	0	0	766	218	2,740	0	0	0	3,653
s ($\alpha=3$)	0	0	763	210	3,049	0	0	0	3,889
s ($\alpha=4$)	0	0	779	208	2,922	0	0	0	3,086
s ($\alpha=5$)	0	0	804	189	2,799	0	0	0	2,723
s ($\alpha=6$)	0	0	870	147	3,077	0	0	0	0
s ($\alpha=7$)	0	0	735	107	3,077	0	0	0	0
s ($\alpha=8$)	0	0	761	148	3,077	0	0	0	0
s ($\alpha=9$)	0	0	837	152	3,077	0	0	0	0
s ($\alpha=10$)	0	0	823	114	3,077	0	0	0	0
s_d ($\alpha=0$)	164	135	1,063	1,544	3,077	4,364	669	19,690	29,613
s_d ($\alpha=1$)	175	139	1,071	1,554	3,077	4,333	580	20,464	30,225
s_d ($\alpha=2$)	179	144	1,056	1,487	3,077	4,368	590	20,130	30,064
s_d ($\alpha=3$)	241	179	1,001	1,297	3,077	4,356	0	25,165	30,862
s_d ($\alpha=4$)	282	195	1,041	1,528	3,077	4,316	0	37,640	31,927
s_d ($\alpha=5$)	262	190	1,104	1,240	3,077	4,624	0	35,365	31,559
s_d ($\alpha=6$)	187	169	978	977	3,077	4,831	0	27,880	31,475
s_d ($\alpha=7$)	65	51	917	966	3,077	5,337	0	12,397	29,017
s_d ($\alpha=8$)	0	0	918	1,075	3,077	4,798	0	0	33,130
s_d ($\alpha=9$)	0	0	907	561	3,077	4,960	0	0	27,611
s_d ($\alpha=10$)	0	0	897	483	3,077	5,349	0	0	28,511

¹ aggregated values across all temperature levels

solving time did not, in all cases, decrease with decreasing model complexity. Interestingly, the Pearson correlation coefficient between τ_d and N_G was 0.99 but only 0.70 between τ_d and N_K . For τ , the corresponding values were 0.91 and 86. Especially in s_d this means that the solving time mainly depended on the number of segments. For example, while the solving time decreased for $\alpha \leq 3$ (where only N_G reduced), it increased for $3 \leq \alpha \leq 5$ (where only N_K reduced). In s , this increase was partly overcompensated by a shorter TSA calculation duration. However, in one instance in the non-decarbonization case s ($\alpha=5$) and in two instances in the decarbonization case s_d ($\alpha=4$ and $\alpha=5$), the total calculation time actually increased with increasing α values (decreasing model complexity).

Lost load. Lost loads were a marginal phenomenon. Besides numerical inaccuracies (<10 kWh/yr), it appeared for the cooling case in the scenarios $s(\alpha, \text{BT})$ for $6 \leq \alpha \leq 10$.

However, it accounted for no more than 0.3% of the cooling demand, see Table 9.4.

TABLE 9.4: Lost load of more than 10 kWh/yr.

Scenario	Lost load (kWh/yr)	Share of cooling demand (%)	Operating costs (€/yr)
s ($\alpha = \mathbf{6}$, BT)	101	0.01	201
s ($\alpha = \mathbf{7}$, BT)	4,559	0.30	9,118
s ($\alpha = \mathbf{8}$, BT)	2,637	0.17	5,275
s ($\alpha = \mathbf{9}$, BT)	380	0.02	760
s ($\alpha = \mathbf{10}$, BT)	551	0.04	1,102

MES design. Table 9.3 shows the impact of Pareto-optimal complexity reduction on the MES design. According to Table 9.3, the resulting MES design varies significantly depending on decarbonization ambitions and α value. In s , the conversion and storage capacities were either relatively small (HP, P2H, PV, TES) or not selected at all (WT, BES, H₂S). TES was the only storage technology that was selected and it was only selected for $\alpha \leq 5$. Essentially, as α values increased, the capacities for PV and HP increased, while the P2H capacity decreased. In s_d in contrast, WTs were selected and increased in size with increasing α value. The maximum space-restricted PV capacity of 3,077 kW was selected for all α values. While the TES capacities remained at a similar level, the capacities of the H₂ storage chain (Elc, FC, H₂S) increased for $\alpha \leq 4$ and decreased for $5 \leq \alpha \leq 8$ until they reached zero in $\alpha = 8$.

Annual balances. Fig. 9.9 depicts the annual balances for costs (a, c, d), CEs (b), and electrical energy (e) of all scenarios compared to the base case ($\alpha = 0$). According to Fig. 9.9 a) and b), with increasing α values TACs and CEs mainly decrease for s but increase for s_d . A significant change is observed between $s_d(\alpha = 6)$ and $s_d(\alpha = 7)$ where the CEs drop from +2.5% to -23.3% and TACs drop from +4.8% to -1.7%. In this step, the capacities of the H₂ storage chain (Elc, FC, and H₂S) decreased by 55–70%, and the WT capacity increased by 10%. Progressing from $s_d(\alpha = 7)$ to $s_d(\alpha = 10)$, only the number of typical periods (N_K) is reduced since there is only one segment per typical period left. Interestingly, while the CEs increased consistently for $\alpha \geq 7$ due to higher electricity purchase, the TACs did not increase monotonically. In fact, TACs even decrease slightly between $\alpha = 8$ and $\alpha = 9$ since the increasing DAC costs are overcompensated by higher earnings from selling electricity to the grid and cost reductions due to decreased electricity peak load.

FIGURE 9.9: Annual optimization results for different α values of s and s_d : a) TAC, b) operational CEs, c) CapEx, d) OpEx, and e) electricity consumption (+) and supply (-). Percentages compare to the base case ($\alpha=0$) and are the assumed TSA-induced errors.

9.3.2.2 TSA-induced investor's loss

So far, only the results of the TSA model have been compared with the original model (*assumed error*). In the next step, the BT model, which is a backtest of the TSA-based design with the original time series, is considered. Analogous to Fig. 9.9 a) and b), Fig. 9.10 compares the TACs and CEs between the BT models and the original models ($\alpha = 0$). As a reminder: The difference between the BT models and the according original model is the *total TSA-induced error*.

FIGURE 9.10: TACs (left) and operational CEs (right) of backtest of TSA-based design with original time series for different α values of s and s_d . Percentages compare to the base case ($\alpha = 0$) and are the total TSA-induced errors.

Fig. 9.11 shows all three TAC and CE errors for s and s_d and demonstrates that the *total error* is the sum of the *assumed* and the *hidden error*. While for s , the total TSA-induced TAC error stayed below 4%, for s_d , it increased to 12.3% for $\alpha = 9$ and to 14.9% for $\alpha = 10$. In s_d , also the relative deviations between the *hidden error* and the *assumed error* are significant; for $\alpha = 8$, the *hidden error* is 29.3 times higher than the *assumed error*.

Fig. 9.12 shows the *total TSA-induced error* in a way that the absolute values can be compared between s and s_d . For s_d , additionally, the contribution of the DAC costs to the TACs is presented. Interestingly, the α values 2, 4, 5, and 6 in s_d led to a negative *hidden TAC error* which means the *total error* is lower than the *assumed error*. In those cases, the CEs of the backtest were lower than the CEs of the original model, so the TSA-induced CE error was negative, which reduced the *total TSA-induced TAC error* through decreased DAC costs.

FIGURE 9.11: Different relative TSA-induced errors on TACs and CEs.

In Fig. 9.13, the *total TSA-induced TAC error* is plotted against the total calculation time. In both s and s_d , the α values 3, 4, and 5 are a good compromise between the two objectives.

Fig. 9.14 compares the *a priori* TSA error with the *a posteriori total TSA-induced TAC error* for different α values. As the α value increased, the TSA RMSE increased steadily and degressively while the *total TSA-induced TAC error* jumped and showed significant deviations between s and s_d .

FIGURE 9.12: Absolute *total TSA-induced error* of TACs (top) and CEs (bottom).

FIGURE 9.13: Relative total TSA-induced TAC error vs. calculation time.

FIGURE 9.14: TSA RMSE (*a priori*) vs. total TSA-induced TAC error (*a posteriori*).

9.3.2.3 Impact of carbon removal price

So far, a DAC price of $\text{€}800/\text{tCO}_2\text{eq}$ has been assumed. This analysis investigates the impact of the DAC price on the resulting system design, TACs, and CEs. Fig. 9.15 shows the sensitivity of the DAC price of the s_d original model on TACs and CEs. According to Fig. 9.15 a), increasing DAC price led to a CapEx increase and an OpEx decrease (with one exception). This is counter-intuitive since the DAC costs directly add to the OpEx. The TAC increased since the OpEx decrease could not compensate for the CapEx increase. According to Fig. 9.15 b), assuming a DAC price of $\text{€}200/\text{t}$ instead of $\text{€}800/\text{t}$ almost tripled the CEs while increasing the DAC price from $\text{€}800/\text{t}$ to $\text{€}1,000/\text{t}$ led to 56% lower CEs. The CE reductions were achieved by investing in clean technologies namely vRESs, energy storage, and electrification of heat, see Fig. 9.16 and Table 9.5. The *total TSA-induced error* strongly correlates with the DAC price, see Fig. 9.17. An explanation for this is that an increased DAC price incentivizes stronger decarbonization, which increases the dependency on storage technologies and the exploitation of dynamic signals such as CEFs, two aspects that are particularly difficult to address in TSA.

FIGURE 9.15: Impact of different DAC prices (from €10/t_{CO_{2eq}} to €10,000/t_{CO_{2eq}}) on TACs (a) and CEs (b) of the original decarbonization model $s_d(\alpha=0)$.

FIGURE 9.16: CapEx of s_d for $\alpha \in \{0, 5\}$ and 12 different DAC prices c^{DAC} in €/t_{CO_{2eq}}.

9.3.2.4 Impact of using MEFs instead of XEFs

Due to the significant differences in autocorrelation values between MEFs and XEFs in Fig. 9.3, the impact of considering MEFs instead of XEFs on the TSA adequacy is now examined. In the style of Fig. 9.4, Fig. 9.18 shows the Pareto-optimal TSA hyperparameters for the different α values when aggregating all time series together (total) and aggregating only the XEFs or MEFs individually. In the individual case, the consideration of MEFs further increased the preference for reducing N_G instead of N_K . Interestingly, when all

TABLE 9.5: Effect of DAC price and TSA on MES design: New energy conversion and storage capacities of s_d for $\alpha \in \{0, 5\}$ and 12 different DAC prices c^{DAC} ($\text{€}/\text{tCO}_{2\text{eq}}$).

Scenario	Conversion capacity (kW)						Storage capacity (kWh)		
	Elc	FC	HP	P2H	PV	WT	BES	H2S	TES ¹
s ($\alpha=0$)	0	0	763	221	2,647	0	0	0	3,276
s ($\alpha=5$)	0	0	804	189	2,799	0	0	0	2,723
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=10, \alpha=0$)	0	0	889	759	3,077	0	0	0	6,387
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=10, \alpha=5$)	0	0	922	593	3,077	0	0	0	6,357
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=100, \alpha=0$)	0	0	886	920	3,077	833	0	0	9,177
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=100, \alpha=5$)	0	0	914	730	3,077	786	0	0	8,785
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=200, \alpha=0$)	0	0	899	1,083	3,077	2,078	0	0	13,865
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=200, \alpha=5$)	0	0	944	906	3,077	2,072	0	0	10,189
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=300, \alpha=0$)	0	0	956	1,132	3,077	2,657	35	0	16,891
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=300, \alpha=5$)	0	0	950	1,027	3,077	2,736	0	0	14,961
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=400, \alpha=0$)	0	0	978	1,277	3,077	3,304	124	0	21,864
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=400, \alpha=5$)	0	0	993	1,062	3,077	3,579	0	0	20,851
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=500, \alpha=0$)	0	0	1,047	1,333	3,077	3,697	227	0	25,277
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=500, \alpha=5$)	0	0	1,057	1,118	3,077	3,806	0	0	24,643
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=600, \alpha=0$)	0	0	1,084	1,448	3,077	4,028	413	0	28,832
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=600, \alpha=5$)	0	0	1,168	1,072	3,077	4,094	0	0	29,649
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=700, \alpha=0$)	16	11	1,087	1,503	3,077	4,183	640	1,437	30,045
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=700, \alpha=5$)	39	24	1,145	1,115	3,077	4,395	0	4,272	32,496
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=800, \alpha=0$)	164	135	1,063	1,544	3,077	4,364	669	19,690	29,613
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=800, \alpha=5$)	262	190	1,104	1,240	3,077	4,624	0	35,365	31,559
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=900, \alpha=0$)	307	260	1,025	1,557	3,077	4,462	680	44,075	28,665
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=900, \alpha=5$)	394	296	1,084	1,198	3,077	4,764	0	54,576	30,285
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=10^3, \alpha=0$)	388	346	1,005	1,564	3,077	4,546	703	60,108	28,108
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=10^3, \alpha=5$)	522	362	1,049	1,222	3,077	4,800	0	64,793	29,125
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=10^4, \alpha=0$)	480	751	940	1,490	3,077	4,964	1,018	190,298	25,350
s_d ($c^{\text{DAC}}=10^4, \alpha=5$)	742	734	933	1,303	3,077	5,659	593	144,620	29,325

¹ aggregated values across all temperature levels

 FIGURE 9.17: Total TSA-induced error for different DAC prices and for $\alpha = 5$.

time series were aggregated together, considering MEFs instead of XEFs did not change the resulting Pareto-optimal hyperparameters at all.

When considering MEFs instead of XEFs, the total TSA-induced TAC error for $\alpha = 5$ decreased by 16% for s but increased by 121% for s_d , see Fig. 9.19.

FIGURE 9.18: Hyperparameters of Pareto-optimal aggregations for $\alpha \in \{0, \dots, 10\}$.

FIGURE 9.19: Impact of considering MEFs instead of XEFs on the total TSA-induced TAC error for $\alpha = 5$.

9.3.3 Discussion

Interdependencies & patterns. The change in MES design and operation due to increasing α values cannot be described with a single line of reasoning. Instead, the complex interrelationships cause different individual phenomena that do not form consistent patterns. Depending on the selected typical day and its assigned days, electricity generation from PV and WT is underestimated in certain months and overestimated in others, as shown in Fig. 9.7. This variability affects the required electricity purchase and its associated DAC costs in s_d . Consequently, unlike the *a priori* TSA error, the TSA-induced error cannot be estimated by interpolating between two α values and also depends on the model. Even the single CE constraint that differentiates s_d from s leads to significant changes in the *a posteriori* metrics, as illustrated in Fig. 9.14.

Impact of hyperparameter selection. An explanation for the drop in TAC between $s_d(\alpha = 6)$ and $s_d(\alpha = 7)$ is that N_G reduces from two to only one, which means completely

neglecting intraday fluctuations, as demonstrated in Fig. 9.5. So for this particular hyperparameter selection, PV production is underestimated during the daytime and overestimated at nighttime. Assuming steady demand, this would overestimate the value of PV and wind for the decarbonization and, as a consequence, underestimate the carbon removal costs.

Computation time – accuracy dilemma. In general, simplifying optimization models reduces computation time, though this principle does not apply universally in all cases, as seen in Fig. 9.8. Within this chapter, the overall computation time remains relatively low due to starting with a strongly simplified base model. For example, uncertainties, piecewise-linear approximations for costs or efficiencies, and multi-year input data were not considered. Since these are important factors for optimally designing low-carbon MESs, it is a limitation of this work. However, taking them into account can potentially result in a base model that is too complex to be solvable within a reasonable period, and in that case, no reference model would be available against which the TSA could be evaluated.

Impact of temporal simplification on costs. In the analysis of this chapter, the *total TSA-induced TAC error* remained below 15% even for a 99.99% reduction of time steps ($\alpha = 10$). This is remarkably low taking into account that only 8 typical days with a single time step each are computed for this extreme case of $\alpha = 10$. However, even the seemingly good compromise of the decarbonization case with $\alpha = 6$ and a *total TSA-induced error* of 2.0% (see Fig. 9.13) would lead to significant additional costs of over €0.7M for a 20-year period. In theory, investments in information technology infrastructure of this magnitude would pay off if they enable the original model to be calculated in an acceptable amount of time, thus avoiding the need for TSA. In reality, however, besides the so-called *total TSA-induced TAC error*, there are other errors not considered in this thesis. The original problem at hand is a two-stage stochastic optimization problem, with a 20-year operational period, typically approximated by a two-stage deterministic problem using one representative year to represent the entire probability space of the influential parameters. This approach is a significant approximation and already an implicit aggregation of the time series. The resulting question is: Will a system design that performs better for the representative year perform better across the entire solution space? Future research should focus on how we can accurately approximate the entire solution space while preserving computational tractability. These errors could either amplify the *total TSA-induced TAC error* or coincidentally diminish it. Nevertheless, the results of this chapter show that the *total TSA-induced error* does not necessarily correlate with the *assumed error* and thus proves that the *assumed error* is not a good metric for evaluating the accuracy of the identified system design and investments.

Summary. Modern low-carbon MESs are characterized by intricate interdependencies and a high degree of complexity. Reducing this complexity invariably introduces a certain level of error into the model. This creates a dilemma where we must balance the objectives of minimizing computation time and maximizing accuracy.

9.4 Conclusions

This chapter has shown that using TSA in the design optimization of MESs leads to a *hidden error*, which remains largely unexplored but can be quantified retrospectively. The results indicate that the *total error* increases not only with increasing aggregation intensity but also with increasing CE reduction ambitions. Furthermore, the analyses indicate that due to the *hidden error* the *total error* does not necessarily correlate with the *assumed error*.

The results show that TSA increasingly underestimated the required energy flexibility due to the mismatch between fluctuating renewable electricity generation and demand as aggregation increased and led to the undersizing of energy storage technologies. This does not have a large impact in the non-decarbonization case, but it does in the decarbonization case, as it means that self-supply cannot be ensured, electricity must be purchased from the grid, and CEs must be removed at a high cost. The findings that higher decarbonization ambitions lead to higher TSA errors are in line with the results of [222, 235].

Furthermore, it was shown that the impact of using MEFs instead of XEFs on the TSA-induced error highly depends on the decarbonization ambitions. While in the decarbonization scenario, using MEFs instead of XEFs more than doubled the *total TSA-induced TAC error*, in the non-decarbonization scenario, the error even slightly decreased.

In conclusion, the analyses in this chapter suggest that careful use of TSA for ambitious CE targets and self-sufficiency levels is advisable, especially when the results inform investment decisions and a model with a lower level of TSA can be solved with acceptable computational effort.

Part III

GLOBAL DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

Chapter 10

Global discussion

In this chapter, the key findings from the individual experimental studies (Part II) are comprehensively synthesized and holistically discussed. The primary objectives of the research project are systematically addressed offering a cohesive understanding.

Essence of the experimental studies. The following encapsulates the core findings and implications of the respective chapters in this work:

- Chapter 3 quantified and discussed the effects of PBDR on operational CEs in European countries. It highlighted that straightforward and common approaches like XEF calculations are unsuitable for evaluating the impact of DR on CEs. Instead, the use of MEFs, based on the concept of marginal power plants, is necessary. The merit order dilemma of CEs, where electricity prices do not necessarily align with corresponding CEs, was also addressed. Notably, in Germany in 2019, low residual load meant that dirty lignite power plants operated at the margin. This dilemma could be resolved with higher carbon prices. The study compared 20 European countries based on MEFs and XEFs, and the cost and CE reduction of price-based daily load shifts, presenting results as a theoretical potential. CE savings based on XEFs ranged from -3 to 92% (27% on average).
- Chapter 4 described and demonstrated DRAF, an open-source decision support tool for L-MESs with a focus on DR. DRAF assists in understanding the environmental and economic potential of flexible technologies, thereby reducing investment barriers. Three case studies illustrated DRAF's utility in various settings, including PBDR in production processes, design and operational optimization of BES and PV systems, and design optimization and DR of distributed thermal energy resources.

- Chapter 5 provided an in-depth analysis of the value of flexibility in decarbonizing a production company's MES, indicating significant benefits of energy flexibility through storage and sector coupling for achieving a net-zero carbon footprint.
- In Chapter 6, a MILP formulation for PBDR, applied to a cement plant, was proposed. This approach enabled dynamic machine scheduling by integrating multiple machines and sorts.
- Chapter 7 analyzed the challenges FGFs and IGU pose to the use of industrial demand-side flexibility for integrating renewable energy sources. It presented an optimized design and operation of a local energy system, including a BESS and a PVS, along with results from various model configurations.
- In Chapter 8, the impact of landing interruptions on the optimal design of an H₂ import hub was investigated using a MILP model. The study revealed that overlooking landing interruptions resulted in unmet demands and unexpectedly high follow-up costs.
- Chapter 9 demonstrated that using TSA in the design optimization of MESs introduces a 'hidden error'. This error, quantifiable in post-analysis, increased with aggregation intensity and CE reduction ambitions.

Facets of demand-side flexibility. This thesis explores various aspects of demand-side flexibility, revealing its multifaceted benefits and applications. Demand-side flexibility is instrumental in:

- Reducing CEs, particularly when integrated with an effective carbon pricing (Chapter 3).
- Lowering the decarbonization costs for companies, aiding in their transition to more sustainable practices (Chapter 5).
- Decreasing electricity purchase costs, leading to significant financial savings (Chapter 6).
- Minimizing grid fees, thus contributing to the overall reduction in energy expenditure (Chapter 7).
- Enhancing system resiliency, ensuring more robust and reliable energy supply (Chapter 8).

Alignment with primary objectives. Section 1.3 outlined four primary objectives for this thesis, following a thorough review of the existing literature in the field. The first objective involved developing a methodology for computing dynamic electricity MEFs

and XEFs for European countries to approximate the impact of DR on CEs (Chapter 3). The second objective analyzed the influence of PBDR on CEs across different European countries and varying carbon pricing scenarios (Chapter 3). The third objective, addressed in Chapter 4, revolved around creating and demonstrating a modular open-source optimization framework. This framework was designed to comprehensively evaluate the PBDR potential of an L-MES, identifying its optimal design and operational strategies for targeted CE reduction. The fourth objective, spanning Chapters 5 to 8, applied this framework to multiple non-residential case studies, thereby determining their individual economic and environmental DR potential. Lastly, the fifth objective, which evaluated the suitability of using TSA for low-carbon industrial L-MES models in the context of DR, was covered in Chapter 9. Collectively, the research objectives set out in Section 1.3 have been successfully achieved, effectively addressing the identified gaps in the field.

Interconnections of chapters, methodologies, and tools. Each chapter of this thesis examines a distinct dimension of the economic and environmental evaluation of non-residential DR in Europe’s transition towards zero-carbon energy. However, the chapters, methodologies, tools, and analyses are interconnected and cumulative, as illustrated in the overarching structure in Fig. 1.2. Chapter 3 proposed a novel methodology to calculate dynamic CEFs. This methodology was implemented in an open-source Python software, Elmada. Elmada’s source code, usage of clean code, automated tests, and documentation were peer-reviewed and published in JOSS (see [261], Appendix C). Elmada played a pivotal role in analyzing the impact of DR on CEs and was further integrated into DRAF, as described in Chapter 4. Subsequently, DRAF and the CEFs provided by Elmada were applied to various case studies (Appendix C, Chapter 5, Chapter 6, Chapter 7, and Chapter 8), enhancing the knowledge of DR’s impact in diverse scenarios. In Chapter 9, DRAF was expanded with the DRAF TSA module and applied to a modified version of the case study from Chapter 5. This extension aimed to assess TSA’s effectiveness for decarbonized L-MES considering PBDR, with MEFs and XEFs calculated by Elmada used to test their influence on TSA’s adequacy. Collectively, the results presented in this thesis align with the research objectives set out in Section 1.3, substantiating a comprehensive approach to investigating the economic and environmental aspects of non-residential DR within Europe’s transition to zero-carbon energy.

Environmental evaluation of DR. DR is a key element for the transition to zero-carbon energy since it helps integrate vRESs into electricity systems by providing operational flexibility in a cost-effective way. Therefore, it is obvious that DR significantly contributes to climate protection and the environment. However, quantifying the effect of a specific load change on CEs is challenging for two reasons. Firstly, in national electricity systems,

electricity is generated from power plants with different CE intensities, and electrical flows cannot be traced from generation to consumption. This implies that accurately measuring the CE intensity for generating a specific amount of electrical energy demand is not possible. Secondly, to quantify the effect of a load change, it must be compared to a counterfactual base scenario that did not happen. In the environmental evaluation of DR, therefore, two pivotal questions arise:

1. How can the effect of DR on operational CEs be approximated?
2. How can DR be actively utilized to reduce operational CEs?

To address the first question, dynamic CEFs are required. More specifically, dynamic MEFs are necessary, as dynamic XEFs are not adequate for assessing the effect of load change on CEs, as demonstrated in Fig. 3.1. Calculating historic MEFs is complex and data-intensive, especially when not all necessary data are available. However, for reducing CEs through DR (question 2), relying solely on historic MEFs is insufficient. Instead, accurate MEF forecasts, calculated under uncertain electricity system conditions, are essential. Nevertheless, with rapid advancements in big data, machine learning, and digitalization, this task seems feasible.

Interconnections of investigated aspects. In the modeling of non-residential DR potentials, this work focused on the investigation of the following aspects:

1. The holistic consideration of different flexible assets
2. The costs and CEs
3. The use of dynamic MEFs and XEFs
4. The consideration of investments to increase flexibility
5. The utilization of TSA to reduce model complexity

There are several interconnections between these aspects, which are discussed as follows:

- **Interconnections between various flexible loads.** The flexible loads are interconnected through energy or material flows and depend on each other. For example, a CHP unit, a HP, and a production process may be interconnected through both thermal and electrical energy flows.
- **Interconnections between CEs and costs of DR.** There are multiple linkages between costs (economic evaluation) and CEs (environmental evaluation). In electricity generation from vRES, there is a natural link between cost and CEs, as vRES typically have both low operating costs and low CEs. In pay-as-cleared markets, market participants are incentivized to bid their marginal costs, making this natural correlation visible through wholesale electricity prices. For fossil energy sources, a carbon price (e.g., via the European Union Emissions Trading System) creates an

artificial positive link between costs and CEs. Chapter 3 analyzes the required level of carbon pricing to effectively rearrange the merit order. As demonstrated in Chapter 5, costs and CEs can also be linked through carbon removal costs.

- **Interconnections between resiliency and flexibility.** Resilience and flexibility are intrinsically linked, each playing a crucial role in strengthening the other. Enhancing a system's flexibility directly contributes to its resilience, especially when flexibility is strategically used to manage extreme events. Conversely, designing a resilient system requires integrating flexibility, particularly for dealing with extreme events that can be anticipated with a certain degree of probability. In such scenarios, the system's built-in flexibility can be repurposed for additional objectives, such as optimizing operational costs, thereby maximizing efficiency. The importance of detailed information about potential extreme events is paramount. With comprehensive knowledge, the flexibilities built into a system can be more effectively tailored and deployed for alternative uses. A pertinent example, highlighted in Chapter 8, is the strategic use of an ammonia storage system. Originally designed to address supply interruptions, this system can be repurposed during periods when such extreme events are improbable, thus optimizing the system's functionality.
- **Interconnections between DR potential identification and TSA.** The accuracy of estimates for DR potential in renewable MESs can be enhanced by eliminating simplifications in the model, such as considering part-load behavior or cost functions. However, this increases model complexity. To maintain practical computation times, this complexity can be reduced in other model parts, such as by temporally aggregating input time series using TSA methods.

Environmental impact of this work. This research project has significantly contributed to a more sustainable future in several ways. The analyses in Chapter 3 highlighted the differences between MEFs and XEFs and explained the relationship between carbon pricing and the environmental assessment of PBDR. This comparative analysis of 20 countries illustrates the varying impacts of DR on CEs across different nations. In Chapter 5, the research demonstrated how incorporating demand-side flexibility and DR in the planning or retrofit stages of L-MESs can reduce decarbonization costs for companies, potentially leading to more ambitious CE reduction goals. The research conducted in Chapter 8 emphasized the importance of anticipating and considering increased extreme weather events during the planning of green energy hubs to ensure their robustness and cost-effective operation.

Chapter 11

Global conclusions

This chapter provides a cohesive overview of the dissertation’s collective insights. The overarching goal of this thesis was to develop methods and tools for evaluating the environmental and economic potential of non-residential DR and to apply these tools to real-world case studies within the context of Europe’s transition to zero-carbon energy. By achieving this goal, this thesis fills several gaps in the existing literature. These gaps, listed in Section 2.6, were identified following a comprehensive literature review.

In addition to the conclusions drawn in the individual experimental studies, the following global conclusions can be drawn:

1. **Importance of energy flexibility.** The findings of this thesis highlight the significance of DR, specifically PBDR, in reducing operational CEs and costs for non-residential L-MES operators. The value of the flexibility of L-MESs, enabled by storage technologies, sector coupling, or flexible production processes, is identified as a key factor in decarbonizing energy systems, particularly for industrial applications.
2. **Evaluation of DR-induced CEs.** The analyses differentiated and provided methodologies for evaluating the CEs associated with DR. Furthermore, they clarified how the carbon price influences PBDR and its associated CEs in the electricity systems.
3. **Two proposed tools.** Two pieces of software were developed as part of this PhD thesis: Elmada and DRAF. Elmada lays the foundation for the environmental evaluation of DR by providing dynamic electricity CEFs for European countries. DRAF, in contrast, is a modular framework designed to facilitate the modeling of L-MESs for DR potential quantification and decision support. Various analyses and case studies presented in this document have demonstrated that combining these two tools can effectively quantify the economic and environmental value of non-residential DR for L-MESs.

4. **Limits of advanced modeling.** This research project advocates for advanced modeling techniques to accurately capture the complexities of modern MESs in investment decision support and DR potential quantification. However, the findings of this dissertation suggest that when considering DR, vRES, and corporate CE neutrality goals, it is important to apply the TSA approach cautiously, especially if the outcomes are used for investment decision-making and if the non-aggregated model can be resolved within a reasonable computational effort.
5. **Challenges and opportunities in vRES integration.** The document underscores that the structure of existing grid fees hinders the adoption of vRES and DR in non-residential MESs. However, it also points out the opportunities that arise from overcoming these challenges, such as the potential for significant environmental and economic benefits. This implies a need for policies and market structures that support the adoption of vRES and DR.
6. **Risk of oversights in energy system design.** The analysis of landing interruptions of hydrogen import hubs and the discussion of 'hidden errors' in TSA highlight the risks associated with oversights in the design and optimization of energy systems. These findings stress the importance of comprehensive modeling and consideration of various factors to avoid costly mistakes or inefficiencies.
7. **Interdisciplinary approach for optimal solutions.** The diverse range of topics covered, from mathematical modeling to policy analyses, underpins the necessity of an interdisciplinary approach in addressing the challenges of modern energy systems. This approach enables a more holistic understanding and effective solutions that encompass technical, economic, and regulatory aspects.

In summary, this research provides means to measure and improve DR-induced cost and CE reductions. It demonstrates how demand-side flexibility can be used to reduce CEs in both the electricity system and the local non-residential energy systems. Furthermore, the study contributes to unlocking and expanding the potential of large-scale DR by reducing the barriers to adoption. This is achieved by providing methods and tools to quantify specific DR potentials and to support investment decisions. The study collectively illustrates the complexity and interconnectedness of issues in modern energy systems and calls for an integrated approach that considers technical, economic, and legislative factors to effectively transition towards sustainable energy systems.

Chapter 12

Limitations and future work

This chapter outlines the limitations of the study and discusses potential avenues for expanding the research introduced in this dissertation.

Calculating CEFs

1. **Consideration of cross-border energy flows for MEFs.** As did all studies presented in Table 2.1, this thesis did not consider transnational power flows in the calculation of MEFs since there is no existing available method to do so. Commercial entities like Tomorrow [183, 336] provide estimated MEFs considering cross border flows, however their method is not published. Due to these two limitations, the MEFs calculated in this chapter are subject to an unquantified level of uncertainty. However, the authors deem this to be reasonably low due to the high number of empirically derived parameters factored into the analyses of this thesis. In future research, the interconnectivity of individual countries to form a large interconnected network should be investigated, as this is an increasingly important aspect, which was however outside the scope of this thesis. Furthermore, dynamic MEFs may be used for the assessment of the environmental potential of PBDR in real case studies considering technical, organizational, and process-related constraints in a realistic way.
2. **Life cycle assessment approaches for XEFs.** The focus of this work was on the calculation of MEFs to evaluate the short-term effects of PBDR on CEs. Consequently, direct fuel-specific CE intensities were used in the calculation, see Table 3.2. These CE intensities do not include indirect CEs such as the CEs embodied in infrastructure and power plants. However, from an attributional perspective (i.e., using XEFs instead of MEFs), life cycle assessment approaches could be applied to also consider long-term

effects on CEs. For this, indirect fuel-specific CE intensities should be used in the calculation process.

3. **Fundamental electricity grid modeling.** For the calculation of CEFs, an economic power plant dispatch was simulated using historical electricity generation data. The historical data already includes redispatch measures, technical outages, and international electricity trading. However, this data was only included in the simulation in an aggregated form, which may lead to an unrealistic simulation of the dispatch. Ideally, to simulate dispatch decisions accurately, a comprehensive agent-based and game-theoretical model of the electricity network, accounting for power flows, would be required. This advanced modeling was beyond the scope of this study due to its substantial complexity and effort. The limitations' impact on the findings of this work is considered marginal, as the study primarily quantifies the current potential of individual L-MESs, presumed to be price-takers without significant load change feedback effects on the overall electricity system. However, these limitations become more critical when assessing future potentials or under markedly different market conditions.

Modeling DR

4. **Further case studies.** In this document, DRAF is applied to different industrial case studies. To evaluate the full potential of industrial DR, the interdependencies and synergies of combining demand-side flexibility from industrial processes with cross-sectional technologies such as power-to-heat should be analysed in depth. In future work, DRAF could be used to model such detailed case studies.
5. **Uncertainty.** In this research project, perfect foresight is assumed for all input time series. Future research endeavors could involve implementing myopic and stochastic modeling in a rolling horizon fashion.
6. **Intraday trading and reserve markets.** In this thesis, an economic and environmental assessment of non-residential DR is conducted considering peak-shaving, self-consumption optimization, and PBDR based on the day-ahead market price. In future works, the models could be extended by considering other electricity flexibility markets such as reserve and intraday markets in a cross-market optimization.
7. **Battery degradation.** In this thesis, battery degradation is limited by constraining the minimum and maximum state of charge but not explicitly modeled.
8. **Grid congestion.** This thesis analyzes the potential of PBDR from a consumer perspective. However, it should be noted that when many flexible electricity consumers respond to the same DR signal, simultaneous demand spikes in the electricity system

may occur. Such a phenomenon, similar to the peak-rebound effect of load-shedding programs, where initial reductions in electricity demand are followed by a sharp increase, can strain the grid infrastructure and lead to network congestion, potentially causing failures or necessitating costly emergency measures. Dynamic and region-specific network charges, along with cooperation between flexible consumers and distribution system operators, could mitigate the peak-rebound issue by incentivizing smoother and more distributed patterns of energy consumption.

Adequacy of TSA

9. **Analysis of the year-selection error.** In this dissertation, the application of TSA methods is investigated within the design of MESs. Typically, for such design optimization problems, a design year is chosen that represents the entire optimization horizon for multiple years. The selection of the representative year itself can be considered as a form of temporal aggregation, which also induces an error. Since the analysis of this error exceeds the scope of this thesis, it is assumed that the year picked is representative for all years in the optimization horizon. Therefore, future analyses may involve the quantification of the error of picking one year instead of taking all available information for future years into account.

Ethical issues

This research did not directly involve human or live animal subjects. No humans were monitored or recorded. The handling of all data within this research project was in line with MTU and GDPR guidelines.

Calculation methods and optimization models were published within open-source repositories on GitHub to ensure transparency and reproducibility.

Part IV

APPENDIX

Appendix A

Publications

Research findings of this PhD project have been published in peer-reviewed articles:

Journal publications:

1. M. Bohlayer, **M. Fleschutz**, M. Braun, G. & Zöttl (**2020**). Energy-intense production-inventory planning with participation in sequential energy markets. *Applied Energy*, 258(June 2019).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.113954> [76]
2. M. Bohlayer, A. Bürger, **M. Fleschutz**, M. Braun, & G. Zöttl (**2021**). Multi-period investment pathways - Modeling approaches to design distributed energy systems under uncertainty. *Applied Energy*, 285(December 2020), 116368.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.116368> [281]
3. **M. Fleschutz**, M. Bohlayer, M. Braun, G. Henze, & M. D. Murphy (**2021**). The effect of price-based demand response on carbon emissions in European electricity markets: The importance of adequate carbon prices. *Applied Energy*, 295(May), 117040.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.117040> [240]
4. **M. Fleschutz** & M. D. Murphy (**2021**). elmada: Dynamic electricity carbon emission factors and prices for Europe. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 6(66), 3625.
<https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.03625> [261]
5. **M. Fleschutz**, M. Bohlayer, M. Braun, & M. D. Murphy (**2022**). Demand Response Analysis Framework (DRAF): An Open-Source Multi-Objective Decision Support Tool for Decarbonizing Local Multi-Energy Systems. *Sustainability*, 14(13), 8025.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su14138025> [209]
6. A. Leippi, **M. Fleschutz**, & M. D. Murphy (**2022**). A Review of EV Battery Utilization in Demand Response Considering Battery Degradation in Non-Residential Vehicle-to-Grid Scenarios. *Energies*. 15(9):3227.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/en15093227> [95]

7. **M. Fleschutz**, M. Bohlayer, M. Braun, & M. D. Murphy (2023). From prosumer to flexumer: Case study on the value of flexibility in decarbonizing the multi-energy system of a manufacturing company. *Applied Energy*, 347(October), 121430.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.121430> [287]
8. A. Leippi, **M. Fleschutz**, K. Davis, A. Klingler, & M. D. Murphy (2024). Optimizing electric vehicle fleet integration in industrial demand response: Maximizing vehicle-to-grid benefits while compensating vehicle owners for battery degradation. *Applied Energy*, 374(November), 123995.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.123995> [337]
9. **M. Fleschutz**, M. Bohlayer, M. Braun, & M. D. Murphy (Working Paper). The hidden cost of using time series aggregation for modeling low-carbon industrial energy systems: An investors' perspective.
<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4796211> [329]

Conference proceedings:

1. **M. Fleschutz**, M. Bohlayer, A. Bürger, & M. Braun (2017). Electricity Cost Reduction Potential of Industrial Processes using Real Time Pricing in a Production Planning Problem. Collaborative European Research Conference (CERC).
<https://perma.cc/2XT6-47JL> [285]
2. **M. Fleschutz**, A. Leippi, M. Bohlayer, M. Braun, & M. D. Murphy (2022). Industrial grid fees vs. demand response: A case study of a multi-use battery in a German chemical plant. Conference on the European Energy Market 2022.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/EEM54602.2022.9921156> [303]
3. **M. Fleschutz**, D. Bull, M. Braun, & M. D. Murphy (2023). Impact of Landing Interruptions on the Optimal Design and Operation of Green Hydrogen Hubs. IEEE ISGT Europe 2023. 2023 IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Europe (ISGT EUROPE) Conference
<https://doi.org/10.1109/isgteurope56780.2023.10408039> [312]

Appendix B

Appendix to Chapter 3 (Effect of PBDR on carbon emissions)

B.1 ENTSOE data

	AT	BA	BE	BG	CH	CZ	DE	DK	EE	ES	FI	FR	GB	GR	HU	IE	IT	LT	LV	ME	MK	NL	NO	PL	PT	RO	RS	SE	SI	SK		
Wind Onshore	35040	8760	8760	8760	8750	35037	8760	8753	8755	8760	8751	17507	8740	33691	17472	8759	8730	8735	8731	7615	34388	8759	8760	8760	8635	-	8760	8729	8760			
Wind Offshore	-	8760	-	-	-	35040	8760	-	8755	-	-	17507	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	34802	-	-	-	-	-	-	-			
Waste	35040	-	8760	8760	-	8757	35040	8760	8755	8755	8760	8751	-	35038	-	8760	8730	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8729		
Solar	35040	-	8760	8760	8760	8758	35040	8760	8753	8755	-	8751	17507	8740	9604	-	8760	8730	-	-	-	-	-	34771	-	-	8760	8635	-	8742	8760	
Other renewable	35040	-	-	-	-	8758	35040	-	8755	8755	8760	-	-	35036	-	-	-	-	-	8731	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8760		
Other	35040	-	8760	-	-	8758	35040	-	8755	8755	8760	-	17466	-	35038	17472	8592	8730	8735	-	-	-	34726	8759	-	8760	-	8760	8760	-	8760	
Nuclear	-	-	8760	8760	8760	8758	35040	-	-	8755	8760	8751	17466	-	35038	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	33642	-	-	-	8635	-	8760	8729	8760	
Marine	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Hydro Water Reservoir	35040	8708	-	8760	8760	8759	35040	-	-	8755	-	8751	-	8758	35038	-	8760	-	-	8731	-	-	8759	8760	8760	8642	8760	8760	-	-	8760	
Hydro Run-of-river and pondage	35040	-	8760	8760	8760	8758	35040	-	8755	8755	8760	8751	17466	-	35038	17472	8760	8730	8735	-	7603	34771	8759	8760	8760	8642	8760	-	-	8729	8760	
Hydro Pumped Storage	35040	-	8760	8760	8760	8758	35040	-	8755	-	8751	17466	8758	-	-	17472	8760	8730	-	-	-	-	-	-	8760	8760	-	8760	-	-	8729	8760
Geothermal	35040	-	-	-	-	-	35040	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8760	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Fossil Peat	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8755	8755	8760	-	-	-	-	-	17472	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Fossil Oil shale	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8755	8755	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Fossil Oil	35040	-	8760	-	-	8758	35040	8760	-	8755	8760	8751	17466	8758	32639	17472	8736	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8760	-	-	-	8729	8760
Fossil Hard coal	35040	8708	4645	8760	-	8759	35040	8760	-	8755	8760	8751	17466	-	-	17472	8760	-	-	-	-	-	33689	-	-	8760	8760	8635	-	-	8760	
Fossil Gas	35040	-	8760	8760	-	8759	35040	8760	8755	8755	8760	8751	17466	8758	35038	17472	8736	8730	8735	-	-	-	34771	8759	8760	8760	8635	8760	-	-	8729	8760
Fossil Coal-derived gas	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8208	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Fossil Brown coal/Lignite	-	8708	-	8760	-	8758	35040	-	-	8755	-	-	-	8758	35038	-	-	-	-	-	8731	7603	-	-	-	8760	-	8635	8760	-	8729	8760
Biomass	35040	-	8760	8760	-	8758	35040	8760	8755	8755	8760	8751	17466	-	35038	-	8760	8730	8735	-	-	34683	-	8760	8760	8635	8760	-	-	8729	8760	

FIGURE B.1: Number of available national generation data points available on the ENTSOE Transparency Platform [242] for European countries in 2019.

	AL	AT	BA	BE	BG	CH	CZ	DE	DK	EE	ES	FI	FR	GB	GR	HR	HU	IE	IT	LT	LU	LV	ME	MK	NL	NO	PL	PT	RO	RS	SE	SI	
Wind Onshore	-	14	2	10	5	-	2	24	28	16	22	12	10	12	14	12	4	20	10	15	147	2	12	2	12	4	14	26	16	4	18	0	
Wind Offshore	-	0	-	7	-	-	3	11	0	0	0	0	0	9	-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	-	0	-	-	-	0		
Waste	-	1	-	2	0	-	0	1	2	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	0	1	8	-	-	-	2	-	-	0	-	-	-	1		
Solar	-	-	-	15	8	-	10	20	6	1	6	0	6	13	14	1	10	-	5	2	0	-	-	-	13	-	1	2	6	0	-	7	
Other renewable	-	0	-	-	-	-	2	0	1	0	0	1	-	2	0	1	1	-	0	0	0	-	-	-	0	-	0	-	-	-	-	0	
Other	-	0	-	0	-	-	0	1	-	0	0	2	0	4	-	-	7	1	4	-	-	-	-	-	0	0	0	-	0	21	0		
Nuclear	-	0	-	26	16	21	19	4	-	0	7	16	48	9	-	21	-	-	-	0	0	-	-	-	2	-	0	0	7	-	21	19	
Marine	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	-	0	-	-	-	-	0	
Hydro Water Reservoir	-	11	53	-	14	34	4	1	-	0	18	-	6	14	29	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	35	31	0	9	0	8	18	4	40	0
Hydro Run-of-river and pondage	100	26	-	1	4	4	2	2	0	0	1	18	8	2	2	8	0	2	11	4	9	54	31	-	0	3	1	15	15	21	-	28	
Hydro Pumped Storage	-	15	-	6	7	41	6	4	-	0	5	-	4	3	4	6	-	3	8	25	0	-	-	-	0	-	4	14	-	7	-	5	
Geothermal	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	0	-	-	-	-	0	0	0	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
Fossil Peat	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	7	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
Fossil Oil shale	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	63	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
Fossil Oil	-	1	-	1	-	-	0	2	6	1	8	3	0	0	19	5	13	2	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	0	-	1	0	-	-	2	0
Fossil Hard coal	-	3	21	2	3	-	6	11	23	0	9	13	3	8	-	7	-	9	5	0	-	-	-	-	15	-	52	9	5	-	-	0	
Fossil Gas	-	21	-	29	10	-	6	14	11	4	29	11	9	35	29	15	44	43	49	47	31	39	-	16	51	2	5	23	16	3	-	13	
Fossil Coal-derived gas	-	0	-	-	-	-	2	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
Fossil Brown coal/Lignite	-	0	24	-	32	-	41	10	0	0	-	-	-	23	-	12	-	0	-	0	-	-	-	21	51	0	-	19	0	16	60	-	25
Biomass	0	2	-	3	1	-	2	3	11	6	0	10	1	4	0	1	3	-	2	3	1	4	-	-	2	-	2	3	1	0	-	0	

FIGURE B.2: Available national installed generation capacity data available on the ENTSOE Transparency Platform [242] for European countries in 2019.

To save space for the following diagrams, the following renaming and aggregation was conducted: biomass=Biomass, lignite=Fossil Brown coal/Lignite, oil=Fossil Oil, gas=Fossil Gas, coal=Fossil

Hard coal, pumped_hydro=Hydro Pumped Storage, hydro=Hydro Run-of-river and poundage, nuclear=Nuclear, solar=Solar, wind_offshore=Wind Offshore, wind_onshore=Wind Onshore, other_CONV = Other + other_conventional + Fossil Coal-derived gas + Fossil Oil shale + Fossil Peat, other_RES = Waste + Geothermal + Hydro Water Reservoir + Marine + Other renewable + other renewables.

FIGURE B.3: Residual load per installed conventional capacity in 2019 for analyzed countries.

FIGURE B.4: Shares of renewable vs. conventional generation in 2019 for analyzed countries.

B.2 Analysis of German generation data

FIGURE B.5: Average power generation per fuel type and year in Germany. Data: ENTSOE Transparency Platform [242].

FIGURE B.6: Normalized violin plots of German electricity generation technologies for the years 2015–2019. Data: ENTSOE Transparency Platform [242].

FIGURE B.7: Top: Stacked-area plot of German conventional electricity generation for the year 2019 sorted by ascending residual load. Bottom: Individual line plots for each conventional technology.

FIGURE B.8: Top: German conventional electricity generation for the year 2019. Bottom: Linear regression analysis for each generation technology where r is the spearman correlation coefficient and R^2 is the coefficient of determination.

B.3 OPSD power plant list

FIGURE B.9: Net generation capacity and power plant efficiency distribution of all in 2019 available conventional power plants from OPSD [247].

B.4 GEO power plant list

FIGURE B.10: Average power plant sizes used in PWL method. The average values at the bottom were used where no data were available (indicated with "-"). Data source: [248].

B.5 Outliers and special missing data

TABLE B.1: Handling of outliers and special missing data in national electricity generation data.

Country	Fuel type	Timestamp(s)	z-Score	Type	Treatment
CZ	Hydro Run-of-river and poundage	2018-05-24 12:00	>40	outlier	as missing value
DK	Waste	2019-11-04 08:00	>90	outlier	as missing value
HU	Other renewable	2019-12-04 13:00, 2019-12-04 13:15	>18	outlier	as missing value
LT	Other	2018-01-07 08:00	>90	outlier	as missing value
LT	Solar	2018-10-24 15:00, 2018-10-26 11:00, 2018-10-26 12:00	>12	outlier	as missing value
SI	Waste	2019-11-04 08:00	>90	outlier	as missing value
NL	All	2018-12-31 23:00		no data	data of previous hour is used.
NL	All	2019-01-01 (whole day)		no data	data of next sunday is used.

B.6 Reasons for exclusion of countries from analyses

TABLE B.2: Exclusion reasons for European countries that were excluded from the analyses.

Reason	Countries
No generation data available	AD, AL, AM, AZ, BY, CY, FO, GE, GI, HR, IS, KZ, LI, LU, MC, MD, MT, RU, SM, TR, UA, VA, XK
Only one fossil fuel-type available	coal: BA; nuclear: CH, SE; gas: NO, LV; lignite: MK, ME; other_conv: EE
No installed capacity for 2019 available	BG, SK

B.7 Validation

FIGURE B.11: Comparison of methods to calculate MEFs. For each method (PP method left and PWLv method right) the hourly MEFs for Germany for the year 2019 are shown as scatter plot (top) and as heatmap (bottom). While in the scatter plot the range of values of the two resulting MEFs can be compared well, the heatmaps clearly show the similar daily and seasonal patterns, especially for times in winter where gas_cc power plants kick in due to high residual load.

B.8 Merit orders for the years 2017–2019

2017

FIGURE B.12: Merit orders of for analyzed European countries resulting from PWL-method for the year 2017.

2018

FIGURE B.13: Merit orders of for analyzed European countries resulting from PWL-method for the year 2018.

2019

FIGURE B.14: Merit orders of for analyzed European countries resulting from PWL-method for the year 2019.

B.9 Correlation of prices and CEFs for the years 2017–2019

FIGURE B.15: Scatter plots of German CEFs (from top to bottom: XEFs^{PP} , $\text{XEFs}^{\text{PWLv}}$, MEFs^{PP} , $\text{MEFs}^{\text{PWLv}}$) and prices (left: marginal cost from simulation, right: historic day-ahead market prices from the ENTSOE Transparency Platform [242]) for the year 2017. The Spearman correlation coefficient r is displayed in the lower right corner.

FIGURE B.16: Scatter plots of German CEFs (from top to bottom: $XEFs^{PP}$, $XEFs^{PWLv}$, $MEFs^{PP}$, $MEFs^{PWLv}$) and prices (left: marginal cost from simulation, right: historic day-ahead market prices from the ENTSOE Transparency Platform [242]) for the year 2018. The Spearman correlation coefficient r is given in the lower right corner.

FIGURE B.17: Scatter plots of German CEFs (from top to bottom: $XEFs^{PP}$, $XEFs^{PWLv}$, $MEFs^{PP}$, $MEFs^{PWLv}$) and prices (left: marginal cost from simulation, right: historic day-ahead market prices from the ENTSOE Transparency Platform [242]) for the year 2019. The Spearman correlation coefficient r is given in the lower right corner.

B.10 Load shift analysis

FIGURE B.18: Relative changes in cost and carbon emissions of the shifted energy for 2017–2019 and for different European countries. The grid mix and marginal carbon emissions are based on XEF^{PWL} and MEF^{PWL} respectively.

FIGURE B.19: Distribution of the number of daily marginal fuel type changes for 2019.

FIGURE B.20: Box plots of the daily prices and CEFs for 2019. Outliers were removed for this plot for better readability.

Carbon price[€/ t]

	0.0	5.8	16.0	24.9	42.6	65.3	100.0	156.1	235.6	1269.5	10000.0
oil⇒oil	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-
oil⇒lignite	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-
oil⇒gas_cc	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	2
oil⇒gas	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	20
oil⇒coal	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9	10
lignite⇒lignite	78	78	76	77	28	39	26	31	7	-	-
lignite⇒gas_cc	-	-	-	-	8	42	40	47	7	1	-
lignite⇒gas	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7	19	10	6
lignite⇒coal	-	-	1	13	33	51	70	66	41	15	10
gas⇒lignite	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	10	2	-	-
gas⇒gas_cc	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	45	101	109
gas⇒gas	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	16	26	21
gas⇒coal	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	16	29	4	4
gas_cc⇒lignite	1	1	2	8	33	31	1	-	-	-	-
gas_cc⇒gas_cc	-	-	-	3	9	25	21	12	12	12	12
gas_cc⇒coal	15	15	18	22	58	27	-	-	-	-	-
coal⇒oil	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4
coal⇒lignite	198	198	194	153	138	58	62	9	1	1	-
coal⇒gas_cc	-	-	-	-	10	49	98	100	104	52	45
coal⇒gas	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	23	93	108
coal⇒coal	73	73	74	89	48	43	40	53	61	35	14

FIGURE B.21: Frequency of load shift events per carbon price and marginal fuel type combination (denoted in the form $f^{\text{source}} \Rightarrow f^{\text{sink}}$) for Germany in 2019.

2017

FIGURE B.22: Merit orders and load shift analysis of analyzed European countries resulting from PWL-method for the year 2017: **a)** Merit order with marginal prices c_p^m (left) and emission intensities ε_p (right), **b)** histogram of residual load P_t^{resi} , **c)** load shifts of all days of the year (squares indicating sources and triangles indicating sinks), and **d)** inverted load duration curves of sources (right) and sinks (left)). The x-axis (net generation power in GW_{el}) is shared across the four subplots.

2018

FIGURE B.23: Merit orders and load shift analysis of analyzed European countries resulting from PWL-method for the year 2018: **a)** Merit order with marginal prices c_p^m (left) and emission intensities ε_p (right), **b)** histogram of residual load P_t^{resi} , **c)** load shifts of all days of the year (squares indicating sources and triangles indicating sinks), and **d)** inverted load duration curves of sources (right) and sinks (left)). The x-axis (net generation power in GW_{el}) is shared across the four subplots.

2019

FIGURE B.24: Merit orders and load shift analysis of analyzed European countries resulting from PWL-method for the year 2019: **a)** Merit order with marginal prices c_p^m (left) and emission intensities ε_p (right), **b)** histogram of residual load P_t^{resi} , **c)** load shifts of all days of the year (squares indicating sources and triangles indicating sinks), and **d)** inverted load duration curves of sources (right) and sinks (left)). The x-axis (net generation power in GW_{el}) is shared across the four subplots.

B.11 Description of the remaining 14 countries

In this section, all values refer to the year 2019 and all superlatives to the 20 countries analyzed in Chapter 3. Gas includes also gas_cc.

Austria (AT). Austria has the highest RES share (74%) after Denmark (77%), and with 45%, the highest hydro share. The main fossil energy sources are gas_cc and coal. The fluctuation of the residual load compared to the aggregated installed capacity is high and features a pronounced seasonal pattern. Price-based load shifts led to reductions of 24% in cost and 53% in grid mix emissions but to an increase of 11% in (marginal) emissions. Most fuel type combinations were gas_cc-to-gas_cc (179) and gas_cc-to-coal (130).

Belgium (BE). In Belgium, the main fuel types for electricity production are nuclear (47%), gas (27%), wind (9%), and solar (4%). Price-based load shifting led to reductions of 6% in cost, 45% in grid mix emissions, and to 7% in (marginal) emissions. 330 (90%) load shifts were gas_cc-to-gas_cc.

Czech Republic (CZ). In the Czech Republic, the main fuel types are lignite (39%) and nuclear (35%). The load shifting simulations showed 354 lignite-to-lignite and 11 coal-to-lignite load shifts. The resulting reductions were 6% for cost, 21% for grid mix emissions, and 5% for (marginal) emissions. 354 (97%) load shifts were lignite-to-lignite, 11 (3%) were coal-to-lignite.

Spain (ES). Spain is mainly powered by gas (31%), nuclear (22%), and wind_onshore (21%). The load shifting simulations showed that the cost reduced only by 4%, the grid mix emission reduced by 10%, but (marginal) emission increased by 25%. The emission increase is mainly caused by 144 (39%) gas_cc-to-coal shifts.

Finland (FI). In Finland, nuclear (38%), hydro (19%), biomass (10%), and wind_onshore (9%) are the most utilized fuel types. The results of the load shifting simulations were a 10% reduction in cost and grid mix emissions and a 4% reduction in (marginal) emissions. The emissions did not increase since only 51 (14%) load shifts (gas_cc-to-coal) were not beneficial from an emissions perspective.

United Kingdom (GB). In the United Kingdom, the main fuel types are gas (45%), nuclear (21%), and wind (18%). Price-based load shifting led to reductions of 16% in cost, 57% in grid mix emissions, and 3% in (marginal) emissions. The most frequent fuel type combinations were gas_cc-to-coal (114) and gas_cc-to-gas_cc (108).

Hungary (HU). Hungary features a low RES share of 8%. The most utilized fuel types are nuclear (51%), gas (25%), and lignite (14%). From load shifting, both cost and grid mix emission

decreased by 13%. However, (marginal) emissions increased by 31%. The emission increase is mainly caused by 129 gas_cc-to-lignite shifts.

Italy (IT). Italy shows a diversified electricity supply system. The most utilized fuel types are gas (44%), hydro (13%), wind (8%), solar (7%), and coal (7%). The load shifting simulations showed low reductions in cost (4%), grid mix emissions (3%), and (marginal) emissions (4%). The main fuel type combination gas_cc-to-gas_cc occurred 335 times (92%).

Lithuania (LT). Lithuania is the country with the highest pumped hydro share (17%). The other main fuel types are wind_onshore (39%), biomass (12%), and gas (11%). Reductions from price-based load shifting were low in the case of cost (3%) and (marginal) emissions (3%) but high in the case of grid mix emissions (53%). All load shifts were gas-to-gas.

Netherlands (NL). The Netherlands has the lowest RES share (7%) and the highest gas share (49%). Besides other_conv (21%), coal has also a considerable share (19%). The results of the load shifting simulations were reductions of 5% in cost, 1% in grid mix emissions, and 5% in (marginal) emissions. 71% of load shifts remained within the fuel type gas_cc.

Portugal (PT). The main fuel types in Portugal are gas (33%), wind (27%), hydro (11%), and coal (11%). Load shifting simulations led to a 14% reduction in cost, a 20% reduction in grid mix emissions, but a 22% increase in (marginal) emissions. The emission increase is mainly caused by 150 gas_cc-to-coal load shifts.

Romania (RO). In Romania, the most utilized fuel types for electricity production are lignite (22%), nuclear (19%), hydro (18%), gas (16%) Through load shifting, cost and grid mix emissions decreased by 11% and 22%, respectively while the (marginal) emissions increased by 4%. This slight increase of emissions is due to 112 coal-to-lignite load shifts.

Serbia (RS). Serbia features the highest lignite share (68%). However, Hydro (26%) is also a main fuel type. The effects of the price-based load shifting simulations were -3% cost, +3% grid mix emissions, and -3% (marginal) emissions. A possible explanation for the unintuitive increase of mix emissions of Serbia can be found in Chapter 3.

Slovenia (SI). In Slovenia, the main fuel types are nuclear (37%), hydro (29%), and lignite (27%). The load shifting simulations resulted in reductions of 19% in cost, 27% in grid mix emissions, and 13% in (marginal) emissions. 81% of load shifts remained within the fuel type lignite.

Appendix C

Elmada: Dynamic electricity carbon emission factors and prices for Europe (JOSS paper)

Abstract. The expansion of intermittent renewable energy sources such as solar and wind requires increased operational flexibility in electricity systems. Energy system models at the scale of individual decentral energy hubs can help decision-makers of energy hubs such as city quarters or industrial sites evaluate the cost and carbon emission saving potentials of their flexibility. For national scale models, the carbon emissions of the electricity supply system are endogenously determined. However, low-level models (at the scale of decentral energy hubs) need this information as input. Since specific carbon emissions of national electricity supply systems fluctuate hourly, the usage of dynamic (i.e., at least hourly resolved) carbon emission factors is essential [338].

Elmada is an easy-to-use open-source Python package designed to provide dynamic electricity carbon emission factors and prices for European countries. The target group includes modelers of distributed energy hubs who need electricity market data. This is where the name **Elmada** comes from: **e**lectricity **m**arket **d**ata. Elmada is developed in the open on GitHub [339]. Each release is archived on Zenodo [275].

Acknowledgments. The contents of this chapter are based on the paper *elmada: Dynamic electricity carbon emission factors and prices for Europe* [261]. Markus Fleschutz is the primary author of this paper. The author acknowledges funding by the MTU Risam Scholarship Scheme and the German Federal Ministry of the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU) via the project WIN4Climate (No. 03KF0094 A) as part of the National Climate Initiative.

C.1 Statement of need

Dynamic CEFs are important for the environmental assessment of electricity supply in not fully decarbonized energy systems. To the best of the author's knowledge, Elmada is the first free and open-source Python interface for dynamic CEFs in Europe. This makes Elmada an important complement to existing commercial services.

At the moment, there are two main commercial services that provide an application programming interface (API) for historical dynamic CEFs: the electricityMap API [340] and the Automated Emissions Reduction from WattTime [182]. The electricityMap is maintained by Tomorrow, a startup based in Denmark, and WattTime is a nonprofit organization in the USA. However, both focus on real-time CEFs as incentive signals for DR answering the question "How clean is my electricity right now?". electricityMap is discussed in greater detail here, as it originated in Europe, which is also the primary focus of Elmada. The services of WattTime are broadly similar.

electricityMap is a software project that visualizes the CE intensity linked to the generation and consumption of electricity on a global choropleth map. Additionally, the electricityMap API provides historical, real-time (current hour), forecast, and since recently also marginal data. The calculation methods consider international energy exchanges and the fact that the list of data sources is curated by Tomorrow (the company behind it) makes it save-to-use as a live incentive signal e.g., for carbon-based DR applications. However, the use of electricityMap API requires a data-dependent payment even for the historic data, so it is not free of charge.

There are two types of dynamic CEFs:

- Grid-mix emission factors (XEFs), which represent the CE intensity based on the current generation mix of the electricity system,
- and marginal emission factors (MEFs), which quantify the CE intensity of the generators likely to react to a marginal system change.

Currently, there is no multi-national solution for modelers of decentral energy hubs searching for free historical hourly CEFs (in particular MEFs). This gap often leads to the usage of yearly average CEFs, which are potentially misleading [165]. We close this gap by providing the conveniently installable Python package Elmada that calculates XEFs and MEFs in hourly (or higher) resolution for 30 European countries for free. Elmada provides modelers a no-regret (free) entry point to European dynamic CEFs leaving it open to the modeler to later switch to a paid service that generate more accurate CEFs, e.g., through advanced methods such as the consideration of cross-border energy flows through flow tracing [164].

C.2 Functionality

Elmada calculates both types of dynamic CEFs: XEFs and MEFs. MEFs are more challenging to approximate than XEFs since MEFs require the identification of the marginal power plants per

time step. In Elmada, this is done through a merit order simulation within the power plant (PP) and piecewise linear (PWL) method described in Chapter 3.

Also, historical and simulated day-ahead electricity market prices are provided. They can be used either for the economic evaluation of electricity demands or to model the incentive signal of price-based DR.

Currently, Elmada provides data for 30 European countries and for each year since 2017. Elmada works mainly with data from the ENTSO-E Transparency Platform [242].

C.3 Current and future usage

So far, Elmada has been used in a study where MEFs, XEFs and the results of load shift simulations based on them are compared across 20 European countries in Chapter 3. In Chapters 4, 5 and 9, Elmada is used to quantify the costs and CE-saving potentials that arise from the exploitation of existing and future flexibility in decentral energy hubs.

We hope that Elmada reduces the difficulty associated with the use of dynamic CEFs and prices in the modeling of decentral energy systems.

Appendix D

Appendix to Chapter 4 (DRAF)

D.1 Screenshots of DRAF output

D.1.1 DemandAnalyzer

FIGURE D.1: Demonstration of DemandAnalyzer.

D.1.2 PeakLoadAnalyzer

FIGURE D.2: Demonstration of PeakLoadAnalyzer.

D.1.3 Result visualization

FIGURE D.3: Screenshot of DRAF with overview of results of Case Study 2 (described in Section 4.3.2).

FIGURE D.4: Screenshots of interactive Sankey diagrams. Data: Results of scenarios REF (top) and sc3 (bottom) of Case Study 3.

FIGURE D.5: Screenshot of interactive heatmap plotting of Case Study 3.

FIGURE D.6: Output of `cs.scens.sc3.plot.collectors(filter_etype="C")` of Case Study 3.

D.2 Component template definitions

This section presents the mathematical formulation of component templates which can be classified as storages, conversion technologies, demands, interfaces and a combination of them. For each technology, it contains an entity description table, the constraints, and registrations to collectors. In the entity description table, all entities (parameters and variables) are listed with source, unit, descriptions, and default value in case of a scalar parameter. All optimization variables are indicated in bold and are non-negative continuous variables if not stated otherwise. Thanks to consistent usage of naming conventions, the tables could programmatically be generated from DRAF components, which also ensures consistency between the software and the paper. Furthermore, it demonstrates DRAF's possibilities in handling metadata such as units, data source information, and docstrings.

Δ_t is the width of the according time step in hours.

FIGURE D.7: Relationship between time steps and time points.

D.2.1 Electricity grid (EG)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
ce_t^{EG}	-		kg_{CO2eq}/kWh_{el}	Carbon emission factors (via Elmada using year, freq, country, and CEF-method)
$c^{EG,addon}$	0.131		$€/kWh_{el}$	Electricity taxes and levies
$c^{EG,buypeak}$	50.000		$€/kW_{el}/a$	Peak price
$c_t^{EG,flat}$	-		$€/kWh_{el}$	Flat electricity tariff (calculated from RTP)
$c_t^{EG,rtp}$	-		$€/kWh_{el}$	Day-ahead-market-prices (via Elmada using year, freq, and country)
$c_t^{EG,tou}$	-		$€/kWh_{el}$	TOU-tariff (calculated from RTP)
c_t^{EG}	-		$€/kWh_{el}$	Chosen electricity tariff
Variables:				
$P^{EG,buypeak}$	-		kW_{el}	Peak electrical power
$P_t^{EG,buy}$	-		kW_{el}	Purchased electrical power
$P_t^{EG,sell}$	-		kW_{el}	Selling electrical power

Internal constraints:

$$P^{EG,buypeak} \geq P_t^{EG,buy} \quad (D.1)$$

$$P_t^{EG,sell} = \sum_j \Phi_{i=elSell,j,t}^{source} \quad (D.2)$$

Collector contributions:

$$\Phi_{i=el,j=eg,t}^{source} = P_t^{EG,buy} \quad (D.3)$$

$$\Phi_{i=el,j=eg,t}^{sink} = P_t^{EG,sell} \quad (D.4)$$

$$C_{j=eg}^{op} = 10^{-3} \sum_t \Delta_t \left(P_t^{EG,buy} (c_t^{EG} + c^{EG,addon}) - P_t^{EG,sell} c_t^{EG} \right) \quad (D.5)$$

$$C_{j=egPeak}^{op} = 10^{-3} P^{EG,buypeak} c^{EG,buypeak} \quad (D.6)$$

$$CE_{j=eg} = \sum_t \Delta_t (P_t^{EG,buy} - P_t^{EG,sell}) ce_t^{EG} \quad (D.7)$$

D.2.2 Fuels (**Fuel**)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
ce_f^{Fuel}	-		kgCO ₂ eq/kWh	Carbon intensity of fuel
c_f^{Fuel}	-		€/kWh	Fuel costs
c^{fuelTax}	-		€/kgCO ₂ eq	Fuel tax
Variables:				
F_f^{Fuel}	-		kW	Total fuel energy demand

Internal constraints:

$$F_f^{\text{Fuel}} = \sum_j F_{f,j} \quad (\text{D.8})$$

Collector contributions:

$$C_{j=\text{fuel}}^{\text{op}} = 10^{-3} \sum_f F_f^{\text{Fuel}} c_f^{\text{Fuel}}$$

$$CE_{j=\text{fuel}} = \sum_f F_f^{\text{Fuel}} ce_f^{\text{Fuel}}$$

$$C_{j=\text{fuelTax}}^{\text{op}} = 10^{-3} CE_{j=\text{fuel}} c^{\text{fuelTax}}$$

D.2.3 Battery energy storage (BES)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
$E^{\text{BES,capx}}$	0.000		kWh _{el}	Existing energy capacity
N^{BES}	20.000	[325]	years	Operation life
$\eta^{\text{BES,ch}}$	97.468	[341]	%	Charging efficiency
$\eta^{\text{BES,dis}}$	97.468	[341]	%	Discharging efficiency
$\eta^{\text{BES,time}}$	99.998	[297]	%/h	Efficiency due to self-discharge rate
$c^{\text{BES,inv}}$	720.000	[342]	€/kWh _{el}	CapEx
$k^{\text{BES,ini}}$	0.000		%	Initial and final energy filling share
$k^{\text{BES,inpercap}}$	70.000	[295]	%	Maximum charging power per capacity
$k^{\text{BES,outpercap}}$	70.000	[295]	%	Maximum discharging power per capacity
$k^{\text{BES,rmi}}$	2.000	[325]	%	Repair, maintenance, and inspection per year and investment cost
Variables:				
$E^{\text{BES,capn}}$	-		kWh _{el}	New capacity
E_t^{BES}	-		kWh _{el}	Electricity stored
$P_t^{\text{BES,in}}$	-		kW _{el}	Charging power
$P_t^{\text{BES,out}}$	-		kW _{el}	Discharging power

Internal constraints:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_t^{\text{BES}} = \eta^{\text{BES,time}} \begin{cases} k^{\text{BES,ini}}(E^{\text{BES,capx}} + E^{\text{BES,capn}}) & \text{if } t = t_0 \\ E_{t-1}^{\text{BES}} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\
 + \Delta_t \left(\eta^{\text{BES,ch}} P_t^{\text{BES,in}} - \frac{1}{\eta^{\text{BES,dis}}} P_t^{\text{BES,out}} \right) \quad (\text{D.9})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$E_t^{\text{BES}} \leq E^{\text{BES,capx}} + E^{\text{BES,capn}} \quad (\text{D.10})$$

$$P_t^{\text{BES,out}} \leq k^{\text{BES,outpercap}}(E^{\text{BES,capx}} + E^{\text{BES,capn}}) \quad (\text{D.11})$$

$$P_t^{\text{BES,in}} \leq k^{\text{BES,inpercap}}(E^{\text{BES,capx}} + E^{\text{BES,capn}}) \quad (\text{D.12})$$

$$E_{t|\tau}^{\text{BES}} = k^{\text{BES,ini}}(E^{\text{BES,capx}} + E^{\text{BES,capn}}) \quad (\text{D.13})$$

Collector contributions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Phi_{i=\text{el},j=\text{bes},t}^{\text{source}} &= P_t^{\text{BES,out}} \\
 \Phi_{i=\text{el},j=\text{bes},t}^{\text{sink}} &= P_t^{\text{BES,in}} \\
 C_{j=\text{bes}}^{\text{invAnn}} &= 10^{-3} E^{\text{BES,capn}} c^{\text{BES,inv}} k^{\text{af}}(r, N^{\text{BES}}) \\
 C_{j=\text{bes}}^{\text{rmi}} &= 10^{-3} E^{\text{BES,capn}} c^{\text{BES,inv}} k^{\text{BES,rmi}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Battery degradation is not considered. Please see [95] for more details regarding battery degradation in DR scenarios. A feed-in from the BES is not allowed. Following [343], $\eta^{\text{BES,ch}}$ and $\eta^{\text{BES,dis}}$ are calculated as the square root of the cycle efficiency assuming them to be symmetrical.

D.2.4 Thermal energy storage (TES)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
N^{TES}	30.000	[282]	years	Operation life
$Q_l^{\text{TES,capx}}$	-		kWh _{th}	Existing capacity
$\eta^{\text{TES,time}}$	99.500		%	Storing efficiency
$c^{\text{TES,inv}}$	28.709	[296]	€/kW _{th}	CapEx
$k_l^{\text{TES,ini}}$	-		%	Initial and final energy level share
$k^{\text{TES,inpercap}}$	50.000		%	Maximum charging power per capacity
$k^{\text{TES,outpercap}}$	50.000		%	Maximum discharging power per capacity
$k^{\text{TES,rmi}}$	0.100	[296]	%	Repair, maintenance, and inspection per year and investment cost
Variables:				
$Q_l^{\text{TES,capn}}$	-		kWh _{th}	New capacity
$Q_{t,l}^{\text{TES}}$	-		kWh _{th}	Stored heat
$\dot{Q}_{t,l}^{\text{TES,in}}$	-		kW _{th}	Storage input heat flow

Internal constraints:

$$Q_{t,l}^{\text{TES}} = \eta^{\text{TES,time}} \begin{cases} k_l^{\text{TES,ini}}(Q_l^{\text{TES,capx}} + Q_l^{\text{TES,capn}}) & \text{if } t = t_0 \\ Q_{t-1,l}^{\text{TES}} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} + \Delta_t(\eta^{\text{TES,cycle}} \dot{Q}_{t,l}^{\text{TES,in}} - \dot{Q}_{t,l}^{\text{TES,out}}) \quad (\text{D.14})$$

$$Q_{t,l}^{\text{TES}} \leq Q_l^{\text{TES,capx}} + Q_l^{\text{TES,capn}} \quad (\text{D.15})$$

$$\dot{Q}_{t,l}^{\text{TES,in}} \leq k^{\text{TES,inpercap}}(Q_l^{\text{TES,capx}} + Q_l^{\text{TES,capn}}) \quad (\text{D.16})$$

$$\dot{Q}_{t,l}^{\text{TES,out}} \leq k^{\text{TES,outpercap}}(Q_l^{\text{TES,capx}} + Q_l^{\text{TES,capn}}) \quad (\text{D.17})$$

$$Q_{t,l}^{\text{TES}} = k_l^{\text{TES,ini}}(Q_l^{\text{TES,capx}} + Q_l^{\text{TES,capn}}) \quad \forall t \in \{t_1, t|\mathcal{T}\} \quad (\text{D.18})$$

$$\dot{Q}_{t,l}^{\text{TES,in}} \in \mathbb{R}^{|T| \times |L|}$$

Collector contributions:

$$\Phi_{i,j=\text{tes},t}^{\text{source}} = \dot{Q}_{t,l}^{\text{TES,out}} \quad \forall i, l \in \mathcal{L}$$

$$\Phi_{i,j=\text{tes},t}^{\text{sink}} = \dot{Q}_{t,l}^{\text{TES,in}} \quad \forall i, l \in \mathcal{L}$$

$$C_{j=\text{tes}}^{\text{invAnn}} = 10^{-3} \sum_l Q_l^{\text{TES,capn}} c^{\text{TES,inv}} k^{\text{af}}(r, N^{\text{TES}})$$

$$C_{j=\text{tes}}^{\text{rmi}} = 10^{-3} \sum_l Q_l^{\text{TES,capn}} c^{\text{TES,inv}} k^{\text{TES,rmi}}$$

D.2.5 Photovoltaic system (PV)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
$A^{\text{PV,avail}}$	100.000		m^2	Area available for new PV
$A^{\text{PV,perpeak}}$	6.500		$\text{m}^2/\text{kW}_{\text{peak}}$	Area efficiency of new PV
N^{PV}	25.000	[323]	years	Operation life
$P^{\text{PV,capx}}$	0.000		kW_{peak}	Existing capacity
$P_t^{\text{PV,profile}}$	-	[276]	$\text{kW}_{\text{el}}/\text{kW}_{\text{peak}}$	Produced PV-power for 1 kW_{peak}
$c^{\text{PV,inv}}$	460.000	[286]	$\text{€}/\text{kW}_{\text{peak}}$	CapEx
$c^{\text{PV,oc}}$	0.028	[344]	$\text{€}/\text{kWh}_{\text{el}}$	Renewable Energy Law (EEG) levy on own consumption
$k^{\text{PV,rmi}}$	2.000	[323]	%	Repair, maintenance, and inspection per year and investment cost
Variables:				
$P^{\text{PV,capn}}$	-		kW_{peak}	New capacity
$P_t^{\text{PV,fi}}$	-		kW_{el}	Grid feed-in power
$P_t^{\text{PV,oc}}$	-		kW_{el}	Own consumption power

Internal constraints:

$$(P^{\text{PV,capx}} + P^{\text{PV,capn}})P_t^{\text{PV,profile}} = P_t^{\text{PV,fi}} + P_t^{\text{PV,oc}} \quad (\text{D.19})$$

$$P^{\text{PV,capn}} \leq \frac{A^{\text{PV,avail}}}{A^{\text{PV,perpeak}}} \quad (\text{D.20})$$

Collector contributions:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{i=\text{el},j,t}^{\text{source}} &= P_t^{\text{PV,oc}} \\ P_{t,j=\text{pv},t}^{\text{sell}} &= P_t^{\text{PV,fi}} \\ C_{j=\text{pv}}^{\text{op}} &= 10^{-3} c^{\text{PV,oc}} \sum_t \Delta_t P_t^{\text{PV,oc}} \\ C_{j=\text{pv}}^{\text{invAnn}} &= 10^{-3} P^{\text{PV,capn}} c^{\text{PV,inv}} k^{\text{af}}(r, N^{\text{PV}}) \\ C_{j=\text{pv}}^{\text{rmi}} &= 10^{-3} P^{\text{PV,capn}} c^{\text{PV,inv}} k^{\text{PV,rmi}} \end{aligned}$$

D.2.6 Battery electric vehicle (BEV)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
$E_b^{\text{BEV,cap1bat}}$	-		kWh _{el}	Capacity of one battery
$E_b^{\text{BEV,capx}}$	-		kWh _{el}	Capacity of all batteries
$P_{t,b}^{\text{BEV,drive}}$	-		kW _{el}	Discharging power for driving
$\eta^{\text{BEV,ch}}$	97.468	[341]	%	Charging efficiency
$\eta^{\text{BEV,dis}}$	97.468	[341]	%	Discharging efficiency
$\eta^{\text{BEV,time}}$	1.0		-	Storing efficiency. Must be 1.0 for the uncontrolled charging in REF
$k_b^{\text{BEV,empty}}$	-		%	Minimum allowed SOC
$k_b^{\text{BEV,full}}$	-		%	Maximum allowed SOC
$k_b^{\text{BEV,ini}}$	-		%	Initial and final SOC
$k_b^{\text{BEV,inpercap}}$	-	[295]	%	Maximum charging power per capacity
$k_b^{\text{BEV,v2xpercap}}$	-	[295]	%	Maximum V2X discharging power per capacity
$n_b^{\text{BEV,nbats}}$	-		-	Number of batteries
$y_{t,b}^{\text{BEV,avail}}$	-		-	If BEV is available for charging at time step
$z^{\text{BEV,smart}}$	0.000		-	If smart charging is allowed
$z^{\text{BEV,v2x}}$	0.000		-	If V2X is allowed
Variables:				
$E_{t,b}^{\text{BEV}}$	-		kWh _{el}	Electricity stored in BEV battery
$P_{t,b}^{\text{BEV,in}}$	-		kW _{el}	Charging power
$P_{t,b}^{\text{BEV,v2x}}$	-		kW _{el}	Discharging power for V2X
$X^{\text{BEV,penalty}}$	-		-	Penalty to ensure uncontrolled charging in REF

Internal constraints:

$$E_{t,b}^{\text{BEV}} = \eta^{\text{BEV,time}} \begin{cases} k_b^{\text{BEV,ini}} E_b^{\text{BEV,capx}} & \text{if } t = t_0 \\ E_{t-1,b}^{\text{BEV}} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} + \Delta_t (\eta^{\text{BEV,ch}} P_{t,b}^{\text{BEV,in}} - \frac{1}{\eta^{\text{BEV,dis}}} (P_{t,b}^{\text{BEV,drive}} + P_{t,b}^{\text{BEV,v2x}})) \quad (\text{D.21})$$

$$E_{t,b}^{\text{BEV}} \leq k_b^{\text{BEV,full}} E_b^{\text{BEV,capx}} \quad (\text{D.22})$$

$$E_{t,b}^{\text{BEV}} \geq k_b^{\text{BEV,empty}} E_b^{\text{BEV,capx}} \quad (\text{D.23})$$

$$E_b^{\text{BEV,capx}} = n_b^{\text{BEV,nbats}} E_b^{\text{BEV,cap1bat}} \quad (\text{D.24})$$

$$P_{t,b}^{\text{BEV,in}} \leq y_{t,b}^{\text{BEV,avail}} k_b^{\text{BEV,inpercap}} E_b^{\text{BEV,capx}} \quad (\text{D.25})$$

$$P_{t,b}^{\text{BEV,v2x}} \leq z^{\text{BEV,v2x}} y_{t,b}^{\text{BEV,avail}} k_b^{\text{BEV,v2xpercap}} E_b^{\text{BEV,capx}} \quad (\text{D.26})$$

$$E_{t|\tau_1,b}^{\text{BEV}} = k_b^{\text{BEV,ini}} E_b^{\text{BEV,capx}} \quad (\text{D.27})$$

$$X^{\text{BEV,penalty}} = (1 - z^{\text{BEV,smart}}) \sum_{t,b} t P_{t,b}^{\text{BEV,in}} \quad (\text{D.28})$$

Collector contributions:

$$X_{j=\text{bev}}^{\text{penalty}} = X^{\text{BEV,penalty}}$$

$$\Phi_{i=\text{el},j=\text{bev},t}^{\text{source}} = \sum_b P_{t,b}^{\text{BEV,v2x}}$$

$$\Phi_{i=\text{el},j=\text{bev},t}^{\text{sink}} = \sum_b P_{t,b}^{\text{BEV,in}}$$

D.2.7 Combined heat and power (CHP)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
N^{CHP}	25.000	[345]	years	Operation life
$P^{\text{CHP,capx}}$	0.000		kW_{el}	Existing capacity
$P^{\text{CHP,max}}$	100000.000		kW_{el}	Big-M number (upper bound for CAPn + CAPx)
$\eta^{\text{CHP,el}}$	40.000	[346]	%	Electric efficiency
$\eta^{\text{CHP,th}}$	45.000	[346]	%	Thermal efficiency
$c^{\text{CHP,inv}}$	589.458	[291]	$\text{€}/\text{kW}_{\text{el}}$	CapEx
$c^{\text{CHP,oc}}$	0.028	[344]	$\text{€}/\text{kWh}_{\text{el}}$	Renewable Energy Law (EEG) levy on own consumption
$k^{\text{CHP,minpl}}$	50.000		%	Minimal allowed part load
$k^{\text{CHP,rmi}}$	18.000	[345]	%	Repair, maintenance, and inspection per year and investment cost
Variables:				
$\dot{F}_{t,f}^{\text{CHP}}$	-		kW	Consumed fuel energy flow
$P^{\text{CHP,capn}}$	-		kW_{el}	New capacity
$P_t^{\text{CHP,fi}}$	-		kW_{el}	Grid feed-in power
$P_t^{\text{CHP,oc}}$	-		kW_{el}	Own consumption power
P_t^{CHP}	-		kW_{el}	Producing power
Y_t^{CHP}	-		-	Binary: If in operation
\dot{Q}_t^{CHP}	-		kW_{th}	Producing heat flow

Internal constraints:

$$P_t^{\text{CHP}} = \eta^{\text{CHP,el}} \sum_f \dot{F}_{t,f}^{\text{CHP}} \quad (\text{D.29})$$

$$\dot{Q}_t^{\text{CHP}} = \eta^{\text{CHP,th}} \sum_f \dot{F}_{t,f}^{\text{CHP}} \quad (\text{D.30})$$

$$P_t^{\text{CHP}} \leq P^{\text{CHP,capx}} + P^{\text{CHP,capn}} \quad (\text{D.31})$$

$$P_t^{\text{CHP}} = P_t^{\text{CHP,fi}} + P_t^{\text{CHP,oc}} \quad (\text{D.32})$$

$$P_t^{\text{CHP}} \leq Y_t^{\text{CHP}} P^{\text{CHP,max}} \quad (\text{D.33})$$

$$P_t^{\text{CHP}} \geq k^{\text{CHP,minpl}} (P^{\text{CHP,capx}} + P^{\text{CHP,capn}}) - P^{\text{CHP,max}} (1 - Y_t^{\text{CHP}}) \quad (\text{D.34})$$

$$Y_t^{\text{CHP}} \in \{0, 1\}$$

Collector contributions:

$$\Phi_{i=\text{heat2},j=\text{chp},t}^{\text{source}} = \dot{Q}_t^{\text{CHP}}$$

$$\Phi_{i=\text{el},j=\text{chp},t}^{\text{source}} = P_t^{\text{CHP,oc}}$$

$$P_{t,j=\text{chp}}^{\text{sell}} = P_t^{\text{CHP,fi}}$$

$$F_{f,j=\text{chp}} = \sum_t \Delta_t \dot{F}_{t,f}^{\text{CHP}}$$

$$C_{j=\text{chp}}^{\text{op}} = 10^{-3} c^{\text{CHP,oc}} \sum_t \Delta_t P_t^{\text{CHP,oc}}$$

$$C_{j=\text{chp}}^{\text{invAnn}} = 10^{-3} P^{\text{CHP,capn}} c^{\text{CHP,inv}} k^{\text{af}}(r, N^{\text{CHP}})$$

$$C_{j=\text{chp}}^{\text{rmi}} = 10^{-3} P^{\text{CHP,capn}} c^{\text{CHP,inv}} k^{\text{CHP,rmi}}$$

D.2.8 Heat-only boiler (HOB)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
N^{HOB}	15.000	[345]	years	Operation life
$\dot{Q}^{\text{HOB,capx}}$	0.000		kW _{th}	Existing capacity
η^{HOB}	90.000	[345]	%	Thermal efficiency
$c^{\text{HOB,inv}}$	57.133	[292]	€/kW _{th}	CapEx
$k^{\text{HOB,rmi}}$	18.000	[345]	%	Repair, maintenance, and inspection per year and investment cost
Variables:				
$\dot{F}_{t,f}^{\text{HOB}}$	-		kW	Input fuel energy flow
$\dot{Q}^{\text{HOB,capn}}$	-		kW _{th}	New capacity
\dot{Q}_t^{HOB}	-		kW _{th}	Output heat flow

Internal constraints:

$$\dot{Q}_t^{\text{HOB}} = \eta^{\text{HOB}} \sum_f \dot{F}_{t,f}^{\text{HOB}} \quad (\text{D.35})$$

$$\dot{Q}_t^{\text{HOB}} \leq \dot{Q}^{\text{HOB,capx}} + \dot{Q}^{\text{HOB,capn}} \quad (\text{D.36})$$

Collector contributions:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{i=\text{heat2},j=\text{hob},t}^{\text{source}} &= \dot{Q}_t^{\text{HOB}} \\ F_{f,j=\text{hob}} &= \sum_t \Delta_t \dot{F}_{t,f}^{\text{HOB}} \\ C_{j=\text{hob}}^{\text{invAnn}} &= 10^{-3} \dot{Q}^{\text{HOB,capn}} c^{\text{HOB,inv}} k^{\text{af}}(r, N^{\text{HOB}}) \\ C_{j=\text{hob}}^{\text{rmi}} &= 10^{-3} \dot{Q}^{\text{HOB,capn}} c^{\text{HOB,inv}} k^{\text{HOB,rmi}} \end{aligned}$$

D.2.9 Power-to-heat (P2H)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
N^{P2H}	30.000		years	Operation life
$\dot{Q}^{\text{P2H,capx}}$	0.000		kW_{th}	Existing capacity
η^{P2H}	90.000	[347]	%	Efficiency
$c^{\text{P2H,inv}}$	100.000	[293]	$\text{€}/\text{kW}_{\text{th}}$	System CapEx
$k^{\text{P2H,rmi}}$	0.000		%	Repair, maintenance, and inspection per year and investment cost
Variables:				
P_t^{P2H}	-		kW_{el}	Consuming power
$\dot{Q}^{\text{P2H,capn}}$	-		kW_{th}	New capacity
\dot{Q}_t^{P2H}	-		kW_{th}	Producing heat flow

Internal constraints:

$$\dot{Q}_t^{\text{P2H}} = \eta^{\text{P2H}} P_t^{\text{P2H}} \quad (\text{D.37})$$

$$\dot{Q}_t^{\text{P2H}} \leq \dot{Q}^{\text{P2H,capx}} + \dot{Q}^{\text{P2H,capn}} \quad (\text{D.38})$$

Collector contributions:

$$\Phi_{i=\text{heat2},j=\text{p2h},t}^{\text{source}} = \dot{Q}_t^{\text{P2H}}$$

$$\Phi_{i=\text{el},j=\text{p2h},t}^{\text{sink}} = P_t^{\text{P2H}}$$

$$C_{j=\text{p2h}}^{\text{invAnn}} = 10^{-3} \dot{Q}^{\text{P2H,capn}} c^{\text{P2H,inv}} k^{\text{af}}(r, N^{\text{P2H}})$$

$$C_{j=\text{p2h}}^{\text{rmi}} = 10^{-3} \dot{Q}^{\text{P2H,capn}} c^{\text{P2H,inv}} k^{\text{P2H,rmi}}$$

D.2.10 Electric heat pump (HP)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
N^{HP}	18.000	[348]	years	Operation life
$\dot{Q}^{\text{HP,capx}}$	0.000		kW_{th}	Existing heating capacity
$\dot{Q}^{\text{HP,max}}$	100000.000		kW_{th}	Big-M number (upper bound for CAPn + CAPx)
η^{HP}	50.000	[349]	%	Ratio of reaching the ideal COP (exergy efficiency)
$\vartheta_c^{\text{HP,cond}}$	-		$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Condensation-side temperature
$\vartheta_e^{\text{HP,eva}}$	-		$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Evaporation-side temperature
$c^{\text{HP,inv}}$	285.788	[350]	$\text{€}/\text{kW}_{\text{el}}$	CapEx
$k^{\text{HP,rmi}}$	2.500	[348]	%	Repair, maintenance, and inspection per year and investment cost
$n^{\text{HP,modes}}$	1.000		-	Maximum number of parallel operation modes
Variables:				
$P_{t,e,c}^{\text{HP}}$	-		kW_{el}	Consuming power
$Y_{t,e,c}^{\text{HP}}$	-		-	Binary: If source and sink are connected at time-step
$\dot{Q}^{\text{HP,capn}}$	-		kW_{th}	New heating capacity
$\dot{Q}_{t,e,c}^{\text{HP,cond}}$	-		kW_{th}	Heat flow released on condensation side
$\dot{Q}_{t,e,c}^{\text{HP,eva}}$	-		kW_{th}	Heat flow absorbed on evaporation side

Internal constraints:

$$\dot{Q}_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP,cond}} = \text{COP}_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP}} P_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP}} \quad (\text{D.39})$$

$$\dot{Q}_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP,cond}} = \dot{Q}_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP,eva}} + P_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP}} \quad (\text{D.40})$$

$$\dot{Q}_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP}} \leq Y_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP}} \dot{Q}^{\text{HP,max}} \quad (\text{D.41})$$

$$\sum_{c,n} \dot{Q}_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP}} \leq \dot{Q}^{\text{HP,capx}} + \dot{Q}^{\text{HP,capn}} \quad (\text{D.42})$$

$$\sum_c \sum_n Y_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP}} \leq n^{\text{HP,modes}} \quad (\text{D.43})$$

$$\text{COP}_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP}} = \begin{cases} 100 & \text{if } \vartheta_{t,c}^{\text{HP,cond}} \leq \vartheta_n^{\text{HP,eva}} \\ \eta^{\text{HP}} \text{COP}_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP,carnot}} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (\text{D.44})$$

$$\text{COP}_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP,carnot}} = \frac{\vartheta_{t,c}^{\text{HP,cond}} + 273}{\vartheta_{t,c}^{\text{HP,cond}} - \vartheta_n^{\text{HP,eva}}} \quad (\text{D.45})$$

$$Y_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP}} \in \{0, 1\}$$

Collector contributions:

$$\Phi_{i,j=\text{hp},t}^{\text{source}} = \dot{Q}_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP,cond}} \quad \forall i, c \in \mathcal{H}$$

$$\Phi_{i,j=\text{hp},t}^{\text{sink}} = \dot{Q}_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP,eva}} \quad \forall i, n \in \mathcal{N}$$

$$\Phi_{i=\text{el},j=\text{hp},t}^{\text{sink}} = P_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP}}$$

$$C_{j=\text{hp}}^{\text{invAnn}} = 10^{-3} \dot{Q}^{\text{HP,capn}} c^{\text{HP,inv}} k^{\text{af}}(r, N^{\text{HP}})$$

$$C_{j=\text{hp}}^{\text{rmi}} = 10^{-3} \dot{Q}^{\text{HP,capn}} c^{\text{HP,inv}} k^{\text{HP,rmi}}$$

D.2.11 Heat downgrading (**H2H1**)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
Variables:				
\dot{Q}_t^{H2H1}	-		kW _{th}	Heat down-grading

Collector contributions:

$$\Phi_{i=\text{heat1},j=\text{h2h1},t}^{\text{source}} = \dot{Q}_t^{\text{H2H1}}$$

$$\Phi_{i=\text{heat2},j=\text{h2h1},t}^{\text{sink}} = \dot{Q}_t^{\text{H2H1}}$$

D.2.12 Product demand (**pDem**)

Formulation partly based on Chapter 6.

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
$\dot{G}_{t,s}^{\text{pDem}}$	-		t/h	Product demand

Collector contributions:

$$\Phi_{i=\text{prod},j=\text{pdem},t}^{\text{sink}} = \dot{G}_{t,s}^{\text{pDem}}$$

D.2.13 Production process (PP)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
$P_m^{\text{PP,capx}}$	-		kW _{el}	
$\eta_{s,m}^{\text{PP}}$	-		%	Production efficiency
$c^{\text{PP,sc}}$	10.000		€/change	Costs per sort change
$c^{\text{PP,su}}$	10.000		€/SU	Costs per start up
$k_m^{\text{PP,minpl}}$	-		%	Minimum part load
$y_{t,m}^{\text{PP,avail}}$	-	-	-	If machine is available at time step
$y_{s,m}^{\text{PP,compat}}$	-	-	-	If machine and sort is compatible
Variables:				
$C^{\text{PP,sc}}$	-		k€	Total cost of sort change
$C^{\text{PP,su}}$	-		k€	Total cost of start up
$P_{t,s,m}^{\text{PP}}$	-		kW _{el}	Nominal consumption power of machine
$Y_{t,s,m}^{\text{PP,op}}$	-	-	-	Binary: If machine is in operation
$Y_{t,s,m}^{\text{PP,sc}}$	-	-	-	Binary: If sort has just changed
$Y_{t,m}^{\text{PP,su}}$	-	-	-	Binary: If machine just started up
$\dot{G}_{t,s,m}^{\text{PP}}$	-		t/h	Production of machine

Internal constraints:

$$\dot{G}_{t,s,m}^{\text{PP}} = \eta_{s,m}^{\text{PP}} y_{s,m}^{\text{PP,compat}} y_{t,m}^{\text{PP,avail}} \quad (\text{D.46})$$

$$P_{t,s,m}^{\text{PP}} \leq Y_{t,s,m}^{\text{PP,op}} P_m^{\text{PP,capx}} \quad (\text{D.47})$$

$$P_{t,s,m}^{\text{PP}} \geq Y_{t,s,m}^{\text{PP,op}} k_m^{\text{PP,minpl}} P_m^{\text{PP,capx}} \quad (\text{D.48})$$

$$C^{\text{PP,su}} = 10^{-3} \sum_{t,m} Y_{t,m}^{\text{PP,su}} c^{\text{PP,su}} \quad (\text{D.49})$$

$$Y_{t,m}^{\text{PP,su}} \geq \sum_s Y_{t,s,m}^{\text{PP,op}} - \sum_s Y_{t-1,s,m}^{\text{PP,op}} \quad (\text{D.50})$$

$$C^{\text{PP,sc}} = 10^{-3} \sum_{t,m} Y_{t,m}^{\text{PP,sc}} c^{\text{PP,sc}} \quad (\text{D.51})$$

$$Y_{t,s,m}^{\text{PP,sc}} \geq Y_{t,s,m}^{\text{PP,op}} - Y_{t-1,s,m}^{\text{PP,op}} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \setminus \{t_0\} \quad (\text{D.52})$$

$$\sum_s Y_{t,s,m}^{\text{PP,op}} \leq 1 \quad (\text{D.53})$$

Collector contributions:

$$\Phi_{i=\text{prod},j=\text{pp},t}^{\text{source}} = \sum_m \dot{G}_{t,s,m}^{\text{PP}}$$

$$P_{i=\text{prod},j=\text{pp},t}^{\text{sink}} = \sum_{s,m} P_{t,s,m}^{\text{PP}}$$

$$C_{j=\text{pp}}^{\text{op}} = C^{\text{PP,sc}} + C^{\text{PP,su}}$$

D.2.14 Product storage (PS)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
$G_s^{\text{PS,capx}}$	-		t	Existing storage capacity of product
N^{PS}	50.000		a	Operation life
$c^{\text{PS,inv}}$	1000.000		€/t	Investment cost
$k_s^{\text{PS,ini}}$	-		%	Initial storage filling level
$k_s^{\text{PS,min}}$	-		%	Share of minimal required storage filling level
Variables:				
$E^{\text{PS,delta}}$	-		kWh _{el}	Energy equivalent
$G_s^{\text{PS,capn}}$	-		t	New capacity
$G_s^{\text{PS,delta}}$	-		t	Final time step deviation from init
$G_{t,s}^{\text{PS}}$	-		t	Storage filling level

Internal constraints:

$$G_{t,s}^{\text{PS}} \leq (G_s^{\text{PS,capx}} + G_s^{\text{PS,capn}}) \quad (\text{D.54})$$

$$G_{t,s}^{\text{PS}} \geq k_s^{\text{PS,min}} (G_s^{\text{PS,capx}} + G_s^{\text{PS,capn}}) \quad (\text{D.55})$$

$$G_{t|\mathcal{T}|,s}^{\text{PS}} = k_s^{\text{PS,ini}} (G_s^{\text{PS,capx}} + G_s^{\text{PS,capn}}) - G_s^{\text{PS,delta}} \quad (\text{D.56})$$

$$E^{\text{PS,delta}} = \sum_s G_s^{\text{PS,delta}} \max_m \frac{1}{\eta_{s,m}^{\text{PP}}} \quad (\text{D.57})$$

Collector contributions:

$$\Phi_{i=\text{prod},j=\text{ps},t}^{\text{sink}} = \frac{1}{\Delta_t} \begin{cases} (k_s^{\text{PS,ini}} (G_s^{\text{PS,capx}} + G_s^{\text{PS,capn}}) - G_{t,s}^{\text{PS}}) & \text{if } t = t_0 \\ (G_{t-1,s}^{\text{PS}} - G_{t,s}^{\text{PS}}) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$C_{j=\text{ps}}^{\text{op}} = 3 \times 10^{-3} \left(\frac{\sum_t c_t^{\text{EG}}}{|\mathcal{T}|} + c^{\text{EG,addon}} \right) E^{\text{PS,delta}}$$

$$C_{j=\text{ps}}^{\text{invAnn}} = 10^{-3} \sum_s \dot{G}_s^{\text{PS,capn}} c^{\text{PS,inv}} k^{\text{af}}(r, N^{\text{PS}})$$

D.2.15 Cooling demand (cDem)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
$\dot{Q}_{t,n}^{\text{cDem}}$	-		kW_{th}	Cooling demand
$\vartheta_n^{\text{cDem,in}}$	-		$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Cooling inlet temperature
$\vartheta_n^{\text{cDem,out}}$	-		$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Cooling outlet temperature

Collector contributions:

$$\Phi_{i,j=\text{cdem},t}^{\text{source}} = \dot{Q}_{t,n}^{\text{cDem}} \quad \forall i, n \in \mathcal{N}$$

D.2.16 Heating demand (hDem)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
$\dot{Q}_{t,h}^{\text{hDem}}$	-		kW_{th}	Heating demand
$\vartheta_h^{\text{hDem,in}}$	-		$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Heating inlet temperature
$\vartheta_h^{\text{hDem,out}}$	-		$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Heating outlet temperature

Collector contributions:

$$\Phi_{i,j=\text{hdem},t}^{\text{sink}} = \dot{Q}_{t,h}^{\text{hDem}} \quad \forall i, h \in \mathcal{H}$$

D.2.17 Electricity demand (eDem)

Symbol	Default	Src	Unit	Description
P_t^{eDem}	-		kW_{el}	Electricity demand from standard load profile G3: Business continuous

Collector contributions:

$$\Phi_{i=\text{el},j=\text{el},t}^{\text{sink}} = P_t^{\text{eDem}}$$

Appendix E

Appendix to Chapter 5 (From prosumer to flexumer)

E.1 Detailed parameters

TABLE E.1: General parameters used in the case study.

Symbol	Description	Value
r	Discount rate	10%
Δt	Time step width	1h
$ \mathcal{T} $	Number of time steps	8760
-	Assumed heat exchanger temperature difference for HPs	5°C
$\eta^{\text{HP,Carnot}}$	Ratio of reaching ideal Carnot COP	50% [351]
$n^{\text{HP,modes}}$	Maximum parallel HP operation modes	1
$\dot{Q}^{\text{HP,max}}$	Big-M number (upper bound for $\dot{Q}_{t,c,n}^{\text{HP}}$)	100 MW _{th}

E.2 Detailed results

TABLE E.2: Nominal capacities of new technologies in kW or kWh (see base unit of Table 5.1). Colors highlight differences between scenarios. All-zero columns were removed.

	c_base					c_strict										c_scaled					
	HP	P2H	PV	TES	WT	BES	Elc	FC	H2S	HP	P2H	PV	TES	WT	BES	HP	P2H	PV	TES	WT	
REF	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
noFlex	918	105	1,356	0	0	0	0	0	0	918	105	1,356	0	0	0	907	314	3,077	0	18,982	
someFlex	907	197	2,853	0	0	0	0	0	0	907	197	2,853	0	0	0	907	485	3,077	0	19,492	
fullFlex	760	222	3,028	3,216	0	0	0	0	0	760	222	3,028	3,216	0	14	757	1,414	3,077	8,986	20,875	
noFlex_d	1,723	485	3,077	0	2,183	0	0	0	0	1,639	567	3,077	0	19,413	0	1,546	659	3,077	0	19,413	
someFlex_d	1,049	863	3,077	0	2,140	0	0	0	0	1,106	716	3,077	0	19,492	0	1,045	872	3,077	0	19,492	
fullFlex_d	899	1,082	3,077	14,675	2,344	169	456	804	189,953	969	1,592	3,077	27,807	5,347	18	1,085	2,214	3,077	22,060	21,859	

FIGURE E.1: Comparison of $\hat{P}^{EG, buy}$, $W^{EG, buy}$, π -rate, and ε -rate of all optimized scenarios of all contexts. Here, decarb. refer to the decarbonization scenarios noFlex_d, someFlex_d, and fullFlex_d.

FIGURE E.2: Violin plot of purchased (+) and sold (-) electricity.

FIGURE E.3: Number of full V2X discharges per year of average BEV battery (i.e., total annual energy V2X discharge divided by the usable battery capacity).

FIGURE E.4: Heatmaps of purchased (+) and sold (-) electricity in % based on maximum purchased and sold electricity, respectively.

FIGURE E.5: Electricity balance of the c_base context for one week (Monday–Sunday) in May 2019.

FIGURE E.6: Sankey diagrams of annual energy sums for the **c_base** context.

FIGURE E.7: Sankey diagrams of annual energy sums for the c_strict context.

FIGURE E.8: Sankey diagrams of annual energy sums for the `c_scaled` context.

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